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MUNDARIJA | TABLE OF CONTENTS | СОДЕРЖАНИЕ

1.	READING AND READING COMPREHENSION BY A2 STUDENTS Кодирова Сарвиноз Махмуджон кизи	100
2.	NATURAL MONUMENTS AND THEIR PROTECTION Obidova Shoira Azamatovna	108
3.	ЧИЗИҚЛИ ЭЛЕКТР ЗАНЖИРЛАРИДА ЎТКИНЧИ ЖАРАЁН ТАҲЛИЛИНИНГ ВАҚТ УСУЛИ Бабажанова Тазахан Мырзабаевна, Атажанова Гулзар Казакбаевна	112
4.	ПЛАСТИК МАТЕРИАЛЛАР ЁРДАМИДА ДИДАКТИК АШЁЛАР ТАЙЁРЛАШ МЕТОДИКАСИГА ОИД ТАЖРИБАЛАР Валижон Қодиров, Ойбарчин Маҳмудова	116
5.	FICTION IS A FACTOR IN THE FORMATION OF NATIONAL EDUCATION AND SPIRITUALITY IN CHILDREN Valijon Kadirov, Dildora Abdullajonova	124
6.	ENLIGHTENMENT-IDEOLOGICAL, LINGUISTIC, GENERAL AESTHETIC COMMONALITIES BETWEEN THE TWO PERIODS Khakimova Muhabbat Alimovna	128
7.	THE HISTORY OF THE RUSSIAN EPISTOLARY NOVEL IN EIGHTEENTH CENTURY Manzila Nuriddinova Habibova	135
8.	VARIOUS TYPES OF ASSESSMENT IN LANGUAGE TEACHING AND LEARNING Nematova Zebo Tursunboevna	140
9.	METHODOLOGICAL BASIS OF MASTERING FOREIGN LANGUAGE Bakaev N.B.	146
10.	TRANSFER OF PHRASEOLOGICAL UNITS DURING TRANSLATION Mirzayunosova Ziyoda Ibragimovna	151
11.	"MALIK AL-ULAMO" DEYA TA'RIFLANGAN AJDODIMIZ HAQIDA Mamasidiqov Fazliddin Muzaffar o'g'li	154
12.	СУД ҲУЖЖАТИНИ ИЖРО ЭТМАСЛИК ЖИНОЯТИНИ РИВОЖЛАНИШИ ҲАМДА ТАКОМИЛЛАШТИРИШ МУАОММОЛАРИ Абдуллаев Тўлқин Бектемирович	158
13.	ЖАМОАТ ХАВФСИЗЛИГИНИ ТАЪМИНЛАШНИНГ ҲУҚУҚИЙ АСОСЛАРИНИ ТАКОМИЛЛАШТИРИШ Жолдасов Айдос Фархадович	164
14.	O'ZBEK MILLIY MADANIYATINING TURKIY MADANIYATLAR RIVOJIGA TA'SIRI Aziza Nazirkulova Abduvaliyevna	172
15.	БИЛЛИНГВИЗМ В УЗБЕКСКОЙ И ЧИКАНСКОЙ ЛИТЕРАТУРЕ. МАРТИН ЭСПАДА И САДРИДДИН АЙНИЙ КАК ИЗВЕСТНЫЕ ДВУЯЗЫЧНЫЕ ПРЕДСТАВИТЕЛИ	176

Зиёдиллаева Махбуба Эрматовна

16.	АБУЛ БАРАКОТ НАСАФИЙ ИЛМИЙ МЕРОСИННИГ ТАСНИФИ Наргиза Абдурахманова	183
17.	BOLALAR INTELLEKTINI RIVOJLANTIRISH USULLARI Ismoilova Zulayxo Islom qizi	189
18.	THE MAGIC OF THE WORD IN THE PROCESS OF ARTISTIC TRANSLATION Ibrokhimova Markhabo Ulugbek kizi	193

READING AND READING COMPREHENSION BY A2 STUDENTS

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Reading is connected with influence, function, form, action, process and other aspects. Reading is a complex type of speech activity; it has played and continues to play an important role in individual and social life. Research in teaching to read shows that, according to the assessment, reading as a type of speech activity has a long history and shows a number of problems and its approaches.

Contemporary science fiction writer Neil Gaiman noted that "reading is an education that doesn't end the day we leave school or university, it's leisure, it's a refuge, and it's access to information."

In order to develop the ability to understand the content of the text being read, first of all, students should be

ABSTRACT

The article provides information about reading and a brief description of the main types of speech activity. And also highlighted are the levels of reading comprehension, such as literal, analytical and critical understanding, which depends on many factors.

introduced to what a book is, what genres of works are, and how to receive information, analyze and comprehend it. Students should become familiar with the fact that books can differ:

- by structure and form: picture books, encyclopedias, panoramic books, mono-editions with one work, collections, including several works or series of books;
- by type of information transfer: paper books, audio books, on-line books, etc.;
- by genre: folk tales, science fiction, fantasy, short stories, poetry, historical works, scientific publications, encyclopedias, journalism, biography/auto-biography, books about art (about music, painting, dancing)[1]. In discussing this

topic, the following stages can be noted when reading:

Before reading - students should be taught to predict, assume, build hypotheses about how the plot of the work will unfold, build guesses that, after reading the text, will be confirmed or refuted. This allows you to track the process of understanding the text: while reading, students will try to find answers to the questions posed before reading, which contributes to a deeper understanding of the text.

During the reading process, the process is organized using different forms of reading: model, collaborative, guided and independent reading (for information on reading forms, see the Introduction and Module 4. Fluent reading).

After reading - students should be taught to find the main information (the hero / characters of the work, what events occurred and what is their sequence, place and time of action), the ability to generalize, compare and contrast the information received from the text, analyze, formulate their opinion and express their attitude to reading, evaluate your reading comprehension. You can also highlight the levels of reading comprehension:

Literal understanding. The first level of understanding lies in the ability to repeat or recreate the text, highlight the main information, identify the main characters, idea, place, time, chronology, plot, action.

analytical understanding. The next level of understanding is the ability to reveal the meaning laid down by the author, to understand cause-and-effect relationships, the ability to analyze and interpret (interpret), compare and contrast familiar and new information.

Critical understanding. And, finally, critical or evaluative understanding is the ability to form and express one's attitude to the text and evaluate one's reading comprehension.

Reading comprehension depends on many factors:

- from understanding the meanings of words;

- from the correctness of reading (if the student reads the words incorrectly, he does not understand the meaning of the whole sentence);

- from fluency (speed) of reading (if the student still reads syllable by syllable, then it is difficult for him/her to "grasp" the meaning of what was read);

- life experience and knowledge of students;

- from the ability to "include" in reading memory, thinking, imagination.

Brief description of the main types of speech activity

There are oral and written speech, each of which has two sides - receptive and expressive speech (Fig. 1) [2].

Rice. 1. The main types of speech activity.

The author Olga Zelinkova defines the term SRSHNN as: „obtíže při osvojování základních školních dovedností – čtení (dyslexie), psaní (dysgrafie, dysortografie), počítání (dyskalkulie) i pohybových dovedností (dyspraxie).

SRRSshN are interpreted quite broadly. In the above definition of Zelinkova, not only dyslexia is mentioned, but also other types of disorders - dysgraphia, dysorhography and others.

Dyslexia is a reading disorder. This is the best-known concept of the whole group of specific learning disorders. Initially, the term referred to all types of such violations. Dyslexia can be defined as text-comprehension difficulties characterized by an inability to perceive not only handwritten but also printed text. Dyslexia is characterized by the fact that despite problems with reading, the general level of intelligence of students is at the same level as that of students without specific impairments.

Dysgraphia is a writing disorder. Writing impairment is usually included in the definition of dyslexia. The handwriting of students with dysgraphia is illegible, too small or too large. The shapes of the letters and their connections are usually irregular. It is difficult for students to memorize letters and reproduce them in writing.

Dysorhography is a violation of spelling. This disorder is very often observed simultaneously with dyslexia and dysgraphia. Dysorhography does not concern all areas of grammar, only the so-called specific dysorhographic phenomena. Students with this disorder most often, for example, confuse short and long vowels in the Czech language, do not distinguish between the syllables di-dy, ti-ty, ni-ny. Students with dysorhography add, modify, and omit letters or entire syllables.

The prefix dis- always means warp. In terms of psychological development, dysfunction refers to a function that is not fully developed. Students with dyslexia may also experience speech, concentration, or spatial problems along with SSRS. It is important to note that the slow development of reading, writing and

counting skills in students with a low level of intelligence does not belong to the disorders [3].

Therefore, intermediary activity can easily be associated with non-verbal communication activities, such as verbalization of non-verbal messages.

Reading comprehension typically requires the following skills and knowledge resources:

1. the ability to decipher graphic forms for effective word recognition (phonological, spelling, morphological and semantic processing);

2. the ability to automatically access the meaning of a large number of words (vocabulary);

3. the ability to extract meaning from grammatical information at the level of phrases and sentences (effective grammatical analysis);

4. the ability to combine meanings at the sentence level to create more

a wide network of semantic relations (structuring at the level of discourse and recognition

genres);

5. ability to use different reading strategies with more complex texts

(including goal setting, output and monitoring);

6. ability to draw on life experience, as appropriate;

7. ability to evaluate, integrate and synthesize information from text for

formation of a situational model of understanding (what the reader learns from the text);

8. the ability to freely maintain these processes for a long period

time;

9. ability to continue reading and use textual information appropriately

way in accordance with the purposes of reading [4].

Reading allows you to analyze the degree of perception and acquisition of data in writing.

form. Two types of testing often fall into this class: tests with gaps

(close tests) and texts with all sorts of tasks. Texts with spaces

consider the ability to reconstruct missing significant parts,

maintaining context. In this case, as a rule, the conditions offer short

texts filled with gaps, and these very gaps, the student must fill in, not

forgetting to get to the point.

In tasks, reading becomes more difficult not only in grammatical terms, but there are also

Criteria that help create reinforcing tasks for checking reading. Such

criteria exist for levels A1-C2. We will analyze A1, A2, B1, B2, C1.

For reading characters the following types of tasks [6]:

1. establishing compliance;

2. establishing the sequence of parts of the text;

3. choice from several options only one correct answer;

4. identification;

5. alternative choice;

6. filling in tables or charts;

7. filling in gaps in the text;

8. answers to the given (in the text) questions;

Level A1 is characterized by the following criteria for tasks:

1. No more than 5-10 sentences should be used.

2. The number of words is not more than 20-30.

3. At this level, reinforcing tasks should be no more than 1-2, with a full understanding of the text.

4. Topic, grammar and vocabulary should be familiar.

5. Such reinforcing types of tasks are well suited, such as: choosing from several

options, only one correct answer (no more than 4-6 answer options from the text) or

filling in the gaps (no more than 5-6 gaps from the text), answering questions (no more than 1

question).

Let's show in practice an example of a small text, which is usually shown on

level A1 above the listed criteria (number of words, sentences, simple

grammar and vocabulary):

"I am Jane. I am 18. I am a simple girl who just loves to live. I dream of living on my own when I

grow up. I want to create a strong family and be financially, emotionally independent and strong.»

Level A2 is characterized by the following criteria for tasks:

1. No more than 15-20 sentences should be used

2. The text should not exceed 400-500 words.

3. There can be no more than 2-3 reinforcing tasks at this level.

4. I can read texts with a small amount of unfamiliar vocabulary that does not interfere

general understanding of the text.

5. The following reinforcing types of tasks are suitable: alternative choice (number of

sentences from the general text for reading no more than 10), fill in the gaps in the text

(the number of sentences from the general text is not more than 7-8), establishing correspondence (Not

more than 4-5 matches from the text), answers to questions (no more than 2 questions).

At level A2, the text will be larger in quantity, because the paragraph from level A1 is preserved,

thus, the number of sentences and words for this level fit the criteria.

We will show only a new paragraph (continuation) for this level, the subject of which has not been changed.

The new paragraph contains a small amount of unfamiliar vocabulary and grammar:

"I like that I can spend time with my friends. We often go for a walk together. I can talk to them

for hours. They can not only help me, but also support me in any situation. My mother is a very wise

woman. She always understands me.

As a result, we can say that Reading occupies a significant place in a person's life, starting from the first years of a child's life and ending with mature wisdom. Representatives of various areas of science addressed the study of the problem of reading: teachers (V. A. Sukhomlinsky, K. D. Ushinsky, T. I. Alieva, T. G. Galaktionova, Z. A. Gritsenko, S. V. Evtyushkin, I. G. Zhukova, S. A. Ikramova, O. V. Kiyakina, E. S. Salakhutdinova, N. N. Svetlovskaya, I. P. Smetankina, etc.), psychologists (L. S. Vygotsky, V. V. Davydov, T. G. Egorov, A. A. Leontiev, E. V. Khomskeya, L. S. Tsvetkova, D. B. Elkonin, G. A. Tsukerman, and others), philosophers and sociologists (I. A. Butenko, Yu. A. Eliseeva, E. A. Kolosova, R. A. Trofimova, A. I. Shalimova, etc.), bibliologists and library scientists (V. A. Borodina, S. M. Borodin, O. L. Kabachek, T. A. Novikova, I. I. Tikhomirova, V. P. Chudinova, etc.), etc.).

The philosophical aspect of considering the concept of "reading" is associated with a specific form of linguistic communication of people through printed or handwritten texts, one of the main forms

of mediated communication. Reading differs significantly from other types of communication, which is associated with the specifics of the text as a sign system, the elements of which exist in a fixed spatial form, providing for their subsequent visual perception, and with the possibility of fixing, storing, replicating information in a form in which the consumption processes do not coincide in time with their production, and can last for centuries. This feature turns reading into a very rational way of transferring and assimilating knowledge and values developed by mankind (Ya. Ya. Krasavtseva, V. L. Abushenko, etc.) [7].

The culturological aspect of initiation to reading is considered in the relationship between the reader and the work of art, i.e. the ability of a person to respond to the work being read, to activate their own thoughts and feelings in the course of reading, to recreate images, to leave a trace of what they have read in their soul, to correlate what is read with their experience and knowledge deepen your view of the world.

Laying the responsibility for the intellectual development of society on reading, D.S. Likhachev emphasizes that "the main way of intellectual development is reading. <...> Nothing can replace a book. Despite the latest discoveries, modern ways of preserving information, we will not rush to part with the book. She stays. It is not just read, it is thought about. The new mass media will peacefully coexist with it" [8].

Reading is a system process in which many elements participate. You can't be a good reader without having a culture of reading. Differences in understanding the

culture of reading can be traced in encyclopedic and professional dictionaries and reference books. Experts stopped linking the culture of reading with the general culture of the individual and educational tasks, and turned only to technological aspects. The encyclopedic dictionary "Book" highlights such parameters of the culture of reading as: the ability to navigate in book products, choose literature, apply rational ways of working with text and optimally perceive what is read[9]. In the specialized literature, various phrases with the word "reading" are used - this is the culture of reading, children's reading, etc. V. A. Borodin and S. M. Borodin, A. P. Kashkarov, Z. N. Ovsyankina and others understand the culture of reading "a complex education, it reflects many components of personality development." Among them, the authors distinguish: worldview, information and bibliographic, cultural, philosophical, psychological, literary components, including the development of the speech activity of the individual as a whole. Such polyfunctionality causes objective

difficulties in cultivating a culture of reading in lifelong education [10].

The studies of T. D. Polozova[11] bring together the concepts of "culture of reading", "creative reading", "art of reading": personally significant spiritual, creative activity of each reader, which determines the educational and aesthetic value of literature and reading, a holistic aesthetic perception of what is read - to read and to think, read and feel, transfer the knowledge gained from books to your inner self, to interpersonal relationships.

Thus, reading is a receptive type of activity, which consists in the perception and processing by the reader of an objectively existing text - a product of the reproductive activity of a certain author. In the process of reading, all analyzers responsible for the perception of language and speech are activated: visual as the main, speech-motor and auditory as auxiliary. And the main thing is the time separated for reading and the main thing in it is to learn what you read.

References:

1. Понимание прочитанного. Модуль 5. МИНИСТЕРСТВО ОБРАЗОВАНИЯ И НАУКИ КЫРГЫЗСКОЙ РЕСПУБЛИКИ. <http://www.0c2e3083-b09c-4b42-bb5a-db968b4a7265>.
2. Бредихина И. А. Методика преподавания иностранных языков: Обучение основным видам речевой деятельности : учеб. пособие / И. А. Бредихина ; М-во образования и науки Рос. Федерации, Урал. федер. ун-т. — Екатеринбург: Изд-во Урал. ун-та, 2018.—С. 10.
3. Работа с текстом на уроке русского языка (на примере учащихся с дислексией). р10т0Va ргасе. Вгпо 2018, дос. РЮг. Мдг. 81топа Когусапкоуа, Р11.1). Вс. Ка1ейпа ВeРпагоуа. –С. 10.
4. The CEFR illustrative descriptor scales. The Modern Language Journal, 91, 656–657. DOI: 10.1111/j.1540-4781.2007.00627_3.x.
5. Moskal B. Scoring rubrics: what, when, how? Practical Assessment, Research and Evaluation. 2000. Vol. 7 (3). P. 1-8.
6. Moskal B. Scoring rubrics: what, when, how? Practical Assessment, Research and Evaluation. 2000. Vol. 7 (3). P. 1-8.

7. Новейший философский словарь. – 2009. – URL: http://dic.academic.ru/dic.nsf/dic_new_philosophy/1356/%D0%A7%D0%A2%D0%95%D0%9D%D0%98%D0%95
8. Лихачев, Д. С. Раздумья / Д. С. Лихачев. – М., 1991.-С. 316.
9. Книга: энциклопедический словарь. – М., 1999.
10. Бородина, В. А. Судьба чтения – судьба образования / В. А. Бородина, С. М. Бородин // Личность и культура. – 2005. – №6. – С. 38–43. – URL: <http://lichnost-kultura.ru/2005/20056/2005617/2005617.htm>. Смотрите также: Кашкаров, А. П. Чтение подростка: пособие для отцов / А. П. Кашкаров, З. Н. Овсянкина. – М., 2010. –С. 167.
11. Полозова, Т. Д. Помочь красоте править бал / Т. Д. Полозова // Начальная школа. – 1991.– №8. – С. 81–84.
12. Kodirov N. M. Transformation and globalization of information media //Scientific Bulletin of Namangan State University. – 2019. – Т. 1. – №. 12. – С. 83-93.
13. Nodirbek Kodirov Mamasoliyevich. (2021). Current issues of formation of information culture in youth. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5770626>
14. Kodirov N. M. TRANSFORMATION AND GLOBALIZATION OF INFORMATION MEDIA //Scientific Bulletin of Namangan State University. – 2019. – Т. 1. – №. 12. – С. 83-93.

NATURAL MONUMENTS AND THEIR PROTECTION

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ABSTRACT

This article provides views on natural monuments, their study and protection, in particular, the identification of natural monuments in Bukhara region, the collection of statistical data on them and their protection.

Relevance of the topic: Natural monuments are objects created by nature, which include their preservation, reconstruction, protection of rare trees, plants and others. It is very important today to register trees and use them in tourism. It is necessary to map natural monuments and implement maps. This is not new for the tourism industry, but it remains very shallow.

Goals and objectives: Identification of natural monuments located in Bukhara region

- collection of accurate statistics
- Reduction of negative impacts on the destruction of natural monuments
- Mapping of natural monuments
- Formation of education on the preservation of natural monuments

Natural monuments are unique, remarkable objects created by animate and inanimate nature: caves, waterfalls, beautifully shaped rocks, ravines, geysers, open springs, huge adult trees. Natural monuments are used for scientific, aesthetic, recreational, travel, tourism, recreation, educational purposes. There are more than 400 natural monuments in the country. [Rafiqov, 1997: 124]

Vardondeze Natural Monuments are one of the rare natural monuments under state protection. Originally established as a nature reserve in 1975 in Shafirkan district of Bukhara region, the desert has lost its significance due to the rapid development of the desert and in 1983 was turned into a state natural monument. (oni vardonze) has a monument. Rare saxaul trees, Richter, Circassian, willow and others grow.

According to the Chorchinor State Natural Monument, the regional department of ecology and environmental protection, there are 213 trees aged 100 and over in Bukhara. Among them is a plane tree in the village of Chorchinor, which belongs to the citizens' assembly of Bohouddin Naqshband mahalla of Kagan district. This maple tree lived for 702 years. According to the legends passed down from generation to generation, the maple sapling was planted by Hazrat Bahauddin Naqshband. There were 4 maples around

the pool. Once upon a time, this road was connected to the western gate of the Bahauddin Naqshband shrine. Now there is only one maple tree left. It is necessary to develop measures to improve the surroundings of the Shar maple complex and turn this natural monument into an ecotourism site, to pay attention to the maple and prevent it from drying out. The age of the plane tree should be written on a special sign. It should be hung as a natural monument. The plane tree should be surrounded by a ribbon.

Karakol monuments. Karakol is located in the south of Uzbekistan, at the confluence of the Kyzylkum and Karakum deserts, in the lower reaches of the Zarafshan River. In ancient times, people lived in Zamonbobo district of Karakol region, Poykent, Kichiktuzkon, Kattatuzkon, Odilkuduk, Kurbanboy, Rahmatbobo, Aqrabod and Hatar. Archaeological finds from the II-I millennium BC include a statue of aya, khovoncha handles, gold beads, precious stones - laurels, various primitive

weapons, copper ornaments. Historically known as the "Modern Culture", it is the culture of the Bronze Age clan, where two semi-basement tents, a pottery kiln and 43 tombs were found. This means that the community was engaged in farming and animal husbandry.

Another ancient monument of Karakol is the city of Poykent (Boykent). Poykent has a history of more than 2,500 years, and its arch and two shahristans are surrounded by a fortified wall. The 20-hectare city is located on an artificial hill.

Outside the city walls, a wide and deep ditch was dug, through which bridges were built. Another historical monument of Karakol, the complex of the mausoleum of Chibir don ota - Shah Abdurahmon Vali, is one of the unique examples of Central Asian architecture. The mausoleum of Shah Abdurahman Vali is built on a high sand hill and consists of two parts: an underground cave and a single domed shrine built on top of it. The shrine has a door on all four sides, and the central roof of the building is decorated with marble, ornaments, and Kufic inscriptions.

The octagonal mausoleum was built in the early 11th century. The appearance of the mausoleum is typical of the Samanid period, with square square bricks, unique construction, compositional structure, elongated dome, and a slightly heavier and taller roof. The mausoleum is not overly decorated on the outside.

The composition of the building is simple: each side is 2.65 meters octagonal, octagonal, covered with a dome 6.4 meters in diameter. A 1.4-meter-diameter hole in the top of the dome served to illuminate the inside of the mausoleum. In addition, the inside of the mausoleum is illuminated by three towers - a fence. The top of the central roof and the bars on the east and south sides are made of terracotta.

Another peculiarity of the mausoleum is that the outer part of the wall of the building, which is 2 meters high, is made of 9 rows of bricks facing outwards. This method was used in Central Asia and Iran in the IX-X centuries to cover the huge columns of monuments made of raw bricks and cotton. Chirirdon ota or Shirburdon ota mausoleum was built in honor of Saint Shirburdon ota during the reign of Amir Temur, in the XIV-XV centuries. The

monument consists of three rooms: a khanaqah, a chillaxona and a gorkhona. The roof of the mausoleum faces the octagonal mausoleum to the east. At the top of the roof there are five cupboards, and in the two corners there are tower-shaped bouquets. The high-domed room of the building is arranged in an octagonal shape on top of the sheets with a spherical dome measuring 10 meters in diameter. The tombs and children's rooms are covered with low domes 4 meters in diameter. The cemetery originally had four doors. The doors on the north and south walls were symmetrical to each other, and the west wall had two doors of the same size. The foundation under the walls of the building is laid in the following order: thick clay is laid on top of a layer of hard sand, two rows of square bricks are laid vertically on top of it, a layer of reeds is laid on top of it and bricks are laid on top of it. During excavations near the building, a set of coins minted in Bukhara in 1428-29 was found. The building resembles the mausoleum of Sayfiddin Boharzi in Bukhara. However, the fact that the roof of the Chibir don ota mausoleum is much lower indicates that it was built in the second half of the 14th century.

The Chibir don ota mausoleum complex was identified in 1951 by the expedition of the well-known archeologist Yahyo Gulyamov. The proposal of the State Committee for Environmental Protection and the Ecological Party of Uzbekistan to declare Lake Urungoch and adjacent areas a state hydrological monument of nature was approved. Ugam-Chatkal State National Park declares the 43-hectare Urungoch Natural Lake and adjacent areas located in the Burchmullo State Forestry Territory as a state hydrological natural monument.

It is noted that the Urungoch State Hydrological Natural Monument is part of the Burchmullo State Forestry and is managed by the farm without confiscation of land and prohibiting any activities that could adversely affect the facility. Chust Natural Monument at the initiative of the Central Asian Plant and Conservation Research Institute

Made in accordance with the decision of the khokimiyat of Namangan region No. 65/5 of 19.08.90 (as well as the decision of the Council of People's Deputies of Chust district of Namangan region No. P-5/12 of August 30, 1990), the area is 1000 hectares.

Natural monument "Yozyavon" formed in accordance with Resolution No. 1842.

The natural monument "Central Fergana" was created in accordance with the decision of the Executive Committee of the Akhunboboev district of the Council of People's Deputies of Fergana region on August 2, 1986 on the land of the farm "Solijonobod" with an area of 142.5 hectares.

The natural monument "Yangibozor" was created in accordance with the decisions of the khokimiyat of Yangibazar district of

Khorezm region (No. 738 of 10.05.03, No. 819 of 4.02.04, No. 853 of 7.08.04, No. 1155 of 17-04.04). The area varied and was 136 ha, 113.2 ha, 120 ha, 121 ha, respectively, and now stands at 490.3 ha.

According to the decision of the Namangan regional khokimiyat No. 164/14 dated 28.12.91, the area of the natural monument "Mingbulak" is 1000 hectares. Formed in accordance with the Resolution No. 65/5 (as well as the Resolution of the Council of People's Deputies of Chust district of Namangan region No. II-5/12 of August 30, 1990), the area is 1000 hectares. The Yazyavon natural monument was built in accordance with the decision of the Fergana regional administration No. 164 of 23.05.94 and covers an area of 1,842 hectares. Natural monument "Central Fergana" In accordance with the decision of the Executive Committee of the Council of People's Deputies of Fergana region Ahunboboev district dated August 2, 1986, the area of the farm "Solijonobod" is 142.5 hectares. district khokimiyat (No. 738 of 10.05.03, No. 819 of 4.02.04, No. 853 of 7.08.04, No. 1155 of 17.04.04). The area varied and was 136 ha, 113.2 ha, 120 ha, 121 ha, respectively. [Norbaeva U., Obidova Sh. Taffakur and Talqin 299]

References:

1. The first volume of the National Encyclopedia of Uzbekistan Tashkent 2000
2. Istam Ibragimov people's word
3. Norboyeva UT, Obidova Shoiri, Tafakkur va Talqin `` Bukhara 2021 299 p
1. 4.Rafiqov AA Geoecological problems Tashkent, 1997 124 p
4. The Regulation on State Natural Monuments, approved by the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers No. 399 of May 4, 2018.

ЧИЗИҚЛИ ЭЛЕКТР ЗАНЖИРЛАРИДА ЎТКИНЧИ ЖАРАЁН ТАҲЛИЛИНИНГ ВАҚТ УСУЛИ

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МАҚОЛА ТАРИХИ

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KALIT SO'ZLAR

паремия, семантика,
мақол, фольклор,
элемент, қатлам,
даражаланиш,
фразеология, афоризм,
ритм, матал

Ҳозирги замон ахборотни еткзиш, қайта ишлаш тизимлари шундай мураккаб техник қурилмалар бўлиб, электр занжирлари назарияси, радиотехника, электроника ва ҳисоблаш техникасининг энг охири илмий техник ютуқларини ўз ичида мужассамлантиргандир. Охири йилларда дунёнинг бир қанча давлатларида, шулар қаторида бизнинг давлатимизда ҳам, рақамли автоматик коммутацион станциялар, ўзатишнинг рақамли, толали-оптик тизимлари, спутник алоқа тизимлари билан жиҳозланган ҳар қил халқаро телекоммуникацион тармоқлар ишлаб чиқилмоқда ва эксплуатация қилинмоқда.

ANNOTATSIYA

Мақолада мураккаб шаклдаги сигнални элементар сигналларнинг йиғиндисини сифатида тасвирлаш мумкин бўлган ҳолларда, ҳамда занжир киришидаги бу элементар сигналлар таъсирининг занжир чиқишидаги реакцияси (акс таъсирини) қандайдир бир йўл билан аниқлаш мумкин бўлган ҳоллари ҳақида қисқача маълумот берилган.

Ўткинчи жараёнларни ҳисоблашнинг классик ва оператор усулларини ташқи таъсирнинг шакли содда бўлганда қўллаш қулайдир; аммо ташқи таъсир вақт бўйича мураккаб қонун билан ўзгарганда бу усулларни амалда қўллаш мумкин бўлмайди.

Мураккаб шаклга эга бўлган ташқи таъсирли электр занжирларининг ўткинчи жараёнларини таҳлил қилишда суперпазичия (устлаш) усулини қўллаш қулайликларга олиб келади. Бундай усул фақат нолли бошланғич шарт бўлган чизиқли занжирларда қўлланиши мумкин.

Масалан, мураккаб шаклдаги сигнални элементар сигналларнинг

Йиғиндиси сифатида тасвирлаш мумкин бўлган ҳолларда, ҳамда занжир киришидаги бу элементар сигналлар бир йўл билан аниқлаш мумкин бўлган ҳолларда, қўйилган масаланинг ечими шундай реакцияларнинг оддий

таъсирининг занжир чиқишидаги реакцияси (акс таъсирини) қандайдир

Йиғиндисини аниқлаш билан бажарилади.

Чекланган вақт оралиғида кучланиш ёки токнинг бирламчи қийматидан оғиши электр импульси дейилади (1-расм).

Кучланишнинг берилган қийматидан оғиши кўриладиган AB қисми-импульснинг fronti дейилади.

Кучланишнинг берилган қийматига қайтиши кузатиладиган CD қисми-импульснинг

қирқими дейилади. Импульснинг BC қисми-импульс чўққисси дейилади; AD қисми-импульс

импульс кенглиги; t_f – фронт кенглиги; t_c – қирқим кенглиги 1-расм

асоси; U_m – импульс амплитудаси; t_u –

дейилади.

Кетма-кет тарқалувчи импульслар, импульслар кетма-

кетлигини ташкил этади (2-

импульсларнинг такрорланиш даври

расм). Оний қийматлари бир хил вақт T

дейилади; $f = 1/T$ – импульслар

оралиғида такрорланувчи импульслар кетма-кетлиги импульсларнинг даврий кетма - кетлиги дейилади. Бунда T –

такрорланиш частотаси; $Q = T/t_u$ – импульсларнинг зичлиги дейилади

елекоммуникация тизимларида учрайдиган импульсларнинг шакллари 3-расмда келтирилган

“Тасвир импульси” атамасининг ишлатилишига сабаб шу бўлдики, бундай импульс биринчи марта телевидение техникасида қўлланилади.

стандарт шакли сифатида одатда бирлик сигнали ёки уланиш сигнали (бирлик поғона сигнали, бирлик поғона) ишлатилади.

Суперпозиция усулини элементар қўлаганда сигналнинг

2-расм

3-расм

Бирлик поғона сигнали деб шундай кучланиш ток сигналига айтиладики, ихтиёрий $t < 0$ бўлганда

сигналнинг қиймати нолга тенг, $t \geq 0$ бўлганда эса 1 га тенг бўлади.

$$1(t) = \begin{cases} 0 & t < 0 \text{ бўлганда} \\ 1 & t \geq 0 \text{ бўлганда} \end{cases}$$

References:

1. Азизов О., Ризаев З. Ўзбекча-русча луғат. –Т.: Ўқитувчи, 1989, -288 б.
2. Антонью А. Цифровые фильтры: анализ и проектирование: Пер. с англ. –М.: Радио и связь, 1993. -320 с.
3. Бакалов В.П., Воробийенко П.П., Крук Б.И. Теория электрических цепей.: Учебник для ВУЗов; Под ред. В.П. Бакалова, -М.: Радио и связь, 1998. -444 с.
4. Бекжонов Р.К., Камолхўжаев Ш.М., Ризаев З. Физикадан русча-ўзбекча атамалар луғати. –Т.: Ўқитувчи, 1990. -296 б.
5. Белецкий А.Ф. Теория электрических цепей: Учебник для ВУЗов. –М.: Радио и связь, 1986. -544 с.
6. Матханов П.Н. Основы анализа электрических цепей. Линейные цепи: Учебник для ВУЗов. -3-е изд., -М.: Высш. шк., 1990. -400 с.
7. Крылов В.В., Корсаков С.Я. Основы теории цепей для системотехников: Учеб. Пособие для ВУЗов. –М.: Высш. шк., 1990. -224 с.

ПЛАСТИК МАТЕРИАЛЛАР ЁРДАМИДА ДИДАКТИК АШЁЛАР ТАЙЁРЛАШ МЕТОДИКАСИГА ОИД ТАЖРИБАЛАР

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MAQOLA TARIXI

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KALIT SO'ZLAR

пластик материаллар,
полимер лой, чинни
хамир, моделлаштириш,
образ яратиш,
комбинациялашган услуб,
техник усуллар.

ANNOTATSIYA

Мақолада пластик материаллар билан ишлашда моделлаштириш орқали дидактик материаллар тайёрлаш методикасига оид тажрибалар баён этилган. Полимер лой ҳамда чинни хамир ёрдамида машғулотлар учун дидактик ашёлар тайёрлаш жараёни, у билан боғлиқ тафсилотлар ёритилган.

Пластик материаллар билан ишлаш тасвирий санъатнинг бир тури ҳисобланиб, ҳажмли ёки рельефли образлардан бутун композиция яшаш тушунилади. Бу материаллардан мактабгача таълим ташкилотлари машғулотларида дидактик восита сифатида фойдаланишнинг кенг имкониятлари мавжуд. Бунда тарбиячи, бир томондан, машғулоти учун керакли бўлган дидактик ашёни мақсадга кўра ўзи тайёрлайди, иккинчи томондан, тарбияланувчиларни яшаш, ижод қилиш жараёнига жалб қилиб, уларнинг ақлий, жисмоний ва руҳий ривожланишига туртки беради. Фаолиятга киришишдан олдин аввало машғулотни моделлаштириб олиш лозим бўлади. Моделлаштириш – бадий ижодиётнинг энг аниқ шакли, унда бола яратган нарсасини нафақат кўради, кўлига

олади, пайпаслайди, керак бўлса ўзгартиради. Моделлаштириш техникаси турли ва ранг-баранг бўлиб, шу билан бирга кичик ёшдаги болалар ҳам бажара олиш имкониятига эгадирлар[1,65].

Фазовий-пластик тасвирларни моделлаштиришда пластик материаллардан нарсалар яшаш ажойиб имкониятларни беради. Моделлаштиришнинг асосий асбоби қайчи, қалам ёки мўйқалам эмас, балки кўл, тўғрироғи, икки кўлимиздир, шу сабабли маҳорат малакаси кўлларга эгалик даражасига боғлиқ. Тўғри тайёрланган чинни хамир ўзининг хоссасига кўра юмшоқ, илашувчан, яхши текисланиш ва исталган шаклга кириш хусусиятига эга бўлади. Бу материал билан ишлаш учун чуқурлаштирилган махсус билим ва кўникмалар шарт

эмаслиги, мактабгача ёшдаги болалар учун айна мудаодир.

Полимер лой ёки чинни хамирнинг хусусиятлари билан боланинг ўзи мустақил танишиши тавсия этилади. Ҳеч қандай кўрсатмаларсиз, ҳеч нарсани ўргатмай туриб унинг қўлига бу материал берилади ва қўл ҳаракатлари орқали ўзи табиий равишда танишади. Бу шундай қулай материалки, у «итоаткор», қўлнинг ҳар қандай ҳаракатига жавоб беради. Бу топилманинг чегаралари очиб юборилса, бола тажрибасини янада бойитиш мумкин.

Болага турли материаллар билан ишлаш имкониятини бериш тавсия этилади. Хамир, ёпишқоқ қор, ҳўл қум, сақич кабиларнинг лой ва пластилинга ўхшаш хусусиятлари мавжудлигига амин бўлади. Уларни осонгина турли шаклга ўзгартириш мумкин.

Бола пластик материал билан ишлаш малакасини эгаллар экан, ўзига янги «ихтиролар» очади. Энди у нафақат пластик материал билан ишлашни эгаллайди, балки материалга таъсир этиш соҳаларини текширади. Демак, у бир бутун лойдан бир бўлакни узиб олишни, бураб олишни, чимчилаб олишни ва шаклини ўзгартиршини билиб олади [2,7]. Бунинг учун у лойни эзиш ёки яссиллаш, жувалаш ёки чўзиш, ёки яна бир нарса қилиш мумкинлигини кўради.

Лойни бошқа бўлакка ёпиштириш, бу билан унинг ёпишиб қолиши, қоғозга ёки тахтачага суртиш мумкинлиги билан танишиб, унинг устига тирнаб чизиш, кейин қўл билан силлиқлаб чиқиш ва расм йўқолганини кўриш каби экспериментларда бола мустақил

изланувчи ролини ўйнайди ва атроф-олам билан танишиб, ўзи учун муҳим билимга эга бўлади.

Шу билан бирга кўплаб бошқа материаллар – қуруқ қум, ун, манка ёрмаси ҳеч қандай шаклга эга эмаслиги ва қўллар ёрдамида уларга шакл бера олмаслигини кўради. Мактабгача ёшдаги болалар иштирокида ушбу материал билан эксперимент ўтказиш асосида тасвирга ўтиш билан ифодаланади. Қор, қум устидаги оёқ излари болага нарсаларнинг хоссалари ҳақида биринчи маълумотни беради. Бола тажриба ўтказади, қолдирилган изларни ўрганади, манбаларни аниқлаштиришга интилади («Бу изларни ким ёки нима қолдирди?»). Турли буюмларнинг «излари»ни излашга интилади. Масалан, санчқининг излари пластик маериалда қандай из қолдиришига қизиқади. Пластик материалга санчқини яссилатиб босилса, санчқининг учи тиқилса, санчқи билан тирнаб чиқилса, қандай излар қолдириши болада катта қизиқиш уйғотади. Чинни хамир билан эксперимент ўтказишда жараёнида тугма, танга ёки қалам излари болада тахмин қилиш малакасини ривожлантиради. «Бу нима?», «Нимага ўхшайди?», «Нима билан бундай из қолдириш мумкин?» каби саволлар бошқаларга муражаат қилади.

Барча болалар учун умумий бўлган муҳим ютуқ – бу пластик материал билан ишлашда образ яратишдир. Бирламчи образ яратиш – барча бадий фаолиятнинг хусусияти бўлиб, шу қаторда моделлаштириш ҳамдир.

Шаклларнинг турли хил услублар ва ҳар хил қўл ҳаракатлари билан

яратилиши ҳақидаги тушунчалар аста-секинлик билан шакллантирилади. Боланинг қидирув фаолиятини фаоллаштириш учун вақти-вақти билан муаммоли вазиятлар яратилади. Масалан, бодринг ва помидорни кўрсатиб, уни ясашни таклиф этиш ёки иккита ҳар хил нарсани ўйлаб топиб, ясашни таклиф этиш. Бундай топшириқлар болада ҳар хил образлар турли хил услублар билан яратилиши ҳақидаги ўз-ўзидан шаклланаётган тушунчаларни мустаҳкамлайди.

Кейинчалик шу асосда бола нима ва қандай ясаши ҳақидаги ўзига хос эмперик тизим, яъни сезгилар орқали тушунчаларга эга бўлади.

Мисол тариқасида цилиндр шакли қандай ясаши, қандай қилиб уни ўзгартириш мумкинлиги борасидаги тажрибаларимизни ўртоқлашамиз.

«Кундача» ёки цилиндр – 1-1,5 ёшли боланинг мустақил ясай оладиган биринчи шакли ҳисобланади. Кейинчалик у бу билимини такомиллаштиради, узун, қисқа, йўғон, ингичка, ранг-баранг, бир хил рангли цилиндрларни ясайди. Албатта, бу нарсалар шунчаки эмас, балки улар қалам, дарахт, чўп, мих, конфет ва бошқаларни ифода этади. 2,5-3 ёшга тўлган бола шаклларга диққатлироқ қарайди ва аниқроқ бажаришга ҳаракат қилади. Энди ўзига таниш бўлган услублар ёрдамида цилиндрни тешкулча, ҳалқача ва шиллиққуртчага айлантиради.

Цилиндр шаклини ясашда болага:

– пластик материал бўлагини кафтлар орасига олиб, узунасига

ҳаракатлар билан цилиндр ҳосил қилиниши;

– бир бўлак пластик материални бир кафт билан пластик материални қаттиқ сирт устида тўғри ҳаракатлар билан цилиндр ҳосил қилиниши;

– бир бўлак пластик материалдан катта ва бош бармоқ учиде тўғри ҳаракатлар билан цилиндр ҳосил қилинади; бу услубда жуда кичкина цилиндрчалар ва ингичка чўпчалар ҳосил бўлиши тўғрисидаги маълумотлар ўргатилади.

Цилиндр шаклини ўзгартириш болага:

– йўғон ва ингичка цилиндрчаларни айланага айлантириш (тешкулча, пирамида ҳалқачалари, обрuch);

– спирал шаклига бураш (илонча, шиллиққурт, гул);

– яссилаш услуби орқали тасмачага айлантириш (барг, шар);

– конус шаклини бериш (сабзи, қалпоқча);

– 2-3 та ингичка чўпчаларни бирлаштириб, ўрам ҳосил қилиш (соч ўрами, ўсимлик, колонналар) кабилар ўргатилади (2.5 илова).

Илк ёшдаги болалар томонидан ўзлаштириладиган яна бир шакл бу – шар. Болалар завқ билан олма ва ширинликларни ясаб, қўғирчоқларини меҳмон қилишади. Шунини таъкидлаш керакки, шарни ясаш техникаси цилиндрни ясаш техникасидан мураккаб ҳисобланади, чунки иккала қўлни аниқ ва изчил мувофиқлаштирувчи ҳаракат координациясини талаб этади. Бола шарсимон шаклини яратиш ва унинг

шаклини ўзгартиришни мустақил ясай олмайди.

Шарсимон шаклини яратишда болага:

– пластик материалнинг бир бўлагини кафтлар орасида думалоқлаш ҳаракати орқали;

– пластик материалнинг бир бўлагини битта кафтда қаттиқ сирт устида думалоқлаш ҳаракати орқали;

– пластик материалнинг бир бўлагини иккита бармоқ учида думалоқлатиш ҳаракати орқали; бундай усул билан жуда кичкина («кўзлар», «бурун» ва бошқ.) элементлар ҳосил бўлиши ўргатилади.

Шар шаклини ўзгартиришни ўргатишда болага:

– шарни иккала томондан озгина чўзиб, овал ёки элlepс ҳосил қилиш (киндер-сюрприз, пуфак, қовун, тарвуз шакллари);

– бир томонини чўзиш орқали (нок, лампочка шаклини) ҳосил қилиш;

– узунасига жўвалаб, бир томонга қайириш (банан, бодринг шакллари);

– кафтлар орасида яссилаш (нон, ғилдирак шакллари);

– узунасига жўвалаб, бир томонининг конус шаклини ҳосил қилиш (музқаймоқ, пирамидача шакллари);

– шарни бир томонини яссилаш (қуртча, ширин кулча шаклларида);

– шарнинг ўртасида бармоқ ёки қалам билан чуқурча ҳосил қилиш (кўзиқорин қалпоқчаси, пиёла, гулдон шакллари).

Шар ва цилиндрдан ясаладиган шакллар – бу ўзига хос бўлган моделлаштиришнинг «алифбо» вазифасини бажаради, шу асосда бола

уни «ўқийди» ва ҳар қандай «асарни» мустақил яратиб, моделлаштиришнинг техникасини яратади. Болалар шар, цилиндр ва диск шакллари яшаш малакасини эгаллаб олишгач, бир неча қисмдан тузилган буюмларни яшашга ўрганадилар. Масалан, пирамида, сарак-сарак кўғирчоқ, пуфак ва кубиклардан минорача, айиқ, кўғирчоқ, қуёнча ва ҳоказо. Бу буюм қисмлари 2 ёки 3 тадан ортиқ бўлмайди.

Шу тарзда болалар олган билим ва малакаларини оширадилар. Ёз давомида болалар ҳар хил мева ва сабзавотларни ясаб, зарур бўлган малака ва кўникмаларни эгаллайдилар. Тарбиячи рецептив ва репродуктив усуллардан кенг фойдаланади. Болалар билан биргаликда шар, копток, мева, қалам ва бошқа буюмларни синчовлик билан кўриб чиқадиладар. Энг муҳими, бу буюмларни қўл билан ушлаб кўришлари зарур [3,89].

Моделлаштириш техникаси усулларининг хилма-хил, ранг-баранглигига қарамай, мактабгача ёшдаги болалар уни осон эгаллашади.

Моделлаштиришнинг конструктив услуби конструктор қисмлари каби алоҳида қисмлардан иборат (номи ҳам шундан келиб чиққан).

Тарбиячи, даставвал, болаларнинг диққатини мазкур буюмнинг йирик қисмларига, кейин майда қисмларига, шаклига, рангига жалб этади. Дастлабки машғулотларда тарбиячи тасвирлашнинг техник усулларини кўрсатиб, тушунтириб беради. Шунингдек, тарбиячи болаларнинг лойдан нарсалар ясашида кўпроқ ўйин усулларидан фойдаланади. Бу гуруҳда лой машғулотлари буюмли характерга

эга бўлади, яъни болалар алоҳида, якка буюмларни ясайдилар, бу гуруҳда болалар ишига ёки фаолиятига баҳо бериш ҳам муҳим усуллардан ҳисобланади. Тарбиячи албатта болаларнинг қандай ишлаганларини ва ишни қандай бажарганликларини айтиб ўтиши лозим.

Бола ўзи ўйлаб топган образни тасаввур қилиб, қандай қисмлардан иборатлигини аниқлаб ясайди. Болалар 2–3 ёшдан бошлаб конструкторлик услуги билан ясашни бошлайдилар ва кўпинча ўзларига бу «янгиликни» мустақил «очишади».

Кўп ҳолларда кичик ёшдаги болаларда моделлаштириш қуйидаги вариантларда намоён бўлади:

– иккита бир хил шаклни бирлаштириш (мунчоқ, девор шакллари);

– ўхшаш, аммо турли ҳажмдаги шаклларни бирлаштириш (ҳалқачали пирамида, қорбобо, сарак-сарак қўғирчоқ, минора шакллари);

– турли шаклларни бирлаштириш (қўзиқорин, капалак, қуш шакллари).

Ҳайкалтарошлик услубини адабиётларда пластик ёки бутун бўлақдан моделлаштириш деб аташади [4].

Болалар лой бўлагининг майда қисмларини чўзиб чиқаришга, бармоқ билан чуқурча ҳосил қилишга, буклашга, бириктирилган қисмини маҳкам қилиб ёпиштиришга ўрганадилар. Чимдиб чиқаришни болалар жўжа, қушларни ясашда ўрганадилар. Бу жараёнда болалар буюмларни, уларнинг қисмларини, шаклни катталиқ жиҳатдан таққослашга ўрганадилар. Масалан,

курканинг тана ва бош қисмини ҳайкалтарошлиқ услубидан фойдаланиб моделлаштира бўлади, яъни бир бутун бўлақни олиб, боши ва танасини чўзиш усули билан шакллантириш тавсия этилади. Худди шу тарзда балиқ шаклини ясашдан олдин танасини овал шаклида ясаб оладилар, сўнг балиқнинг бир томонини салгина чўзиб ва думалоқлаб, балиқнинг бошини, қарама-қарши томонини кўпроқ чўзиб чиқариб, япалоқлаб, унинг думини ясайдилар, сузгичларини чимдиб чиқарадилар. Шунингдек, болалар лой бўлагини бир неча бўлакка бўлишга ўрганадилар.

Масалан,

юқоридагилардан ташқари, идишлар ясашга ўрганадилар. Идишларни якка усулда, яъни юмалоқсимон ва цилидрсимон шаклларни бармоқ билан босиб чуқурча ҳосил қилиш, бандини эса алоҳида лой бўлагидан ёки асосий лой бўлагидан чўзиб чиқариб ясаш мумкин. Болалар олган билим ва малакаларини ривожлантириб мустаҳкамлайдилар. Болалар гул, ҳашаротлар, мева солинган идишча, қўзиқорин солинган саватча кабиларни ҳам тарбиячи билан бирга лойдан ясашга, бошлаган ишларини охирига етказшга, мустақил ишлашга, ўз ишларини янги деталлар билан бойитиб боришга ўрганадилар.

Комбинациялашган услуб конструкциялаш ва ҳайкалтарошлиқ каби иккита услубни ўз ичига олади. Бола 6 ёшга тўлгач, унинг теварак- атроф ҳақидаги билим ва тажрибаси орта боради. Унинг қўл мускуллари мустаҳкамланиб, тараққий этади. У қўл бармоқлари билан нозик ҳаракатларни бажара оладиган бўлади. Унинг

руҳиятида сифат ўзгариши юз беради. Хотираси ривожланиб, диққат-эътибори ҳам тобора барқарор бўлади. Болалар олдин буюмни ясашда унинг қисмлари ва уларнинг шаклини, унинг хусусиятларини аниқ тасаввур эта оладилар. Шу билан бирга, улар буюмларни кўпроқ ҳаракатда тасвирлашга ҳаракат қиладилар. Болаларни лой ишларига ўргатишда куйидаги вазифалар устувор бўлади: буюм шаклини, пропорциясини, унинг тузилишини, характерли деталларини ҳамда ҳаракатини тасвир этиш ва бошқалар[5].

Техник усуллар ҳам бу гуруҳда мураккаблашади. 4 ёшли болалар қисмлардан ясашса, 5–6 ёшга келиб бутун бир лой бўлагидан ясайдилар. Шу билан бирга стек билан ишлашга ҳам кенг имконият ёки ўрин ажратилади. Болалар даставвал ўзларига таниш бўлган содда буюмларни ясайдилар. Улар лой билан ишлашнинг икки усули: конструкторлик ва ҳайкалтарошлик усулларидан фойдаланиб, турли хил мева ва сабзавотларни ясайдилар. Масалан, бодринг, лавлаги, сабзи ва олма каби. Болалар шу икки усулда одам ва ҳайвонлар шакллари ясайдилар. Бу ишларнинг мазмуни асосан ўйинчоқлардан олинади.

Пластик материаллар билан ишлашда турли ёрдамчи усуллардан фойдаланилади. Болаларни буюмнинг сифатларини лойдан тасвирлашга ўргатиб борилади. Масалан, узун, қисқа, ингичка, калта, шунингдек, буюмларни вертикал, тик ҳолатда ўрнатадилар, қисмларни маҳкам бириктиришга, бирлаштирилган қисмларни силлиқлашга ўргатадилар. Болалар

аста-секин ўз ишларига мазмун беришни кенг татбиқ этадилар, асосан, бир бутун лой бўлагидан ҳайкалтарошлик усулида ясайдилар. Масалан, мушук, кучук, қуён ва бошқалар. Бутун бир лой бўлагидан тасмасимон усул билан идишлар ясайдилар, сўнг уларни безайдилар. Болалар ўзларига таниш техник усуллар ёрдамида турли нарсаларни ясайдилар. Масалан, хўроз, товуқ, ўрдак, жўжа ва бошқаларни ясаб, паррандалар шаклига мазмун берадилар. Кўпроқ натура асосида ихтиёрий лой ишларини бажарадилар.

Даставвал, буюм ёки натурани кузатиб, унинг шакли ва қисмларини бармоқ ҳаракатлари билан кўриб чиқишлари мумкин. Агар болалар ясаш усулини билишса, мустақил ясайдилар, агар билишмаса, унда тарбиячи қисман кўрсатиб беради. Ишларни бажаришда турли востилардан фойдаланса бўлади. Фломастер ва турли идишларнинг қалпоқчаларини ясалган балиқнинг «тангачаларини» из қолдириш учун ишлатиш тавсия этилади.

Стек ёрдамида кўп ҳаракатлар бажариш мумкин. Масалан, ясалган буюм устида штрихлар, «қанотчаларни» бўрттириб чиқарса бўлади.

Болалар пластик материаллардан одамлар, ҳайвонлар, идишлар, транспорт воситалари, сабзавотлар, мевалар ва ўйинчоқларни моделлаштирадилар. Мактабгача ёшдаги болага моделлаштириш материалининг пластиклиги ва тасвирланган шаклнинг ҳажмлилигини ифода этиш, расм чизишга қараганда техникаларни ўзлаштиришга имкон беради. Масалан, чизилган расмда

ҳаракатни тасвирлаш жуда кўп тайёргарликни талаб қиладиган мураккаб вазифадир, ҳайкалтарошликда эса бу муаммонинг ечими осонлашади. Бола аввал объектнинг статик ҳолатида ҳайкални моделлаштиради, сўнгра ғояларига мувофиқ унинг қисмларини букади. Мавзуларнинг хилма-хиллиги, моделлаштириш, тасвирий фаолиятнинг бошқа турлари сингари, авваламбор, боланинг билим ва ижодий эҳтиёжларини қондирадиган таълим вазифаларини бажариши билан боғлиқ[6,19].

Ҳайкалтарошликда объектларнинг жойлашинув алоқаларини узатиш ҳам соддалаштирилган – объектлар худди ҳаётдаги каби композиция марказидан бирин-кетин, яқинроқ ва узоқроқ жойлаштирилади. Ҳайкалтарошликдаги истиқболли муаммолар шунчаки олиб ташланади. Ҳайкалтарошликда тасвирни яратишда асосий восита бу – ҳажмли шаклни ифода этишдир, ранг эса чекланган даражада ишлатилади. Одатда, бўялган ўйинчоқлар,

кейинчалик болалар ўйинларида фойдаланилади.

Ясалган ўйинчоқларни мунчоқлар, тугмалар, қуш патлари ва чиғаноқлар ёрдамида майда қисмларига безаклар бериб комбинациялаштира бўлади.

Хуллас, пластилин, чинни хамир, лой ва бошқа массалар билан машғулотлар болаларнинг ҳиссий тажрибасини бойитади, бармоқларнинг майда моторикасини ривожлантиради, ишни якунига етказишга ўргатади, болада нутқ, диққат, фикрлаш, тасаввурни ривожлантиришга имкон беради; сабр-тоқат, қатъиятлилик, аниқлик, ишни режалаштириш ва охиригача етказиш қобилиятини тарбиялайди; улар болаларга таҳлил қилиш ва идрокни ривожлантиришни ўргатади, чунки ҳайкалтарошликда ҳар қандай буюмни акс эттириш учун унинг асосий қисмлари ва белгилари (ранг, ўлчам, шакл, нисбат, фазодаги жойлашуви)ни ажратиб кўрсатишга ёрдам беради; ўз ҳаракатларини режалаштириш қобилиятини ривожлантиради; болаларнинг атроф-олам объектлари ҳақидаги ғояларини аниқлаштиради ва мустаҳкамлайди.

References:

1. Иванова Т.Е. Занятие по лепке в детском саду. Методическое пособие. – М.: Сфера, 2010.
2. Махмудова О.А., Махмудова С.А. Maktabgacha ta'lim tizimida plastik materiallar bilan ishlash texnologiyalari..O'quv qo'llanma. "NISO POLIGRAF".-T.:2019.
3. Ветлугина Н.А. Воспитание эстетического отношения ребенка к окружающему. /Под ред. А.В.Запорожца, Т.А.Марковой. - М.: Педагогика, 1980.
4. Акилова К.Б. XX асрларда Ўзбекистон халқ амалий-безак санъати: тараққиёт муаммолари: Санъатшунос. док. дисс... автореф. – Т., 2002.
5. Казакова Т.Г. Теория и методика развития детского изобразительного творчества. - М.: ВЛАДОС, 2006.

FICTION IS A FACTOR IN THE FORMATION OF NATIONAL EDUCATION AND SPIRITUALITY IN CHILDREN

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ABSTRACT

The article discusses the issues of educating children from an early age in the national spirit through fiction, encouraging them to read. It shows the ways of shaping the spirituality of the younger generation through the example of folklore and Uzbek writers.

The following words of Munavvarqori Abdurashidkhonov, a representative of the Jadid movement and one of the founders of the new national school, are still relevant today: "An educated child respects the elders. He treats her equally well. And He has mercy and blessings on **the youth** than Himself, and knows the **value** of everyone "[1; 50]. It should be noted that the phrase "an educated child respects and honors the elders" refers to the fact that a child's upbringing is formed in his childhood. Can we teach our children the right way to raise their children today ?!

Can we instill in them a national spirit, our national values? It would be great if every parent and educator could ask these questions and answer them with pleasure. We are convinced of the truth of U. Chen's

statement that "raising a child requires deeper observation and deeper wisdom than governing the state"

The fact that the upbringing of children in our country is considered to be a deeper issue than the governance of the state is reflected in the fact that our government is taking special and permanent measures. President Mirziyoyev said: "No matter what sector we take, we cannot achieve any change and a prosperous life without training modern specialists. The training of such personnel, the healthy gene pool of the nation, begins, first of all, with the system of pre-school education "[3], - he said.

Kindergarten education is a period of mastering their complex movements, developing basic hygiene, cultural and

labor skills, developing speech, and forming the first buds of social morality and aesthetic taste. According to the famous Russian pedagogue Lesgaft, the period of human kindergarten is a stage in which children develop patterns of character and the foundations of moral character [4, 18].

At a time when parents are preoccupied with their marital worries, filling in any gaps in the quality of child rearing and education in the family places a huge responsibility on professionals at all levels of continuing education.

The pre-school education system in our country is the primary, the most basic link of continuing education. Therefore, educators of preschool education organizations (MTT) should provide their students with quality, meaningful, and most importantly, interesting and non-boring activities for the child.

It is important to ensure that the child's impressions and outcomes continue in speech, movement, and mood after returning to their family. The literature on the subject of our article has a wide range of possibilities and needs.

Preschool educational institutions regularly hold a variety of poems, songs and action games for our time and for future generations. But how it is organized depends on the skill of the teacher.

In our opinion, if children are taught to recite, memorize, and explain various poems that are easy for them to memorize and do not have difficulty in speech (consisting of simple words), the child will feel happy and will be able to read words through fluent pronunciation, fluency in speech, strengthening of memory, ability to express the tone appropriate to the content

of the poem, a sense of perception and national-moral upbringing are formed.

The educator of the preschool organization should be well aware that the choice of poems based on the age of the child and the fact that the poem is recited in a cheerful tone, the simplicity of the words is of great importance. Because if a child chooses poems that are not specific to his age, he will get tired of memorizing and reciting them, and then his interest in memorizing other poems will disappear. What's worse is the words that I can spell I often mistype.

Each age group in preschool has its own set of tasks for speech development. As they get older, their level of acceptance of the various poems taught by their tutor will increase, and they will gradually become more complex. In this way, children develop the ability to listen to poetry. Therefore, adults need to be aware of children's age opportunities.

Early childhood children's acceptance of works of art is based on their emotional response to them, their perception of different tones, their attitude, their ability to recognize and care for the characters of the work as much as possible. For children of this age, small-scale poetry, that is, folklore and authorial poetry, is important. Children are especially interested in playful poems, the main characters of which are children and animals.

Together with adults, the child enthusiastically organizes games based on the plots of proverbs and countless poems, listening to sound imitations and rhythmic repetitions in the direction of folklore. The child takes the events described in literary works very seriously. He is also ready to

listen to his favorite fairy tales and poetic tales several times.

This is the basis for the writing of national spirituality in the minds of children: the desire for knowledge is awakened, national identity is introduced, a sense of respect for national values is nurtured. Below, we decided to give some examples of what preschool educators can select and memorize for children in their classes.

Hamza's book "About School" from the book "Light Literature" is of special importance for children of preschool education:

School is the sun of the nation, School is the palace of the nation

Maybe an eyebrow **of it**. The place of science and etiquette.

The happiest person in the world without eyes and eyebrows

What an ugly head **it has**. The place of seekers.

As children recite this poem, their first impressions of school will be enriched, and their desire to grow up, go to school, and learn will increase.

The poem "School" from the book "The Second Teacher" by A. Avloni also serves to educate, to shape children's desire to explore the school in beautiful, bright colors, to study, to become literate:

School is a pearl, School makes you human,
School will open Paradise for you, School
will give you modesty,

School escapes ignorance, School destroys
grief,

Study hard, boy! Study hard, boy!

H.Olimjon's poem "Vatan" helps children to form a feeling of boundless love for their

homeland, a sense of homeland, love and respect for the motherland:

My joy is unbounded
I have endless happiness.
It made me happy
This is my invincible Motherland.

It should be noted that in addition to Uzbek folk tales, it is important for preschoolers to read a number of works by children's artists. In particular, H. Olimjon's works such as "Semurg", "Aigul and Bakhtiyor", Shukur Sadulla's "The old man and the wolf" are written in a poetic way, and children can listen to them with interest.

The Uzbek national mentality reflected in them is gradually taking root in the minds of young poets. In this way, they are taught to know and understand the unique examples of Uzbek literature. Z.Diyor's poem "Butterfly" is also important in that it forms in children such relationships as love of mother nature, its preservation, feeling of beauty:

Hey butterfly, butterfly, never run away
from me,
Your wings are like silk. I know a friend.
You fly so fast, You fly so fast,
Let me tell you - it was a scary place.

Another of the poet's poems, "Sniper", inspires children to grow up faster, to love the military profession, to defend their homeland like a brother:

Friends, when I grow up,
I'm going to the army.
Who is as killed wrestler
There ill take my brother.

Quds Muhammadi's poem "Hashar" also evokes children's first impressions of the hashar, which is unique to our Uzbek nation. A feeling of love and respect is formed. In the circle of his family, in the processes mentioned in the poem, they start to work by reciting the verses aloud:

Come on guys, whoever it is,
Come on, guys, let's get on with it.
Brothers and sisters, **we plant seedlings.**
All children, don't miss the opportunity.

Elijah Muslim's poem "The Decent Girl" also instills in children such concepts as teaching girls to work hard, helping parents with household chores:

Rana is still young, she keeps the house tidy,

Everyone is amazed at his work. Never on a dusty couch.

A small broom in hand, Neighbors see it
Porcelain courtyard, porch... Praise sooner or later.

In conclusion, if the educators of preschool education institutions enrich their lessons with such poems, the formation of spiritual and moral qualities of preschool children will be observed. Children's spiritual qualities such as fluency, memory, expressive poetry reading, listening skills, responsiveness, activity, self-confidence, love of poetry, sense of beauty are developed. There is a desire to act like the heroes in the poems he remembers. This passion, in turn, plays a key role in learning and being active in the later stages of education.

References:

1. Munavvarqori Abdurashidkhonov, Selected works Танланган асарлар. Т.: Маънавият, 2003.
2. Электрон манба: http://www.ziyouz.com/index.php?option=com_content&task=view&id=2580
3. Электрон манба: http://uza.uz/uz/society/maktabgacha-ta-lim-vazirligi-sohada-yangi-tizim-va-amaliyot--30-10-2017.***
4. Davletshin M.G., Sh.Do'stmuhamedova, M.Mavlonov, S.To'ychiyeva. Yosh davrlari va pedagogik psixologiya. O'quv metodik qo'llanma. Т.: 2004.
5. Кадиров Валижон. Мумтоз адабиёт намуналарини ўқитишда методологик асоснинг аҳамияти. *Тил, таълим, таржима* халқаро журнали. 2 (2020) DOI <http://dx.doi.org/10.26739/2181-0796-2020-2>. С.101.

ENLIGHTENMENT-IDEOLOGICAL, LINGUISTIC, GENERAL AESTHETIC COMMONALITIES BETWEEN THE TWO PERIO

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ABSTRACT

The commonality of the enlightenment, ideological, linguistic, general aesthetic views of the English Renaissance with the tragic works of the Jadids can be seen in the following: Their works are united by the ideas of struggle against freedom, enlightenment. In the complex political conditions, the living language of the people, the wisdom of the people's oral creativity, the realities of the time are reflected in the expressions. Emphasis on symbolism at the beginning and end of dramas serves to express the main idea of the drama.

According to Shakespearean scholar F. Suleymanova, 43 years ago: "Scientific critical monographs and articles about Shakespeare in different eras and languages can not fit into any information, bibliographic works. In our country, Shakespeare's works have been translated into almost all languages and are successfully staged in dramatic theaters. Shakespeare's works, scientific-critical monographs and articles dedicated to him, published in the languages of the peoples of Russia and the fraternal republics, have exceeded six and a half thousand.

Shakespeare, a brilliant intellectual, described social life so accurately that his contemporaries, even the sages of the time, did not notice it. and psychologists are amazed that they know and reveal the most delicate aspects of the human heart.

Therefore, V. Belinsky says, "As a poet, it would be utterly bold and surprising to put Shakespeare above the poets of mankind, but as a playwright he is still unmatched, there is no name that can be put next to his name."

While some works of the great English playwright were translated into Russian, Ukrainian, Estonian, and Georgian in the 18th and 19th centuries, Shakespeare's plays were staged in the early 20th century because drama and theater were relatively new.

It is known from history that the Renaissance began in Europe in the second half of the fourteenth century. This socio-political, enlightenment process was called by the Italians - the Quinquecento, the French - the Renaissance, the Germans - the Reformation, the Renaissance in

general. The ideas of equality, justice, freedom of conscience and the love of life, the enjoyment of worldly pleasures, humanist writers find only in folklore. The greatest humanist writers of the Renaissance, Boccaccio, Rable, Cervantes and Shakespeare, took full advantage of this inexhaustible source.

It is known that the struggle for humanistic culture in England began in the 15th century, but as much as the so-called White and Red Wars in history affected its development, the same tragedy occurred in Turkestan in the second half of the 19th century. pushed back progress. Turkestan has been shackled to join the ranks of developing countries. If we look at the history of 16th century England, we see that along with high progress, cruelty, freedom, individual freedom were violated. In the works of Shakespeare and his contemporaries, the most common overt or covert executions, murders, massacres, battles are described. In the last quarter of the 19th century and the beginning of the 20th century, Turkestan also experienced internal divisions and conflicts, and as a result of the growing oppression of the invaders of Tsarist Russia, many popular uprisings took place in the country. Polatkhan said that the Duke Eshan uprising emerged as one of such popular movements, the revolt was brutally suppressed and its leaders were executed. In Fitrat's dramas "The Lion", "True Love", and "Indian Controversy", the tragedies that took place in Turkestan are presented in all their complexity against the background of India.

The similarity of British and Turkestan political life prompted both artists to create works on the same subject.

The art that was able to fully express the spirit of the English Renaissance and to describe in detail the changes in the life of that period was the English Theater and the playwright-led playwright Shakespeare. Since theater was the most popular art by its own specification, Renaissance English theater had become a venue for public gatherings. While most of the population was illiterate, the theater served as both a convenient tool for propagating new ideas and a means of entertainment and spiritual nourishment for various sections of society. In the early twentieth century, attention to theater began. In 1913, the first theater was established, in which Behbudi's drama "Padarkush" was staged for the first time. If we look at two periods, two political situations, the similarity between them is obvious. This was primarily due to the fact that the progressive intelligentsia of society saw art and theater as a means of expressing their dissatisfaction with the dominant ideology. The theater has become a people's pulpit, and the writers, as the builders of this pulpit, called on the people to be aware, to know themselves, to convey the truth and the truth to the people. In Shakespeare's and Fitrat's tragedies, oppression, violence, injustice, intellectual limitations, and all kinds of vices that are unworthy of human dignity are ruthlessly exposed through reference to history, which is evident in the tragedies of Hamlet, Macbeth, and Abulfayzkhan.

The Nur theater group formed in Ufa visited Tashkent, Samarkand, Bukhara and Mari. The Sayyar theater troupe also visited the Caucasus and performed in a number of cities across the country.

In his works, the famous playwright puts the question of a united country and a

centralized state as the leading idea, and thus partially determines the next direction of English tragedy. By this time, the morale of the popular tourist troupes will also begin to change. Shakespeare brings to the stage the image of explicit historical and mythical figures (Pope Rnm, King John, members of the church, historical figures such as Richard III, Henry V, legendary kings such as Arthur or Lear) instead of previous abstract images. Fitrat follows the same path and addresses historical and legendary characters (Abulfayzkhan, Amir Temur, Abo Muslim Khurasani, Nodirshah, MirvafoKarmanagi, Siyavush) in his dramatic works. This is because both playwrights attached great importance to the role of the individual in history. It is sometimes up to individuals to decide which direction to turn history, it is enough to remember the actions of Genghis Khan, Napoleon, Amir Temur. History had given Shakespeare and the Jadids the same historical mission. Fitrat is one of the leading Jadids, a free-thinking leader, and one of the key figures in the formation and development of Uzbek drama with his works.

Shakespearean F.Sulaymonova writes about the peculiarities of English theaters: is also the effect of the element. As mentioned above, the Renaissance was shaped by English drama, theater, and folk theater under the influence of Italian humanistic literature and Roman drama. "The peculiarities of the dramatic works of the English Renaissance can be seen in the content and performance skills of stage plays created in the Uzbek national literature. Although he did not arrive, the Abo Muslim Khorasan, which fought for independence in its name, the Vose Uprising, dedicated to the 1921 Baljuvan

tragedy, the Abulfayzkhan, which was historically dedicated to the Ashtarkhanid brotherhood, and the local violence. "In India, which was the culmination of the British policy of aggression (in fact, these dramas were multi-layered, with Turkestan in the background of India). "True love" and "Indian dissidents" can be called a chain of tragedies of a whole period, the accusations of an ominous reality.

It is impossible to say anything new about the life of Shakespeare, one of the main objects of our research. Although it is always possible to say something new about the works of a great playwright, it is, of course, impossible to make any novelty about his biography. And yet it is impossible to get started even by bypassing the playwright's biography. Based on this logic, we have found it necessary to briefly repeat the facts known to science so far. Shakespeare was born in 1564 in Stratford-upon-Avon, England, to a family of craftsmen. He was the third of 8 children in the family. The father of the future writer was a craftsman who made leather gloves, and because his father became poor, he was forced to drop out of school at the age of 16 and go to work. She gets married two years later. Unable to meet his needs where he lived, he went to London in 1857 and got a job in theater. In the theater, he goes from assistant to assistant to director's partner, and is formed as a playwright in the theater itself. Shakespeare's first works, Venus and Adonis (1593) and Lucretius (1594) on Roman history, were warmly received by the public.

Shakespeare effectively used Holinshed's Chronicle of England, Scotland and Ireland, rich in plots of English history, to create his charming works, which have won a worthy place in the hearts of fans for

centuries. The skilled playwright also wrote Plutarch's Comparative Biographies in the creation of historical tragedies, and M. in the writing of comedies. Bandello's stories of the Italian Renaissance are known to have served as a major source. Even before Shakespeare, many plays were based on tragedies such as Romeo and Juliet, Hamlet, and King Lear, but they gained worldwide fame only because of Shakespeare's extraordinary dramatic skills.

The source from which Shakespeare's work is nourished is the study of the history, literature, and theater of the peoples of Europe, as well as the enjoyment of the gems of advanced thought of that period. He was able to surpass the creators of his time because he was able to combine these two principles in each other. As has been observed throughout all historical periods, the period in which Shakespeare lived was also full of various contradictions and contradictions. Shakespeare was deeply aware of the contradictions of his time, the imbalances in social life, the complexities of human destiny, and at the same time paid special attention to depicting the drama that took place at a critical point in society and human life. As a true playwright, he revealed the social, domestic, spiritual, and spiritual reasons that led to one or another of the characters' behaviors, allowing each of them to fully justify or explain the dramatic changes in their behavior.

In the second period of Shakespeare's work he appeared as a master of poetic drama. He combined tragic and comic motives with a strong emphasis on drama, without abandoning the methods of confrontation during this period. As a result, in Shakespeare's work ("Romeo and Juliet", "Richard II", "Twelfth

Night") dramatic lyricism reached its peak. In the third period of Shakespeare's work, works of the genre of tragedy occupy a leading position. The playwright sees the contradiction between the ideas of humanism and humanism typical of the Renaissance and the growing selfishness, hypocrisy, and evil in reality, and draws these contradictions into his works as a conflict. He reached the pinnacle of artistic mastery in the tragedies he created during the same period. The romantic dramas and tragic comedies of the last period of Shakespeare's work testify to the emergence in his worldview of the hope that life conflicts could be resolved positively.

The first period is the 50s of the XVI century, but in this decade we also see two stages of the playwright's creative evolution: dramatic chronicles imitating his first contemporaries Lily, Green, Kid and Marlowe (three parts of Henry U1, Richard III), comedies ("The Comedy of Misguidance", "The Conquest of Caesar"), the creation of the first tragedy ("Tpt Andronicus") and two poems imitating Ovid ("Venus and Adonis", "Lucretius"), the period of Shakespeare's formation as a playwright and poet; the second is independent mature works ("Richard II", "King John", two parts of "Henry 1U", "Henry U" chronicles, the tragedy "Romeo and Juliet", "Two young men from Verona", "Fruitless attempts of love", "Summer" Dream of the Night ", " Venetian Merchant ", " Riot in vain ", " Windsorian jokers ", " Do you like it ", " Fifteenth Night " comedy and sonnets. Julius Caesar, Hamlet, Othello, King Lear, Macbeth, Anthony and Cleopatra, Coriolanus, Timon of Athens, and comedies with more tragic elements than laughter, such as Troil and Cressida,

The third period is the last years of the playwright's career, from 1608 to his departure from the theater, until 1613, when romantic dramas or tragicomedies ("Pericles", "Tsimbelii", "Winter Tale", "Storm") and the last chronicle ("Henry

VIII ») created period. This evolution in Shakespeare's work is connected not only with the playwright's worldview, the result of his creative growth, but also with the changes in the socio-political life of the country.

References:

1. Jalolov A. Ideas of national and independence in modern literature. // Uzbek language and literature, 1996. Issue 4. 16-23-b.
2. Zingerman B. Analysis of the director's plan "Othello" K.Stanislavskogo. Shekspirovkiysbornik.Moskva, 1958.s 364-396; Gaevskiy B. Djuletta on the ballet stage. Shekspirovkiysbornik.Moskva, 1958.s 397-401;
3. Zubov K. «Makbet» in the small theater Shekspirovkiysbornik.Moskva, 1958.s 453-457;
4. Zubova N. Two variants of "Hamlet" Shekspirovkiysbornik.Moskva, 1958.p 256-290;
5. Ilinskaya O. People in the tragedies of Shakespeare. Shekspirovkiysbornik.Moskva, 1958.s 164-198;
6. Ismatullaev X. Cholpon and the world.// World literature. 1998. Issue 4. 122-137-b.
7. Karimov E. On the life and work of Fitrat // Uzbek language and literature, 1990. Issue 3. 23-29-b.
8. Shodiyev Shaxobiddin Sharofiddinovich, Tasheva Nafisa Zayniddinovna. Eurasian journal of academic research. Innovative academy research support center. www.inacademy.uz. "The role of the way of the great steppe in the continuity and reuttniship of the philosophy and culture of the muslim east and the renaissance west" <https://doi.org/10.528t/zenodo.4921916>
9. Shodiev Shahobiddin Sharofiddinevich, Majitova Nafisa Zokirovna "Ideas about an ideal person, language, prosperity in Evolution of public and political Views of the Uzbek Jadids of the beginning of the XX century" Eurasian journal of academic research. Innovative academy research support center. www.inacademy.uz
10. Шодиев Ш.Ш., & Бакаев Н.Б. (2021). Проблема сущности человека в «Гамлет» Шекспира. Central Asian journal of theoretical & applied sciences, 2(2), 104-112. Retrieved from <https://cajotas.centralasianstudies.org/index.php/CAJOTAS/article/view/82>
11. Шодиев, Ш.Ш. Шекспировский лексикон: слово Reason как обозначение понятия способности человеческого ума к абстракции, умозаключению /– Москва : Вестник науки, 2020. – 189-197 с.
12. Shodiev, Shahobiddin and Majitova, Nafisa, Ideas About an Ideal Person, Language, Prosperity in the Evolution of Public and Political Views of the Uzbek Jadids of the Beginning of the XX Century (June 11, 2021). Eurasian Journal of Academic Research, Volume 1 Issue 03, June 2021, Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=3865220>

13. Shodiev S. S., Shigabutdinova D. Y. Shakespearean lexicon: the word reason as a designation of the concept of the ability of the human mind to abstraction inference //Innovative potential for the development of science in the modern world. – 2020. – C. 189-197.
14. Shahobiddin Sharofiddinovich Shodiev, Najmiddin Bakaevich Bakaev, & Nafisa Zainiddinovna Tasheva (2021). Studying philosophical realities of the renaissance epoch, based on the structural analysis of philosophical texts. Academic research in educational sciences, 2 (8), 28-34. doi: 10.24412/2181-1385-2021-8-28-34
15. Hakimova Mukhabbat Alimovna Central Asian Journal of Literature, Philosophy and Culture “The problem of development and enrichment of the vocabulary of the english language of philosophy in XXI century volume: 02 issue: 10 | october 2021
16. М.А. Хакимова, З.Т. Нематова, Хоразм Ма’mun Akademiyasi “ Формирование Английской Научно-Философской Лексики Периода Европейского Ренессанса” Ахборотномаси –10/2021 412
17. Shodiev Shahobiddin Sharofiddinovich, Khakimova Mukhabbat Alomovna Eurasian journal of academic research Innovative Academy Research Support Center www.inacademy.uz Revenge Idea’s Transformation in “Hamlet” Poem
18. Muhabbat Alimovna Hakimova, Zebo Tursunbayevna Nematova, Dilnoza Anvarovna Ziyayeva International Scientific Journal ISJ Theoretical & Applied Science Philadelphia, USA “ General Basis of Lexico-Semantic Composition of Words”
Journal available by link: <http://t-science.org/arxivDOI/2020/06-86.html>
19. Nematova Zebo Tursunbaevna, Hakimova Muhabbat Alimovna, Молодой ученый Международный научный журнал
№ 50 (340) / 2020 Songs in teaching English to young second language learners
20. The Problem of Development and Enrichment of the Vocabulary of the English Language of Philosophy in XXI Century. HM Alimovna Central Asian Journal of Literature, Philosophy and Culture 2 (10), 61-63
21. Zaynitdinovna, T. N. . (2022). Lyrical Dialogue in Shakespeare’s Poems as a Reflection of Renaissance Anthropocentrism and a Strong Personality. *Middle European Scientific Bulletin*, 21, 120-125. Retrieved from <http://cejssr.academicjournal.io/index.php/journal/article/view/1085>
22. Zayniddinovna, T. N. . (2022). The Problem of “A Strong Personality” in Shakespeare’ Dramas: Richard III and Macbeth. *Middle European Scientific Bulletin*, 20, 7-10. <https://doi.org/10.47494/mesb.2022.20.1006>
23. Zayniddinovna, T. N. “The Image of the Eastern Ruler in the Works of Christopher Marlowe”. CENTRAL ASIAN JOURNAL OF SOCIAL SCIENCES AND HISTORY, Vol. 2, no. 10, Oct. 2021, pp. 10-14, <https://cajssh.centralasianstudies.org/index.php/CAJSSH/article/view/173>.
24. Zayniddinovna, T. N., and S. S. Sharofiddinovich. “General Cultural and Educational Values of Ancient-Classic Latin Language”. CENTRAL ASIAN JOURNAL OF THEORETICAL & APPLIED SCIENCES, Vol. 2, no. 5, May 2021, pp. 77-80, <https://cajotas.centralasianstudies.org/index.php/CAJOTAS/article/view/157>.

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Идеи об идеальном человеке, языке, процветании в эволюции

Общественно-политических взглядов узбекских джадидов начала XX века

Нематова Зебо Турсунбаевна Хакимова Мухаббат Алимовна

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26. Norova M.F. Connotative meanings in phonetic variants of verbal root-stems (as an example of the English and Uzbek languages) //Research & Development. EPRAInternational OnlineJournal. – India, 2020. – №10(5). – P. 358-362. (Impact Factor SJIF 7.001).

27. Norova M.F. Connotative meanings in phonetic variants of verbal root-stems (as an example of the English and Uzbek languages) //Theoretical & Applied Science. – 2020. – №1. – P. 439-442.

28. Djalilova Z. O. STUDIES ON GENDER LINGUISTICS IN THE FIELD OF UZBEK LANGUAGE //Academic research in educational sciences. – 2021. – Т. 2. – №. 3.

29. Obidovna D. Z. Comparative Analysis Of Uzbek Men's And Women's Speech Through The Prism Of Gender Linguistics //Central Asian journal of literature, philosophy and culture. – 2021. – Т. 2. – №. 2. – С. 22-26.

30. Obidovna D. Z. Gender issues in foreign theoretical linguistics: concerning the history of the issue //Gender issues. – 2021. – Т. 7. – №. 6.

31. Habibova, M. N. (2021). Jorjina Houelling “Queen of the desert” biografik asarida gertruda Bell timsoli tasviri. Academic research in educational sciences, 2(2), 770-778. <https://doi.org/10.24411/2181-1385-2021-00260>

32. Habibova, M. N. (2021). The theme feminism in the epistolary novels in modern times. ISJ Theoretical & Applied Science, 11 (103), 1101-1105. Soi: <http://s-o-i.org/1.1/TAS-11-103-124> Doi: <https://dx.doi.org/10.15863/TAS.2021.11.103.124>

THE HISTORY OF THE RUSSIAN EPISTOLARY NOVEL IN EIGHTEENTH CENTURY

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ABSTRACT

The article explains the concept of epistolary genre in Russian literature in eighteenth century, the study of the early development of the Russian novel, analysis of the institutional conditions of literature and their impact on literary tendencies.

The history of the Russian novel can be traced back to early medieval times with manuscript translations of Byzantine novels. However, it was only in the eighteenth century that Russian novelistic fiction started to appear in print and that educated Russians thought it no disgrace to confess that they themselves were authors of such texts. The acceptance of something like literature as an estimable cultural expression, and indirectly of the novel as an important literary genre, was only possible within conditions created by the reforms of Peter the Great. One of these conditions was an intense conversance with the secular culture of Western Europe. It follows that eighteenth-century Russian literature stands less in a closed national tradition that developed gradually from

medieval times, than that it adopts its ideas and forms from a stockpile of thousands of years of European literature.

The early development of the Russian novel was determined by two significant factors. The first was the reform of Russian society that Peter the Great started around 1700, thereby creating the conditions from which a secular literature could emerge. The second was the state's relaxation of its control of printing presses during the 1760's, which resulted in a growing number of private persons publishing works of their own interest. These two factors in particular make all the difference between the development of the novel in Russia and Western Europe, where a secular culture had existed since the Middle Ages and the state had never

exercised complete control over book production. The emergence of secular literature one of the main characteristics of Russian culture before Peter's reforms was the dominance of the Orthodox Church. In Russia, the church had absolute control over all printing presses and never published works it considered immaterial to the salvation of the soul, in particular something as secular as literature.

Therefore, works of narrative fiction like *facetae* and western European novels of chivalry, made to look like native folk tales by the creative additions of Russian copyists, were not allowed to appear in print and were sold only as shabby handwritten folios, for example at the stalls at Moscow's Bridge of the Redeemer.

Peter the Great restricted the influence of the church, introducing a new and in essence secular mentality to Russian culture. Subscribing to the modern belief that man could improve himself and his environment, he tried to exploit the potential of his people and his country to the fullest.¹ For this purpose he needed the technical and organisational skills developed in Western Europe, so he required that all who entered his service should receive a European-style education. Russian noblemen, for their part, used this obligatory education to distinguish themselves from other social groups by linking the concept of nobility with personal refinement, the appreciation of art and literature and even the ability to produce literary works.

By 1750 literature had become a noble occupation. The secular notion of literature that attached cultural prestige to non-

religious texts thus entered Russia as a result of Peter's reforms and the consequent change in status of the Russian civil service class. The absence of social institutions operating independently from the state characterised eighteenth-century Russian society.² It was the state now that took over the church's control of education and printing presses.³ Thus, the new Russian literature evolved in close connection with the state. Authors were servants of the state and clients of the developing imperial court. They often tried to please the head of state or one of his favourites and tended to express the ideas of the emperor or one of the bureaucratic factions. In the second half of the eighteenth century, the Russian government became aware of the fact that the exploitation of the country's wealth would improve if more private initiative were allowed.⁴ With this aim, the nobility was exempted from obligatory state service, while at the same time room opened up to publicly express ideas not directly dictated by the state. In this way Catherine's government created an atmosphere of tolerance that, although restricted in the modern sense, was free enough for literature to flourish. These changes in the institutional conditions of literature had their impact on literary tendencies. During the first half of the eighteenth century, Russian literature was dominated by a small group of authors closely connected with the court and

¹ Raeff, M.: *The Well-Ordered Police State. Social and Institutional Change through Law in the Germanies and Russia, 1600-1800.* New Haven/London, 1983. P.204

² Raeff, M.: *Understanding Imperial Russia. State and Society in the Old Regime.* New York, 1984.

³ Marker, G.: *Publishing, Printing, and the Origins of Intellectual Life in Russia, 1700-1800.* Princeton, NJ, 1985.

⁴ Raeff, M.: *The Well-Ordered Police State. Social and Institutional Change through Law in the Germanies and Russia, 1600-1800.* New Haven/London, 1983.

governmental institutions such as the Academy of Science. The most prominent of these authors were Vasilii Trediakovskii, Mikhail Lomonosov and Aleksandr Sumarokov. This limited circle of authors produced works that adhered to the same classicist set of literary rules, so that the period can be defined simply as "The Age of Classicism". However, this homogeneity was destroyed after 1760 when more people started to produce literature. Those classicist works still being published had to compete with literary works of many diverging tendencies.⁵

The debate about the novel The greater availability of the printing presses caused a "boom of books", in which one literary genre clearly dominated: the novel.⁶ While visitors of an early eighteenth-century Russian bookstore had only a handful of translated prose works to choose from, such as Fénelon's "Télémaque" or Lesage's "Gil Bias", after 1760 they were confronted with shelves sagging under the weight of novels. However, in the eighteenth century, the novel was still a disputed genre, and its appearance in Russia sparked off a debate about its moral and literary merits, repeating on a small scale the discussions held in France for over a century. The arguments for and against the novel were of an ideological and aesthetic nature.⁷ First, the novel was said to offend Christian morality. It was considered immoral because of the depiction of human passions

such as love. In 1730, representatives of the Russian Orthodox Church accused Vasilii Trediakovskii of corrupting youth in connection with his translation of abbé Tallemant's "Journey to the Island of Love" (*Voyage de l'Isle d'Amour*) (1663), which was in fact the first novel printed in Russian. In his "Rhetoric" (*Ritorika*) of 1748 Lomonosov held the novel responsible for some people's "persistence in animal passions", a reproach echoed by Aleksandr Sumarokov, who in his "Letter on the Reading of Novels" of 1759 accused novelists of writing "bestial descriptions".⁸ In 1766, the enlightened government of Catherine II widely distributed Ivan Betskoi's educational "Brief Instructions", which advised that love novels be withheld from young people on the grounds that they led to moral corruption. A second argument against the novel was that the illusions and false realities created by this genre made it incompatible with Enlightenment ideology.

Lomonosov compared novels with "fairy tales" and Sumarokov praised Cervantes novelistic work because it showed convincingly how readers of novels run the risk of turning into foolish Don Quixotes. In addition, the novel raised desires that could not be realised without destroying the existing social order. For this reason young girls of marriageable age should not read about true love, nor should peasants read about the pleasant lives of nobles." Indulgence in the novel's wish-fulfilling world contradicted the neo-stoic ideals of Russian civil servants. The novel had a potentially subversive quality. The moral arguments against the novel were in many ways intertwined with aesthetic

⁵ Marker, G.: Publishing, Printing, and the Origins of Intellectual Life in Russia, 1700-1800. Princeton, NJ, 1985.

⁶ Sevast'ianov, A.N. Rost obrazovannoi auditorii kak faktor razvitiia knizhnogo i zhurnal'nogo dela v Rossii (1762-1800). M., 1983.

⁷ May, G.: Le Dilemme du Roman au XVIIIe siècle. New Haven/Paris, 1963.

⁸ Lomonosov, M. V. Polnoe sobranie sochinenii. M.: L., 1950-1959.

ones. It seems that the demand for social discipline was reflected in literary discipline, and it should not be surprising that in the mind of a poet like Sumarokov stoic virtues blended with classicist beauties. In his article of 1759 against the novel, Sumarokov opposes “distasteful romance-like style”⁹, meaning an extravagant narration, to a “natural style”, which uses purist, and abstract, universal terms. He associated both styles with moral categories, identifying the ugly ‘romance-like’ or romanesque with immoral, unrestrained behaviour, and the beautiful natural style with a moral, disciplined mode of conduct.¹⁰ It seemed that those who identified with state’s best interest and endorsed its authority felt that any tolerance shown to literature, any loosening of literary restrictions in favour of the novel, would similarly lead to a relaxing of discipline in social behaviour.¹¹ The historians of the western-European novel indeed associate the genre with a dissolution of authoritarian social structures, linking its rise to democratic movements, such as the emergence of the bourgeoisie. A similar picture can be painted of the Russian novel. Whereas Russian novelistic prose was initially allowed to exist only as manuscript literature, beyond the reach of authority, it subsequently emerged in print when enlightened government permitted a freer and less controlled social life. Literature, and especially those forms that presupposed reading in private, like the

⁹ Sumarokov, A.P.: *Polnoe sobranie vsexh sochincnii v stikhakh i proze*. M., 1781.

¹⁰ Sumarokov, A.P.: *Polnoe sobranie vsexh sochincnii v stikhakh i proze*. M., 1781.

¹¹ May, G.: *Le Dilemme du Roman au XVIIIe siècle*. New Haven/Paris, 1963.

novel, became one of the vehicles of such desires. The novel constituted, as it were, a transitional zone between the individual and society, protected from the imperatives of real life. It was by virtue of this non-coercive nature that the novel could turn “into the inescapable biosphere of our daydreams”, as the first historian of the Russian novel, Grigorii Blagosvetlov, wrote.¹² The epistolary novel in particular had the potential to give voice to the emancipatory desires harboured by many members of the eighteenth-century Russian civil service class.

Conclusion. As the obstacles to be transgressed in the Russian epistolary novels are taken from actual conditions of social reality, Russian readers must have read these novels as energised with real social tensions. To a certain degree fiction is analogous to fantasy and dreams, however, in literature there is always a moment of conscious reflection. So literary fiction is not only structured by desire, but also by the opposing forces of reality. So the course of the narrative, the way the narrative is told, is not only determined by desire, but as much by a sense of reality, by a need to conform to social demands. From this perspective it appears that the formal characteristics of the epistolary novel correspond with psychological functions. These characteristics, especially in the way Russian authors applied them, offered specific possibilities to reflect on desire and its relationship with social reality. In short, the epistolary novels under discussion can be seen as an endeavour by some Russian authors to give meaning to the conflicting forces of desire and social

¹² Blagosvetlov, A.: *Istoricheskii ocherk russkago prozaicheskago romana li Syn otechestva*. No. 27. Spb., 1856.

reality and to solve this conflict through a fictitious construct. Therefore, despite their apparent simplicity, these early, sometimes long-neglected Russian texts may give an

especially clear insight into hearts and minds of eighteenth-century Russians, shedding new light on the complexities of their lives.

References:

1. Raeff, M.: *The Well-Ordered Police State. Social and Institutional Change through Law in the Germanies and Russia, 1600-1800.* New Haven/London, 1983.
2. Raeff, M.: *Understanding Imperial Russia. State and Society in the Old Regime.* New York, 1984.
3. Marker, G.: *Publishing, Printing, and the Origins of Intellectual Life in Russia, 1700-1800.* Princeton, NJ, 1985.
4. Sevast'ianov, A.N. *Рост образованной аудитории как фактор развития книжного и журнального дела в России (1762-1800).* М., 1983.
5. May, G.: *Le Dilemme du Roman au XVIIIe siècle.* New Haven/Paris, 1963.
6. Lomonosov, M. V. *Polnoe sobranie sochinenii.* М.:Л., 1950-1959.
7. Sumarokov, A.P.: *Polnoe sobranie vseh sochincii v stikhakh i proze.* М., 1781.
8. Blagosvetlov, A.: *Istoricheskii ocherk russkago prozaicheskago romana li Synotechestva.* No. 27. Spb., 1856.
9. Khayrullayeva, K. R. (2020). Description of Zahiriddin Babur's achievements in various fields in the works of Uzbek and world authors. *ISJ Theoretical & Applied Science*, 09 (89), 8-11. SoI: <http://s-o-i.org/1.1/TAS-09-89-2> Doi: <https://dx.doi.org/10.15863/TAS.2020.09.89.2>
10. Djalilova Z. O. Studies on gender linguistics in the field of Uzbek language // *Academic research in educational sciences.* – 2021. – Т. 2. – №. 3.
11. Davlatova M.H. Variability of Aspectual Meanings in English.-*European Journal of Research and Reflection in Educational Science*, Volume.7 No.12.2019.-P.778-780
12. Zayniddinovna, T. N. "The Image of the Eastern Ruler in the Works of Christopher Marlowe". *CENTRAL ASIAN JOURNAL OF SOCIAL SCIENCES AND HISTORY*, Vol. 2, no. 10, Oct. 2021, pp. 10-14, <https://cajssh.centralasianstudies.org/index.php/CAJSSH/article/view/173>.
13. Нематова, Зебо Турсунбаевна, and Мухаббат Алимовна Хакимова. "Songs in teaching English to young second language learners." *Молодой ученый* 50 (2020): 497-499.

VARIOUS TYPES OF ASSESSMENT IN LANGUAGE TEACHING AND LEARNING

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ABSTRACT

This article will first explain the diagnostic assessment's meaning, list the types of diagnostic assessment, along with relevant diagnostic assessment examples. Then it will illustrate the importance of diagnostic assessment in education. We will also cover the advantages and disadvantages of diagnostic assessment in education.

Quality control is of utmost importance in every industry and sphere of life. Assessments are a useful way of maintaining quality. In the education field, the assessment process utilizes empirical data on student learning to make the learning process more effective and enhance student development. Assessment is the process of collecting useful and relevant data and information from various sources to develop insights into students' understanding, knowledge, and takeaways from the educational experience.

There are various types of assessments available to assess progress and skill levels for this purpose. These are:
Diagnostic Assessment: The purpose of diagnostic assessment is to gauge students' knowledge, skills, strength, and weaknesses beforehand.

Formative Assessment: This is used to collect information on students' understanding throughout the learning process to help teachers adjust their strategies accordingly.

Summative Assessment: This is used to measure students' knowledge after a subject has been taught.

Ipsative Assessment: It is used to track students' performance by comparing their current scores with their past scores.

Norm-referenced Assessment: It is used to compare and rank a group of students.

Criterion-referenced Assessment: It is used to compare a student's score to a set learning standard or performance level.

This article will first explain the diagnostic assessment's meaning, list the types of diagnostic assessment, along with relevant diagnostic assessment examples. Then it will illustrate

the importance of diagnostic assessment in education. We will also cover the advantages and disadvantages of diagnostic assessment in education.

The purpose of diagnostic assessments is to help identify problems with a certain instruction style and provide insights into improvement that can be done in the quality of delivery. Diagnostic assessments in education help educators understand their students' strengths, weaknesses, knowledge level, and skillset prior to beginning instruction. Diagnostic assessment examples include pre-assessment tests that give you a snapshot of or diagnose knowledge to screen students.

For instance, if a teacher wants to start a lesson on two-digit multiplication with young pupils, they can use diagnostic assessment to make sure the lesson is delivered well. They will want to understand if the students have grasped fact families, number place values, and one-digit multiplication before moving on to more complicated questions.

Diagnostic assessments collect data on what the students already know about a specific subject or topic.

These diagnostic assessment examples will make the diagnostic assessment meaning clearer. The following are ways in which instructors from different fields use various types of diagnostic assessment tools:

Introductory physics: A set of conceptual questions is used to assess understanding of physics fundamentals at the start of the course.

Psychology: The instructor conducts a survey to understand students' assumptions about concepts such as the

nature of mind versus the nature of behavior.

Course with group work: The instructor rolls out a self-assessment, where group members rate themselves on certain parameters. Specific examples of their previous group work are collected to understand each individual's mindset.

Creative or fine arts: The instructor collects portfolios to judge the artistic abilities of fine arts students.

There are various types of assessments available to assess progress and skill levels for this purpose. These are:

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Assessment: It is used to compare a student's score to a set learning standard or performance level.

Assessments come in many shapes and sizes. For those who are new to assessment or just starting out, the terms can be hard to sort out or simply unfamiliar. Knowing one type of assessment from another can be a helpful way to understand how best to

use assessment to your advantage. That's why we've taken the time to layout the different types of assessment for you in this post.

The multi-faceted nature of assessments means that educators can leverage them in a number of ways to provide valuable formal or informal structure to the learning process. The main thing to remember is that the assessment is a learning tool. What all assessments have in common is that they provide a snapshot of student understanding at a particular time in the learning process.

Reasonably so, when you were a student yourself, you may not have been aware of the variety of assessments that teachers leverage. To the average student, or anyone who has ever been a student, the word 'test' has a pretty clear cut definition and it usually includes some level of anxiety and expectation about a final outcome. But, to educators, tests – or assessments – are actually quite multi-faceted and have both formal and informal places throughout the learning process.

Assessments can run the gamut from start to finish when it comes to instruction. Think of it like a long distance race that has a start and finish line and many stations to refuel in between. The race can be any instructional period of time, such as a unit, a quarter, or even the full year. In this metaphor, the student is the runner and the teacher is the coach who is trying to help the student run the race as well as they possibly can. Different assessments types, when utilized by the coach (teacher) in the right way, can help the runner (student) run the race better and more effectively.

Here are some more types of diagnostic assessments that can be used for

assessing students: Journals, quiz/test, conference/interview, posters, performance tasks, mind maps, gap-closing, student surveys, anticipation guides.

There are various advantages of different types of diagnostic assessment in education that help achieve the purpose of diagnostic assessment, which is to improve quality. These are:

They provide insights to educators to create customized instructions.

They are usually informal and easy to use.

They don't require high-level training and don't have standardized protocols to follow.

Teachers can further refine or change their methods at any time. For instance, a teacher can start with easier diagnostic assessment examples and then move on to journals or audits.

Such assessments show quick results once you're used to them.

Instructors can easily share their learnings with their peers.

The drawbacks of diagnostic assessment could be:

They don't take into consideration anything that needs to be done post the delivery of a lesson.

The importance of diagnostic assessments also diminishes in large groups.

A teacher may develop inaccurate assumptions about the student's knowledge of a subject and overlook that particular topic during the unit.

Students new to this kit can become anxious.

Generally, for this assessment to be administered correctly and executed reliably, special training may be required.

Plus, this whole process is quite time-consuming.

In summary, the diagnostic assessment serves to know the situation of the students, exactly what is needed to increase their knowledge, and first of all provides very useful information that will

help the teachers to better plan their lessons. Obviously, this is a necessary tool that needs to be done from time to time to know what decisions are best to make in this way students could choose the right path for their education.

References:

1. Cohen, Bella. Diagnostic assessment at the superior-distinguished threshold. Salinas, CA: MSI Press, 2003.
2. Fagan, William T. Monitoring literacy performance: Assessment and diagnostic tasks . Examiner's manual. Montréal PQ: Éditions de la chenelière, 1992.
3. Crooks, T. (2001). "The Validity of Formative Assessments". British Educational Research Association Annual Conference, University of Leeds, September 13–15, 2001.
4. Huhta, Ari (2010). "Diagnostic and Formative Assessment". In Spolsky, Bernard; Hult, Francis M. (eds.). The Handbook of Educational Linguistics. Oxford, UK: Blackwell. pp. 469–482.
5. Shodiev S. S., Shigabutdinova D. Y. Shakespearean lexicon: the word reason as a designation of the concept of the ability of the human mind to abstraction inference //Innovative potential for the development of science in the modern world. – 2020. – C. 189-197.
6. Shahobiddin Sharofiddinovich Shodiev, Najmiddin Bakaevich Bakaev, & Nafisa Zainiddinovna Tasheva (2021). Studying philosophical realities of the renaissance epoch, based on the structural analysis of philosophical texts. Academic research in educational sciences, 2 (8), 28-34. doi: 10.24412/2181-1385-2021-8-28-34
7. Hakimova Mukhabbat Alimovna *Central Asian Journal of Literature, Philosophy and Culture* "The problem of development and enrichment of the vocabulary of the english language of philosophy in XXI century volume: 02 issue: 10 | october 2021
8. М.А. Хакимова, З.Т. Нематова, Хоразм Ма'мун Академияси "Формирование Английской Научно-Философской Лексики Периода Европейского Ренессанса" *Axborotnomasi* -10/2021 412
9. Shodiev Shahobiddin Sharofiddinovich, Khakimova Mukhabbat Alomovna *Eurasian journal of academic research Innovative Academy Research Support Center* www.inacademy.uz *Revenge Idea's Transformation in "Hamlet" Poem*
10. Muhabbat Alimovna Hakimova, Zebo Tursunbayevna Nematova, Dilnoza Anvarovna Ziyayeva *International Scientific Journal ISJ Theoretical & Applied Science Philadelphia, USA* "General Basis of Lexico-Semantic Composition of Words"
Journal available by link: <http://t-science.org/arxivDOI/2020/06-86.html>

11. Nematova Zebo Tursunbaevna, Hakimova Muhabbat Alimovna, Молодой ученый
Международный научный журнал
№ 50 (340) / 2020 Songs in teaching English to young second language learners
12. The Problem of Development and Enrichment of the Vocabulary of the English Language of Philosophy in XXI Century. HM Alimovna Central Asian Journal of Literature, Philosophy and Culture 2 (10), 61-63
13. Zaynitdinovna, T. N. . (2022). Lyrical Dialogue in Shakespeare's Poems as a Reflection of Renaissance Anthropocentrism and a Strong Personality. *Middle European Scientific Bulletin*, 21, 120-125. Retrieved from <http://cejsr.academicjournal.io/index.php/journal/article/view/1085>
14. Zayniddinovna, T. N. . (2022). The Problem of "A Strong Personality" in Shakespeare' Dramas: Richard III and Macbeth. *Middle European Scientific Bulletin*, 20, 7-10. <https://doi.org/10.47494/mesb.2022.20.1006>
15. Zayniddinovna, T. N. "The Image of the Eastern Ruler in the Works of Christopher Marlowe". CENTRAL ASIAN JOURNAL OF SOCIAL SCIENCES AND HISTORY, Vol. 2, no. 10, Oct. 2021, pp. 10-14, <https://cajssh.centralasianstudies.org/index.php/CAJSSH/article/view/173>.
16. Zayniddinovna, T. N., and S. S. Sharofiddinovich. "General Cultural and Educational Values of Ancient-Classic Latin Language". CENTRAL ASIAN JOURNAL OF THEORETICAL & APPLIED SCIENCES, Vol. 2, no. 5, May 2021, pp. 77-80, <https://cajotas.centralasianstudies.org/index.php/CAJOTAS/article/view/157>.
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19. Norova M.F. Connotative meanings in phonetic variants of verbal root-stems (as an example of the English and Uzbek languages) //Research & Development. EPRA International Online Journal. – India, 2020. – №10(5). – P. 358-362. (Impact Factor SJIF 7.001).
20. Norova M.F. Connotative meanings in phonetic variants of verbal root-stems (as an example of the English and Uzbek languages) //Theoretical & Applied Science. – 2020. – №1. – P. 439-442.
21. Djalilova Z. O. Studies on Gender Linguistics in the Field of Uzbek Language //Academic research in educational sciences. – 2021. – Т. 2. – №. 3.
22. Obidovna D. Z. Comparative Analysis Of Uzbek Men's And Women's Speech Through The Prism Of Gender Linguistics //Central Asian journal of literature, philosophy and culture. – 2021. – Т. 2. – №. 2. – С. 22-26.

23. Obidovna D. Z. Gender issues in foreign theoretical linguistics: concerning the history of the issue // Gender issues. – 2021. – Т. 7. – №. 6.
24. Habibova, M. N. (2021). Jorjina Houellning “Queen of the desert” biografik asarida gertruda Bell timsoli tasviri. Academic research in educational sciences, 2(2), 770-778. <https://doi.org/10.24411/2181-1385-2021-00260>
25. Habibova, M. N. (2021). The theme feminism in the epistolary novels in modern times. ISJ Theoretical & Applied Science, 11 (103), 1101-1105. Soi: <http://s-o-i.org/1.1/TAS-11-103-124> Doi: <https://dx.doi.org/10.15863/TAS.2021.11.103.124>
26. Radjabova A. T. Studying Names of Uzbek Dishes as Parts of Lexeme // Science and world. – 2013. – С. 61.
27. Раджабова А. Т. Изучение названий английских блюд как часть лексемы // Наука и мир. – 2016. – Т. 2. – №. 9. – С. 59-60.

METHODOLOGICAL BASIS OF MASTERING FOREIGN LANGUAGE

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ABSTRACT

This article is aimed at methodological analysis and identification of the most pressing issues related to teaching a foreign language in educational institutions. Teaching foreign languages in the era of globalization has its own characteristics and problems: first of all, it is a change in the content of teaching a foreign language, methods and means of teaching in accordance with the requirements of modern society. The most important and relevant aspect of effective foreign language teaching in our time is the use of Internet information resources, their integration into the educational process for the productive solution of a number of didactic tasks in the classroom. Learning a foreign language in modern realities should be carried out in the course of performing productive types of work - listening to foreign language speech, reading texts, writing and speaking. All these activities are considered not as an end in themselves, but as a way for students to solve specific personally important problems and tasks.

The topical issue today is what should be a foreign language lesson in modern conditions. The goals and content of education are changing, new means and technologies of education are emerging, but no matter what reforms are carried out, the lesson remains the eternal and main form of education. No matter what innovations are introduced, participants in the educational process meet only in the classroom: the teacher and the student.

The goal of teaching a foreign language today is no longer achievable by simply

communicating a certain amount of knowledge that students must memorize and reproduce. Simultaneously with arming with knowledge and on its basis, it is necessary to teach students the methods of cognition and practical activity that mankind has developed.

Main part

A foreign language lesson has a special specificity that a foreign language teacher cannot ignore. At present, the global goal of mastering a foreign language is considered to be familiarization with a different

culture and participation in the dialogue of cultures. This goal is achieved through the formation of the ability to intercultural communication. It is teaching, organized on the basis of tasks of a communicative nature, teaching foreign language communication, using all the tasks and techniques necessary for this, that is a distinctive feature of a foreign language lesson.

Training aimed at the formation of communicative competence can only take place in the conditions of a personality-oriented and activity approach. Learning to communicate should take place in the course of performing productive types of work - listening to foreign language speech, reading texts, writing and speaking. All these activities are considered not as an end in themselves, but as a way for students to solve specific personally important problems and tasks. The personality-oriented (personality-activity) approach is based on taking into account the individual characteristics of the trainees, who are considered as individuals with their own characteristics, inclinations and interests.

Training in accordance with this approach involves:

- independence of students in the learning process, which is often expressed in the definition of the goals and objectives of the course by the students themselves, in the choice of methods that are preferable for them;
- reliance on the existing knowledge of students, on his experience;
- taking into account the sociocultural characteristics of students and their

lifestyle, encouraging the desire to be "oneself";

- taking into account the emotional state of students, as well as their moral, ethical and moral values;
- purposeful formation of learning skills, characteristic of a particular student learning strategies;
- redistribution of roles in the educational process: limiting the leading role of the teacher, assigning the teacher the functions of an assistant, consultant, adviser

In a modern foreign language lesson, students, together with the teacher, carry out joint activities. The teacher becomes the organizer of the educational, collectively distributed activities of students, an equal participant in the dialogue. The teacher leads to awareness of the problem, shows, reminds, consults. He creates a situation of success, empathizes, encourages,

inspires confidence, stimulates, forms the motives for teaching, shows encouraging exactingness, coordinates, strengthens the authority of the student among his comrades. Students set and solve educational problems, control and evaluate their activities, compare, analyze, classify, model, communicate, defend their point of view, listen and hear classmates, actively interact, plan and control joint activities.

Modern approaches are of great importance in the organization of the learning process, but despite this, there are also some shortcomings, the elimination of which can significantly improve its quality, as well as be a good help for the teacher in the implementation of modern approaches to the organization of the learning process.

With the use of computers, this is excluded, since the visualization required in the lessons and the situations on the monitors are quite real - the "images" move, speak English, ask questions, etc. Some teachers may ask: won't the lesson turn from creative work into something entertaining? No, because in order to get a good grade when working with a computer, a student has to work creatively. He does everything with joy, and the teacher has to purchase the necessary electronic textbooks and make a selection of the necessary situations from them, as well as print out additional questions and texts and transfer them to all computers so that at a certain point in the lesson, students can sit down at certain computers, find and open desired folder in "My Documents", perform, for example, a listening or reading test. It's a lot of work, but it pays off. The joy of learning - that's what gives the use of computers in the classroom. And this, in turn, along with the development of thinking leads to the development of initiative speech.

Each person has an internal motive aimed at cognitive activity. The task of the teacher is to contribute in every possible way to the development of this motive, not to let it fade away. Now there is a wide variety of modern multimedia programs, where you can find enough exercises for students of all ages and different knowledge. Sounds, words, phrases and sentences are perceived by students by ear and visually. Students have the opportunity to observe articulation movements on the computer screen and perceive the correct intonation by ear. At the same time, due to the rather high imitative abilities of

students, the correct samples are imprinted in their memory.

The computerization of our society is calling for life and the emergence of more and more people who want and can use these smart machines in everyday life. Computers make life easier and more interesting. After all, if with the help of this machine within an hour or two you can attend training courses on the Internet in any subject of the school and extracurricular programs, see the world in its current state and diversity, communicate with a huge mass of different people and gain access to libraries, museums and exhibitions that one can only dream of, then there really is no better means for self-development and individual education and self-education. The use of Internet resources and computer presentations in English lessons.

Now everyone understands that the Internet has enormous information capabilities and no less impressive services. The Internet creates a unique opportunity for foreign language learners to use authentic texts, listen and communicate with native speakers. It is important to decide for what purposes we are going to use its capabilities and resources. For instance:

- to include the materials of the network in the content of the lesson,
- for students to independently search for information as part of the work on the project,

Using the information resources of the Internet, it is possible, by integrating them into the educational process, to more

effectively solve a number of didactic tasks in the lesson:

- to develop reading skills and abilities, directly using the materials of the network of varying degrees of complexity,

- improve listening skills based on authentic Internet audio texts, also prepared by the teacher accordingly,

improve the skills of monologue and dialogic utterance on the basis of a problematic discussion of the materials presented by the teacher or one of the students of the network,

- replenish your vocabulary, both active and passive, with the vocabulary of a modern foreign language, reflecting a certain stage in the development of the culture of the people, the social and political structure of society,

- get acquainted with cultural knowledge, including speech etiquette, especially the speech behavior of various peoples in terms of communication, cultural features, traditions of the country of the language being studied.

Conclusion

In conclusion I would like to add that it is also optimal to create multimedia Power Point presentations. The use of computer presentations in the classroom allows you to introduce new lexical, country-specific

material in the most exciting form, the principle of visibility is implemented, which contributes to a solid assimilation of information. Independent creative work of students to create computer presentations is the best way to expand the stock of active vocabulary.

The tasks of education modernization cannot be solved without the optimal implementation of information technologies in all its spheres. The use of information technology gives impetus to the development of new forms and content of traditional activities of students, which leads to their mastering and implementation at a higher level. Working with a computer should be organized in such a way that from the very first lessons of the initial stage of education it becomes a powerful psychological and pedagogical means of forming a need-motivational plan for students' activities, a means of maintaining and further developing their interest in the subject being studied. Properly organized work of students with a computer can contribute, in particular, to the growth of their cognitive and communicative interest, which in turn will contribute to the activation and expansion of the opportunities for independent work of students in mastering the English language, both in the classroom and outside of school hours.

References:

1. Schukin A.N. Textbook for teachers and students. – M.: Philomatis, 2004. – p. 416.
2. Hutchinson T., Waters; A. English for Specific Purposes: a learning-centered approach. – Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2005. – 183 p.
3. Polyakov O.G. Theoretical and practical aspects of the development of profile-oriented programs in English // IYaSh. - 2004. - No. 7. - S. 12-16.

4. Swales J. Genre Analysis: English in academic and research settings / J. Swales. – Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 1990. – 272 p.
5. Lewis M. & Hill J. Practical Techniques for Language Teaching. - London: Longman, 1992. - 143 p.
6. Tsaturova I.A. The paradigm of language education in higher education in the 21st century is “teaching students to learn” // Education and Society. - 2004. - No. 4. [Electronic pecypc]. URL: http://education.recom.m/3_2004/46.html
7. Abramova I.G. Active teaching methods in higher education. – M.: Gardarika, 2008. – 368 p.
8. Rogers T. Methodology in the New Millennium // English Teaching Forum. - 2000. - Vol. 38. - No 2. - P. 2-13.
9. Tosun V.C. A New Challenge in the Methodology of the Post-Method Era // Journal of Language and Linguistic Studies. – October 2009. – Vol. 5. - No. 2. - P. 10-15.
10. Nuttal C. Teaching Reading Skills in a Foreign Language. (2nd edn.). – Oxford: Heinemann, 1996.

TRANSFER OF PHRASEOLOGICAL UNITS DURING TRANSLATION

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One of the most difficult and controversial tasks in the translation process is the translation of phraseological units. Therefore, the process is the translation of phraseological units requires a lot of responsibility. creativity, care and skill from the person who translates. In terms of comparison, the study of Phraseologisms is of great importance, since they serve to enrich the speech activity of students. When teaching the Russian language, creating an adequate translation, understanding the author's style of translation, the ability to reflect the national flavor in translation is an important link. The translation of phraseological units is of great importance in reflecting the individual author's style in translation.

ABSTRACT

This article provides comprehensive information on the transfer of phraseological units. Pupils are given on equivalent translation of artistic works in the process of translation.

Fedorov: "Translation is considered, first of all, as a speech work in its relation to the original and inconnection with the peculiarities of the two languages and with the belonging of the material to one or another genre category". Thanks to literary translation, the phraseological stock of the students' language is enriched. Winged phrases cannot literally fly, but with their figurative flight they make our speech more interesting and dynamic. We did not invent Phraseologisms in the process of dialogue, but we take them from linguistic memory, like ready-made bricks for building a figurative and expressive speech. That is why it is important to read a lot of fiction during your student years in order to replenish vocabulary and phraseological stock. Phraseologisms make our speech figurative and lively, they help convey more meaning and do it emotionally and expressively.

Phraseology plays an incomparable role in reflecting the national spirit expressed in the language of fiction. In translation activities, the translation of phraseological units takes the main place. Therefore, the translator himself must be personally aware of this problem. Scientist-translator A. B. Fedorov considers it expedient to use the following method when translating phraseological units:

1. Accurate translation of phraseological units with full preservation of the meaning of their structure.
2. With a partial change in the meaning or form of the phraseological units of the original.
3. The ability to translate phraseological units by selection phraseological units to the originals of their corresponding analogs in the language translation.

At the direction of the author, in cases where the first and second methods of translating phraseological units are inapplicable, it is considered acceptable to replace them with expressions with a figurative meaning available in the target language. This method takes a huge place in the translation process. Each expression or phrase used with a figurative meaning is considered a valid Phraseologism for the translator. The proverbs, sayings and idioms that are part of the phraseological units, created and improved by the people for centuries, became a rich heritage for the younger generation. Proverbs, being one of the genre of oral folk art with a short form, but deep content, were created on the basis of centuries-old life observations of the people, socio-economic, political and cultural experience. Proverbs, according to their social ideological tasks, become the

exponent of the worldviews of the broad popular masses, and in some cases of a certain social stratum or group. For this reason, the thematic volume of proverbs is very extensive, and it will be impossible to limit this volume within the we the in significant reality of life, and in connection with this, there is not a single area if social life that would not find its vivid reflection in proverbs. For example: In Russian! Bad news fly in wings. Five fingers, but all different measure seven times, cut once. To make mountains out of molehills. In the Uzbek language: Yomon so'zning qanoti bor. Besh qo'l barobar emas. Yetti o'lchab, bir kes. Pashshadan fil yasamoq. Proverbs are a huge treasure of our speech for expressing our thoughts clearly, clearly and figuratively, and their application with art makes the work of the writer, the orator's speech meaningful and attractive, contributes to becoming more impressionable for the figurative expression of their thoughts. Comparative study of proverbs and the process of their translation are of scientific and practical importance. It is also worth mentioning the presence of literal, explanatory or descriptive methods when translating phraseological units. For example: in Russian: The one who laughs well. In the Uzbek language: Oxirgi kulgan, yaxshi kuladi. The study of the corresponding equivalents to words and expressions, the use of expressions equivalent in meaning to those disclosed in the work, expanding the limits of the figurativeness of the translation, contribute to a more expressive reading of it. The transition of phraseological units with full preservation of the meaning of words in their structure, being considered one of the most common methods of translation,

contributes to the entry of new phraseological units into the translation language of the work and the enrichment of the phraseological composition of the same language. This position can be clearly seen in the following examples: For example: in Russian: There is healthy mind in a healthy body. In the Uzbek language: Sog'liq-tuman boylik. Proverbs and sayings, having a short form and deep content, are considered a very important means of expressing a clear, clear and imaginative thought. Let's turn our attention to examples. In Russian: The fish goes out from the head. In the Uzbek language: Baliq boshidan sasiydi. We can clearly trace the identity of the component word that make up this proverb in the compared languages. In Russian: What goes around comes around. In the Uzbek language: Nima eksang shuni o'rasan. It becomes clear to us from the above examples that the full equivalent of this proverb exists in the Russian and Uzbek Languages. Many scholars claim the existense of similar proverbs, sayings and in many languages. Experienced in everyday life, having a

good, complete general meaning, having a short voiced form, considered folk wisdom, proverbs are used to liven up speech and in order to make it attractive, imaginative and more meaningful. The process of translating the phraseological units of the originals using the equivalents contained in the target language is considered one of the most common methods of translation. In this method, despite the fact that the form changes, the expression that is closest in semantics is selected. For example: In Russian: To be afraid of wolves - do not go to the forest. In the Uzbek language: Chumchuqdan qo'rqqan - tariq ekmaydi. As a result of the research carried out, it would be advisable to affirm that phraseological units, being diverse in ideological content, spiritual and moral outcome, have characteristic features in their stylistic function. Due to the similarity of the law of thinking in all nations and the existense of beliefs and representations that are close to each other, even in languages differing in structure, the same or similar proverbs can be created and conversations.

References:

1. K. Musaev.. Theoretical basis of translation analysis. History and theory of translation. Collection. Tashkent 1992
2. N. M. Shansky. On phraseological unit as a linguistic unit and the subject of phraseology Moscow 1985.
3. Ya. I. Retsker. Translation theory and translation practice. Moscow 1974.

“MALIK AL-ULAMO” DEYA TA'RIFLANGAN AJDODIMIZ HAQIDA

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Namangan, fiqh, tasavvuf,
“Sultonul ulamo”
(Ulamolar sultoni),
“Alouddin” (“Dinni
ulug'lovchi”), Sayxun
(Sirdaryo), husnixat,
Maqomi Ibrohim Halil,
Shayx Alouddin Mansur.

ANNOTATSIYA

Ushbu maqolada biz tanishimiz, faxirlanishimizga loyiq ajdodlarimizdan biri, o'z davrida “Malik al-ulamo” deya tariflangan ulug' vatandoshimiz Abu Bakr Kosoniyning samarali, keng miqiyosli, asrlar davomida saqlanib kelgan ijodi xaqida qisqa ma'lumotlar berilgan.

Mamlakatimizda xalqimizning ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy, tarixiy, madaniy va ilmiy hayotini chuqur o'rganish va keng targ'ib qilish uchun qulay shart-sharoitlar yaratilib berilmoqda. Avvallari o'rganish imkoniyati bo'lmagan, yozgan asarlari tadqiq etilmagan allomalar hayoti va ijodi o'rganila boshlandi. Ana shunday o'zidan qimmatli ilmiy meros qoldirgan, tarix zarqavaqlarida iz qoldirib ketgan o'tmish allomalarimizdan biri Abu Bakr ibn Mas'ud al-Kosoniydir.

O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Shavkat Mirziyoyev 2018-yilning 2 – 3-may kunlari Namangan viloyatiga tashrifi chog'ida ma'naviy-ma'rifiy islohotlarni yanada kengaytirish,

ayniqsa, buyuk ajdodlarimizning ilmiy, adabiy merosini chuqur o'rganish masalasiga alohida e'tibor qaratdilar. Jumladan, Namangan zaminidan yetishib chiqqan, diniy va dunyoviy bilimlarda yuksak maqomga erishgan Alouddin Kosoniy chuqur ehtirom bilan tilga oldilar.

Abu Bakr Kosoniy XIII asrda yashab ijod qilgan taniqli olim va shoirdir. Ma'rifatparvar olimning to'liq ismi Alouddin Abu Bakr ibn Mas'ud ibn Ahmad Kosoniy. U fiqh ilmiga, tasavvufga oid asarlar yozgan, she'riy ijod bilan shug'ullangan. Alouddin Kosoniyning tavallud sanasi haqida aniq ma'lumot yo'q. Uning vafoti 1191-yilga to'g'ri kelishi

tadqiqotchi olimlar tomonidan aniqlangan [1].

Alouddin Abu Bakr ibn Mas`ud ibn Ahmad Kosoniy “Malik al-ulamo”, “Sultonul ulamo” (Ulamolar sultoni), va “Alouddin” (“Dinni ulug’lovchi”) kabi unvonlar bilan shuhrat topgan [2].

Allomaga Kosoniy deya nisbat berilishi Movarounnahrning Shosh viloyati orqasida, Sayxun (Sirdaryo)ning shimoliy qismida joylashgan shahar – Koson bilan bog’liqdir. Koson shahri – hozirgi kunda Namangan viloyatining shimoliy-sharqida joylashgan bo’lib, Kosonsoy shahri deb nomlanadi.

Abu Bakr Kosoniy o`z yurtida ilmni va ulamolar majlislarini sevib ulg’aydi. Balog’at yoshiga yetgach Buxoro shahriga kelib u yerda Alouddin Muhammad ibn Abu Ahmad Samarqandiyning (vaf. 1145-y.) qo’lida tahsil oldi. Ustozining buyuk asarlari “Tuxfat ul-Fuqaho”, “Sharh Ta`vilot fi tafsir al-Qur`oni al-a`zim” kabi asarlarini yod oldi, yana boshqa ko’plab usul va furu ilmiga oid asarlarni ustozlaridan o’rgandi va sohaning yetuk olimlaridan biriga aylandi.

Abu Bakr Kosoniy ustozining “Tuxfat ul-Fuqaho” nomli asarini sharhlab, Xoji Xalifa aytganidek, buyuk asari “Badoi`us-Sanoi` fii tartibish-Sharoi`” (“Shariat qonunlarini tartiblashda go`zal san`atlar”) asarini yozib, ustoziga taqdim qildi [3]. Kitobni ham uslub, ham mazmun jihatdan yuksak saviyada yozilganini ko`rib Alouddin Samarqandiy benihoyat xursand bo`ldi va qizi Fotima Samarqandiyani unga nikohlab berdi va mahriga ushbu kitob qo`yildi.

Ikki ilmi tolibdan hosil bo’lgan oila timsolida o’ziga xos maktab vujudga keldi. Chunki, bu vaqtda Alouddin Kosoniy ham,

uning fiqh, husnixat, hadis ilmida yetuk bo’lgan rafiqasi Fotima ham Alouddin Samarqandiy darajasida fatvo berish maqomiga yetgan edi. Ular ilm istab Turkiya va Shom mamlakatlarida bo’lishadi.

Abu Bakr Kosoniy dastlab Buxoroda, keyinchalik, Shom o’lkalarida zamonasining buyuk muhaddislaridan dars olgan, ulardan hadis eshitgan hamda Shom diyorlarida qirq yildan ziyod hadis ilmidan ta`lim bergani manbalarda aytib o`tilgan [4].

Abu Bakr Kosoniy Halabda yashagan davrda hokimiyat avvaliga Zangilar, keyinchalik Ayyubiylar boshqaruvida bo’lgan. Halabda juda ham yahshi kutib olingan Kosoniy qisqa muddat ichida katta shuhrat qozonib, faqihlarning taklifiga binoan mashhur “Halaviyya” madrasasiga Nuriddin Zangi tomonidan “Xo`ja Mudarris” etib ta`yinlanadi. Ushbu vazifa odatda mamlakatning eng katta ulamosiga topshirilardi.

Abu Bakr Kosoniy umrining oxirigacha, qirq yildan ziyod o`lka (hozirgi Suriya, Falastin, Iordaniya, Iroq hududlarini o`z ichiga olgan Zangiylar davlati)ning “Raisu-l-ulamo”si sifatida keng doirada faoliyat olib borgan, qo`l ostida son-sanoqsiz talabalar tahsil olib, oralaridan yetuk ulamolar yetishib chiqdi. Allomaning shogirdlari: Abu Bakr Kosoniy yirik Zangiylar mamlakatining “Raisu-l- ulamo”si va “Halaviyya” madrasasi “Xo`ja mudarris”i sifatida jo`shqin va keng doirada faoliyat olib bordi. Qo`l ostida Movrounnahr, Xuroson, Shom, Onado`li, Misr, Hijoz va boshqa musulmon o`lkalardan kelgan son-sanoqsiz talabalar tahsil olishdi. Shogirdlari orasidan “Halaviya”, “Juodekiyya”, “Shibliyya” va

boshqa madrasalarda “Xo`ja mudarris”lar, katta-katta qozilar, muftiyar yetishib chiqdi. Tarixchilar ushbu shogirdlarning tarjimai holini zikr qilganda “Imom Kosoniy qo`lida ta`lim olgan” deya alohida e`tirof etib, ularning ilmiy saviyalariga ishora qiladilar.

Alouddin Abu Bakr Kosoniy yuksak bilim, hikmat-zakovat va g`ayrat- shijoat bilan uzoq yillar Halabda olib borgan faoliyatlari natijasida o`lkadagi aqidaviy, fiqhiy ixtiloflarga barham berildi, mazhablar orasidagi bir-biriga bo`lgan birdamlik, hurmat oshdi, Hanafiylarning qaddi tiklandi va ilm-ma`rifat va barqarorlik ta`minlandi.

Abu Bakr Kosoniyning qoldirgan asarlari ko`p bo`lmasa-da, ilmiy saviyasini yuqori bo`lganini ko`rsatib, bera oladi. Olimning bizgacha islom fiqhiga oid yagona asari “Badoi`u-s-sanoi` fi tartibi-sh-sharoi`” (“Shariat qonunlarini tartiblashda go`zal qonunlar”) yetib kelgan.

Abdulahy Laknaviy (vafoti 1886-y.) esa Abu Bakr Kosoniyning bizgacha yetib kelmagan yana bir “Kitob ul-Jalil” nomli asari haqida aytib o`tgan.

Olingan tarixiy ma`lumotlarga ko`ra, alloma Abu Bakr Kosoniy xotirasi, irodasi va qobiliyati kuchli inson bo`lgan chunki, ustoz Alouddin Samarqandiyning “Tuxfatul-fuqaho” nomli asarini yaxshi o`zlashtirgan, ustoz bilan birga amaliyotgan tadbiiq etgan. Shuningdek, “Tuxfatul-fuqaho” asarini kuchli sharhlagan, o`ziga xos dunyo tarixida saqlangan va jamiyat uchun amalda bo`lgan “Badoi`u-s-sanoi` fi tartibi-sh-sharoi`” (Shariat qonunlarini tartiblashda go`zal qonunlar) asarini yozgan.

O`zbekiston musulmonlari idorasining fundamental kutubxonasida

saqlanayotgan 7 juz`dan iborat (5 ta kitob hoida nashr etilgan) Abu Bakr Kosoniyning “Badoi`” asarida allomaning favqulodda iste`dod va mahorati mujassam bo`lgan. Shayx Muhammad Sodiq Muhammad Yusuf hazratlari bu kitobga shunday ta`rif bergan edilar: “Bu – ulkan kitob. Undan hamma faqihlar foydalanib kelgan va bundan keyin ham foydalanadi, inshoolloh” [5].

Abu Bakr Kosoniyning islom fiqhiga oid “Badoe` us-sanoe` fiy tartib ash-sharoe`” (“Shariat qonunlarini tartiblashda go`zal san`atlar”) [6] asari qariyb o`n asrdan buyon musulmon mamlakatlarida nufuzli va mukammal huquqiy manba sifatida e`tirof etilib, hozirga qadar islom huquqi bo`yicha darslik sifatida o`qitiladi.

“Badoe` us-sanoe`” Abu Bakr Kosoniyning ustoz, Movarounnahr fiqh maktabining yirik vakili, O`rta Osiyoda hanafiylarning buyuk imomlaridan biri, aqida, tafsir, fiqh, kalom ilmi sohibi Alouddin Muhammad ibn Ahmad Samarqandiy (vaf. 1145-y.)ning *fiqhiy masalalar jamlangan* “Tuhfat ul-fuqaho” (Faqihlar uchun tuhfa) kitobiga yozgan sharhi bo`lib, unda ibodat va muomalot masalalari san`at darajasida tartib-intizom bilan ta`lif etilgan. “Badoe` us-sanoe`” hanafiya mazhabiga oid asarlar ichida eng mufassal, mukammal va boshqa mazhab egalari ham tan oladigan, dalil-hujjati mustahkam manbadir [7].

Asarning tarixiy xizmati shundaki, sal kam ming yil muqaddam o`tgan hamyurtimiz Alouddin Kosoniyning o`z davridagi aqidaviy, fiqhiy ixtiloflarga barham berish, hanafiylarning mavqei tiklanib, ilm-ma`rifat va barqarorlik ta`minlash, mo``tazila va bid`atchi toifalar yo`q qilish borasidagi sa`y-harakatlari

natijasida mazhablar orasidagi birdamlik, hurmat-e'tibor oshishidadir.

Fiqh ilmi qomusi bo'lgan "Badoe' us-sano'e'" Shayx Alouddin Mansur tomonidan o'zbek tiliga o'girilib, 2018- yilda "Sharq" nashriyotida chop etildi. "Badoi"ni tarjima qilgan Shayx Alouddin Mansur "O'rganayotganimiz "Badoi' us- Sanoi'" – boshqa fiqhiy kitoblardan farqli ravishda mukammal va mufassal asardir. Unda har bir masalaning dalili izchil tekshiriladi, ixtilofli masalalarning sabablari izlanib, ular to'la va atroflicha o'rganiladi", – deb yozgan edi [8].

AbuBakr Kosoniy 587-hijriy rajab oyining 10-kuni (1191-yil 3-avgust)da Halab shahrida vafot etganlar. Mashur faqih shaharning tashqarisidagi Maqomi Ibrohim Halil degan joyga (turmish o'rtog'i Fotimaning yoniga) dafn qilindi. Bu zotning

qabri ziyoratgoh holatiga keltirilgan va bu yerda qilingan duolar ijobat bo'lishiga odamlar astoydil ishonishadi.

O'z hayotini dinu diyonat pokligi, iymon-e'tiqod ustuvorligi, ilm va adolat ro'yobi yo'liga bag'ishlagan mo'tabar alloma, o'z davri afkor ommasi tomonidan "Malik ul-ulamo" degan yuksak e'tirofiga sazovor bo'lgan Abu Bakr Kosoniy nafaqat o'zbek xalqi, balki butun musulmon olamining faxr-iftixoridirki, buyuk vatandoshimiz dunyoga kelgan bu muborak zamindan yana kosoniylar yetishib chiqishiga men ishonaman, chunki bu diyor yer yuziga qanchadan-qancha faylasuflarni yetishtirib bergani barchaga ma'lum. Kelajakda ham yaratib berilayotgan sharoitlar ortidan albatta yetishib chiqishi shubhasizdir.

References:

1. Хомиджон Хомидий., Аширов А., Умаралиев М. Косонсой тарихи. – Т.: EXTREMUM PRESS, 2010. – Б. 85.
2. http://uzbekistonovozi.uz/uz/articles/index.php?ELEMENT_ID=58565
3. Ноёб фикҳий асар // Ҳидоят. – 2011. – №. 12. – Б. 26.
4. http://uzbekistonovozi.uz/uz/articles/index.php?ELEMENT_ID=58565
5. <http://uza.uz/uz/society/alouddin-kosoniy-kim-bo-lgan-06-07-2018>
6. Алоуддин Косоний. Бадоеъ ус-саноеъ фий тартиб иш-шароеъ (Шариат қонунларини тартиблашда гўзал санъатлар). 1-китоб. Таҳорат. Арабчадан таржима ва шарҳ муаллифи Шайх Алоуддин Мансур. – Т.: Шарқ, 2018. – Б. 3.
7. Шайх Алоуддин Мансур. Қомусий асар / Алоуддин Косоний. Бадоеъ ус-саноеъ фий тартиб иш-шароеъ (Шариат қонунларини тартиблашда гўзал санъатлар). 1-китоб. Таҳорат. Арабчадан таржима ва шарҳ муаллифи Шайх Алоуддин Мансур. – Т.: Шарқ, 2018. – Б. 4.
8. Алоуддин Мансур. Бадоеус саноеъ фи тартибиш шароеъ (Шариат қонунини тартиблашда гўзал санъатлар) // Ҳидоят. – 2012. – №. 3. – Б. 19.

СУД ХУЖЖАТИНИ ИЖРО ЭТМАСЛИК ЖИНОЯТИНИ РИВОЖЛАНИШИ ҲАМДА ТАКОМИЛЛАШТИРИШ МУАОММОЛАРИ

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МАҚОЛА ТАРИХИ

Qabul qilindi: 01 September

Ma'qullandi: 10 September

Chop etildi: 14 September

KALIT SO'ZLAR

Суд, ҳужжатлар, қарор,
ижро этмаслик, жиноят,
жазо, жавобгарлик,
таъминлаш, ҳуқуқ, қонун

ANNOTATSIYA

Мазкур мақолада суд ҳужжатини ижро этмаслик жиноятини ривожланиши ҳамда такомиллаштириш муаоммоларига доир масалалар баён этилган. Шунингдек, мақолада суд ҳужжатини ижро этмаслик жиноятини ривожланиши ҳамда такомиллаштириш юзасидан тавсиялар берилган.

Демократик ҳуқуқий давлат ва фуқаролик жамиятни шакллантиришда суд-ҳуқуқ соҳасида олиб борилаётган ислохотлар ҳам муҳим аҳамиятга эга. Чунки, мустақил суд ҳокимиятини шакллантирмасдан туриб, юқоридаги мақсадга эришиб бўлмайди.

Президентимиз Шавкат Мирзиёев Ўзбекистон Республикаси Конституцияси қабул қилинганининг 27 йиллигига бағишланган тантанали маросимдаги маърузасида ҳар қандай демократик ислохотлар самараси, тинчлик ва тараққиётнинг асосий гарови Конституция ва қонун устуворлиги таъминланиши билан бевосита боғлиқлигини, шунингдек, инсон ҳуқуқ ва эркинликларига амал қилинишини таъминлаш, ҳар бир шахснинг кадр-қимматини эъзозлаш биз барпо этаётган очиқ, эркин ва

адолатли жамиятнинг ажралмас хусусияти эканлигини таъкидлади.

Сўнги йилларда, мамлакатимизда фуқароларнинг ҳуқуқ ва эркинликларини, энг аввало, жиноий тажовузлардан ҳимоя қилишнинг ишончли кафолатларини таъминлашга, шунингдек, уларнинг шаъни ва кадр-қиммати камситилишига, қонуний манфаатлари чекланишига йўл қўймасликка қаратилган кенг кўламли ишлар амалга оширилмоқда.

Олиб борилаётган суд-ҳуқуқ ислохотларининг асосига қонун устуворлиги, фуқароларнинг қонун олдида тенглиги, инсонпарварлик, адолатлилик ва айбсизлик презумпцияси каби конституциявий принциплар пойдевор қилиб қўйилган.

2017–2021 йилларда Ўзбекистон Республикасини ривожлантиришнинг

бешта устувор йўналиши бўйича Ҳаракатлар стратегиясининг ижроси юзасидан суд ҳокимиятининг чинакам мустақиллиги ва эркинлигини таъминлаш, одил судловнинг сифати ва шаффофлигини ошириш, «Хабеас корпус» институтини қўллашни кенгайтиришга қаратилган қатор норматив-ҳуқуқий ҳужжатлар қабул қилинди.

Судларнинг прокуратурадан мустақил, эркин фаолият олиб боришини таъминлаш борасида қўйилган дастлабки қадамлар ўз натижасини бераётганини ўтган беш йил вақт мобайнида оқланган шахслар мисолида ҳам кўриш мумкин.

Давлатимиз раҳбари бугунги кунга қадар амалга оширилган ислохотлар ва уларнинг дастлабки натижаларига маҳлиё бўлиб қолмасдан, жамиятда инсон ҳуқуқ ва эркинликларини ҳурмат қилиш маданиятини шакллантириш, шу орқали мамлакатимизнинг халқаро нуфузини янада юксалтиришимиз зарурлигини таъкидлади. Бунинг учун ҳуқуқни муҳофаза қилувчи органларни фақат ва фақат халқ манфаати йўлида оғишмай хизмат қиладиган идораларга айлантиришимиз лозимлигини айтди.

Судларнинг чинакам мустақиллигини таъминлаш биз учун энг устувор вазифа эканлиги, айниқса, суд бирон-бир мансабдор шахсининг қўли етадиган идорага айланиб қолишига мутлақо йўл қўймаслик шартлиги, шу сабабли суд ишларига аралашгани ёки судга босим ўтказгани учун жавобгарликни кучайтириш лозимлиги қайд этилди.

Бундан ташқари, қабул қилинган суд қарорлари ижросини таъминлаш чоралари ҳалигача аниқ амалий натижа бераёпти деб бўлмайди, бу қарорларнинг аксарияти ойлаб, ҳатто йиллаб бажарилмасдан қолмоқда. Одил судлов вазифаларининг муваффақиятли амалга оширилиши нафақат мазкур органлар томонидан ҳуқуқ нормаларига тўлиқ риоя этилишига, балки улар томонидан чиқарилган ҳукм, ҳал қилув қарори, ажрими ёки қарорининг бажарилишига ҳам боғлиқдир. Мамлакатимизда суд ҳужжатлари ижросини таъминлашнинг ҳуқуқий асослари яратилган ҳамда у такомиллаштирилиб борилмоқда.

Жумладан, Ўзбекистон Республикаси Конституциясининг 114-моддасида суд ҳокимияти чиқарган ҳужжатлар барча давлат органлари, жамоат бирлашмалари, корхоналар, муассасалар, ташкилотлар, мансабдор шахслар ва фуқаролар учун мажбурийлиги белгиланган. Шунингдек, Ўзбекистон Республикасининг “Судлар тўғрисида”ги қонуни, Маъмурий жавобгарлик тўғрисидаги кодекси, Жиноят кодекси, Жиноят-ижроия кодекси, Суд ҳужжатлари ва бошқа органлар ҳужжатларини ижро этиш тўғрисида қонун, Ўзбекистон Республикаси Президентининг “Ўзбекистон Республикаси Адлия вазирлиги ҳузуридаги Суд қарорларини ижро этиш, судлар фаолиятини моддий-техника жиҳатидан ва молиявий таъминлаш департаменти фаолиятини янада такомиллаштириш чоратадбирлари тўғрисида” ги 2006 йил 31 августдаги ПҚ-458-сонли қарори,

Ўзбекистон Республикаси Президентининг “Ўзбекистон Республикаси адлия вазирлиги ҳузуридаги суд департаментининг суд қарорларини ижро этиш, моддий-техника жиҳатидан ва молиявий таъминлаш тизимини янада такомиллаштириш чора-тадбирлари тўғрисида” ги 2007 йил 1 ноябрдаги ПҚ-722-сон қарорларида суд ҳужжатлари ижросини таъминлашга оид ҳуқуқий воситалар ишлаб чиқилган.

Суд ҳужжатлари ижросини таъминлашда уларни бажармаганлик учун жавобгарлик чораларининг белгиланиши ушбу қилмишлар содир этилишининг олдини олишда муҳим аҳамиятга эга.

Суд ҳужжатларини бажармаслик ижтимоий хавfli қилмиш сифатида Жиноят Кодексида мустаҳкамланганлиги унинг жамият, аниқроғи, ҳокимиятлар тақсимланишининг мустақил бўғини, давлат ҳокимиятининг алоҳида тармоғи, фуқаролар ҳимоячиси бўлмиш – одил судлов институти манфаатларига жиддий зарар етказиши мумкинлиги билан изоҳланади.

Ўзбекистон Республикаси Жиноят кодексининг XVI боби “Одил судловга қарши жиноятлар”, деб номланиб, жиноят ҳуқуқи назариясида ушбу жиноятлар одил судлов органларининг нормал фаолиятига тажовуз этувчи жиноятлар сифатида белгиланган.

Ўзбекистон Республикаси Конституциясига мувофиқ, одил судлов

фақат судлар томонидан амалга оширилади. Юридик адабиётларда одил судловга қарши жиноятлар дейилганда,

шунингдек, бошқа фуқаролар томонидан суриштирув, дастлабки тергов, суд иш юритуви ва жазони ижро этишни тартибга солувчи қонунларни бузиш йўли билан одил судлов ва шахс манфаатларига зарар етказадиган, ҳамда шу билан суднинг жиноят ёки фуқаролик ишлари бўйича одил судловни амалга ошириш вазифаларига тўсқинлик қилувчи қасддан содир этиладиган ҳаракатлар тушунилади¹, деб таъриф берилади.

Бизнинг фикримизча, одил судловга қарши жиноятлар суриштирувчи, терговчи, прокурор, судья, шунингдек, жиноят процессининг бошқа иштирокчилари, шунингдек, мансабдор шахслар ва фуқаролар томонидан суриштирув, дастлабки тергов ҳамда суд иш юритуви тартибига оид қонунларни бузиш йўли билан одил судлов ва шахс манфаатларига зарар етказадиган, шу билан суднинг жиноят, фуқаролик ёки хўжалик ишлари бўйича одил судловни амалга ошириш вазифаларига тўсқинлик қилувчи қасддан содир этиладиган ижтимоий хавfli қилмишлар йиғиндиси.

Ўзбекистон Республикаси Жиноят кодекси 232-моддасида суд қарорларини бажармаганлик учун жиноий жавобгарлик белгиланган эди.

Мамлакатимизда изчиллик билан олиб борилаётган суд-ҳуқуқ ислохотлари натижасида Ўзбекистон Республикаси Олий Мажлиси Қонунчилик палатаси томонидан 2008 йил 19 ноябрда қабул қилинган, Сенат

1997. – С.40.

томонидан 2008 йил 4 декабрда маъқулланган “Ижро иши юритиш такомиллаштирилиши муносабати билан Ўзбекистон Республикасининг айрим қонун ҳужжатларига ўзгартиш ва қўшимчалар киритиш тўғрисида қонун”га мувофиқ суд қарорларини бажармаганлик учун жиноий жавобгарлик белгиланган Ўзбекистон Республикаси ЖК 232-моддаси янги таҳрирда баён қилинди.

Юқорида кўрсатиб ўтилган қонун асосида Жиноят Кодексга киритилган ўзгартиш ва қўшимчалар ушбу жиноят субъектлари доирасини кенгайтди, эндиликда суд ҳужжатининг бажарилмаганлиги учун нафақат мансабдор шахслар, балки оддий фуқаролар ҳам жавобгар бўлиши белгиланди.

Суд ҳужжатини ижро этмаганлик учун жиноий жавобгарликнинг такомиллаштирилиши ва бу соҳада давом эттирилаётган ислохотлар ушбу диссертация тадқиқоти учун танланган мавзунинг долзарблигидан далолат беради. Мазкур тадқиқот ишининг мазмунини ҳуқуқ тартиботнинг ҳолатига салбий таъсир кўрсатувчи, шунингдек, суднинг обрўсига путур етказётган суд ҳужжатини ижро этмаганлик учун жиноий жавобгарлик ва қарши кураш муаммолари ташкил этади.

Юқорида келтирилганлар нафақат мавзунини танлаш учун асос

бўлди, балки тадқиқотнинг тавсиф ва йўналишини ҳам белгилаб берди.

Таъкидлаганимиздек, суд ҳужжатини ижро этмаганлик учун жиноий жавобгарликни тадқиқ қилиш

адабиётларимизда етарлича эътибор берилмаган. Ғ.Абдумажидов, Ю.Каракетов, М.Усмоналиев, Қ.Абдурасулова, Ю.Рахимовнинг асарларида бу муаммонинг айрим жиҳатлари тадқиқ қилинган, холос.

З.Ҳ.Ғуломов томонидан одил судловга қарши жиноятлар масаласи докторлик диссертацияси даражасида тадқиқ қилинган бўлиб, унда одил судловга қарши бошқа жиноятлар қаторида суд қарорларини бажармаганлик учун жавобгарлик масаласи ҳам тадқиқ қилинган². Ушбу тадқиқот мазкур илмий ишни тадқиқ қилишда муҳим аҳамиятга эга эканлигини таъкидлаган ҳолда, биринчидан, ушбу тадқиқот бевосита суд ҳужжатини ижро этмаганлик учун жавобгарлик масаласига бағишланмаганлигини, иккинчидан, у Жиноят Кодексининг 232-моддасининг эски таҳрири асосида тадқиқ қилинганлигини эътироф этиш жоиз.

Бундан ташқари, 2022 йил 29 январь куни Ўзбекистон Республикаси Президентининг “Давлат органлари билан муносабатларда фуқаролар ва тадбиркорлик субъектлари ҳуқуқларининг самарали ҳимоя этилишини таъминлаш ҳамда аҳолининг судларга бўлган ишончини янада ошириш чора-тадбирлари

2010. №3. С.85-87.

тўғрисида”³ги ПҚ-107-сон Қарори билан қабул қилинган. Қарорга кўра, давлат органлари билан муносабатларда фуқаролар ва тадбиркорлик субъектлари ҳуқуқлари ва қонуний манфаатларининг самарали ҳимоя этилишини таъминлаш ҳамда маъмурий суд ишларини юритишни халқаро стандартлардан келиб чиққан ҳолда такомиллаштириш мақсадида бир қатор чора-тадбирлар белгилаб берилган бўлиб, ушбу чора тадбирларни мавзуга алоқадор қисми бўйича маъмурий судларнинг оммавий-ҳуқуқий муносабатлардан келиб чиқадиган ишлар бўйича ҳал қилув қарорлари давлат органлари ёки ташкилотлари томонидан ижро қилинмаган тақдирда, уларнинг мансабдор шахсларига нисбатан суд жарималарини қўллаш масаласи ҳам кўрсатиб ўтилган.

Ушбу Қарор билан жамиятда маъмурий судларнинг ролини кучайтириш, уларни фуқаролар ва тадбиркорлик субъектларининг ҳақиқий ҳимоячисига айлантириш мақсадида мазкур қарорнинг 2- бандига асосан процессуал қонун ҳужжатларида белгиланаётган тартиблар доирасида давлат органлари ёки ташкилотлари оммавий-ҳуқуқий муносабатлардан келиб чиқадиган иш бўйича ҳал қилув қарорини у қонуний кучга кирган кундан бошлаб бир ой

давомида ижро қилиш ҳамда бу ҳақда маъмурий судга хабар бериш, давлат органлари ёки ташкилотлари томонидан оммавий-ҳуқуқий муносабатлардан келиб чиқадиган иш бўйича суд ҳужжати ижро қилинмаганлиги учун давлат органлари ёки ташкилотларининг мансабдор шахсларига нисбатан суд жаримасини қўллаш ҳамда давлат органлари ёки ташкилотлари томонидан оммавий-ҳуқуқий муносабатлардан келиб чиқадиган иш бўйича ҳал қилув қарорининг такроран ижро қилинмаганлиги учун давлат органлари ёки ташкилотларининг мансабдор шахсларига нисбатан дастлаб қўлланилган суд жаримасини оширилган миқдорда қўллаш назарда тутилган.

Шунингдек, Олий суд ва Судьялар олий кенгашининг маъмурий суднинг қонуний кучга кирган ҳал қилув қароридан аниқланган ҳолатлар бошқа ишни кўраётган фуқаролик ишлари бўйича суд учун мажбурий ҳисобланишини белгилашни назарда тутувчи таклифлари маъқулланган.

Ушбу қарор талабларидан келиб чиқадиган бўлсак, ҳозирда амалда бўлган Жиноят кодексининг 232-моддасига тўла мос келмайди, шу сабабли ушбу модда бўйича қонунчиликни такомиллаштириб, таклиф киритиш учун тадқиқ қилиш лозим бўлади.

Хулоса қиладиган бўлсак, мазкур мавзунинг мақсади, эмпирик материалларни ва статистик маълумотларни ўрганиш, суд ҳукмларини, суд қарорлари ва бошқа суд ҳужжатларини бажармаслик

³ Ўзбекистон Республикаси Президентининг “Давлат органлари билан муносабатларда фуқаролар ва тадбиркорлик субъектлари ҳуқуқларининг самарали ҳимоя этилишини таъминлаш ҳамда аҳолининг судларга бўлган ишончини янада ошириш чора-тадбирлари тўғрисида”ги ПҚ-107-сон Қарори. <https://lex.uz/docs/5841287>

ЖАМОАТ ХАВФСИЗЛИГИНИ ТАЪМИНЛАШНИНГ ҲУҚУҚИЙ АСОСЛАРИНИ ТАКОМИЛЛАШТИРИШ

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KALIT SO'ZLAR

оммавий тартибсизлик,
жамоат хавфсизлиги,
жамоат тартиби,
маъмурий-ҳуқуқий
тартибга солиш,
жиноят, маъмурий
жавобгарлик, превентив
чоралар

ANNOTATSIYA

Ушбу мақолада оммавий тартибсизликларнинг жамоат тартиби ва хавфсизлигига таҳдиди, унинг моҳияти назарий таҳлил қилиниб, мазмунини очиб беришга ҳаракат қилинди. Ўтказилган таҳлиллار асосида маълум даражада ҳуқуқни қўллаш амалиётини мураккаблаштириши мумкин бўлган "оммавий тартибсизлик" тушунчасини тушунишга ягона ёндашув мавжуд эмаслиги аниқланди. Шунингдек, оммавий тартибсизликларнинг олдини олишга қаратилган чора-тадбирлар, чет давларнинг қонунчилиги, хусусан жиноят кодекслари таҳлил қилинди.

мақсадли ҳамкорлиги йўлга қўйилди.

Мамлакатимизда амалга оширилаётган кенг қўламли ислохотлар доирасида аҳолининг тинч ва осойишта ҳаётини таъминлаш ҳамда жамиятимизда қонунга итоаткорлик ва жамоат хавфсизлиги маданиятини шакллантириш, жамоат хавфсизлигига таҳдидларнинг олдини олишга алоҳида эътибор қаратилмоқда. Жумладан, жамоат хавфсизлигини таъминлаш йўналишидаги ишларни «Халқ манфаатларига хизмат қилиш» тамойили асосида ташкил этишнинг мутлақо янги механизм ва тартиблари жорий этилиб, давлат органларининг жамоатчилик тузилмалари билан ўзаро

Бу албатта бежиз эмас,
ҳозирги кунда жаҳонда кучайиб
бораётган турли хавф-хатар ва
зиддиятлар, эл-юрт
тинчлиги ва
осойишталигига
тахдидлар, пандемия, табиий ва
техноген офатлар, терроризмнинг
ҳар хил кўринишлари масъул
давлат тузилмаларига ўз
фаолиятини **«Барча саъй-
ҳаракатлар инсон қадри учун»**
деган устувор ғоя асосида янада
такомиллаштириш вазифасини
юклаб, Президентимизнинг 2021
йил 27
ноябрь кунги “Ўзбекистон
Республикаси жамоат
хавфсизлиги концепциясини
тасдиқлаш ва уни амалга ошириш
чора-тадбирлари
тўғрисида”
27-сон
Фармонида [1] ўз ифодасини
топди.

Ҳаммамизга маълумки кейинги йилларда бир қатор давлатларда, содир бўлган оммавий намоишлар ва ундан келиб чиқаётган оммавий тартибсизликлар кучайиб, тинч намоиш ва митинглар ҳар хил террористик-қўпоровчилик ҳаракатларига айланиб кетиши ҳолатлари тез-тез кузатилмоқда. Юзага келаётган вазиятларнинг чуқур таҳлили шуни кўрсатмоқдаки, олдиндан режалаштирилган, оммавий тартибсизликлар аҳоли осойишталигини бузиб, фавқулодда ҳолатларни юзага келтириб, тўғридан-тўғри давлатларнинг конституцион тузумга таҳдид солмоқда.

Бунда асосан кундалик ҳаётда тез-тез учраб турадиган, деярли дунёнинг барча давлатларида кузатиш мумкин бўлган ижтимоий муаммоларни сунъий равишда ҳақиқатдан йироқ бўлган маълумотлар билан оммавий ахборот воситалари ва жаҳон интернет тармоғи орқали бўрттириб кўрсатиб, ҳар хил ахборот хуружларини яратиб, ижтимоий низоларни вужудга келтириш орқали аҳолини норозилигини уйғотишга ҳаракат қилинмоқда. Натижада ҳаёт маромини таъминловчи объектларга, давлат идора ва ташкилотларининг маъмурий биноларига, фуқароларнинг ҳуқуқ ва манфаатларига жиддий зарар етказилмоқда, айниқса оммавий тартибсизликлар вақтида ҳуқуқни муҳофаза қилувчи орган ходимларига нисбатан бўлаётган зўравонликлар, уларнинг ўз вазифаларини бажариш чоғида ҳалок бўлиш ҳолатлар ва бундай вазиятлардан келиб чиқадиган, бошқа салбий ҳолатлар ижтимоий-иқтисодий

тизимни издан чиқариб давлат органларининг бир меъёрида ишлашини издан чиқармоқда.

Глобал рақобатнинг кучайиши ва инқироз потенциалининг тўпланиши суверен давлатларга сиёсий босим ўтказиш, уларнинг ички ишларига аралаштириш, у ердаги вазиятни беқарорлаштириш, жамоатчилик фикри ва онгини манипуляция қилиш мақсадида “юмшоқ куч” ва инсон ҳуқуқлари тушунчаларидан баъзан бузғунчи ва ноқонуний фойдаланиш хавфини келтириб чиқармоқда. [2]

Бундай ҳолатларнинг олдини олиш, уларга қарши курашиш, фуқароларимизнинг тинчлиги ва осойишталигини таъминлаш, ҳуқуқ ва манфаатларини ҳимоя қилиш, жиноятчилик ва ҳуқуқбузарликларга, терроризм ва қўпоровчиликларнинг ҳар хил кўринишларига қарши курашиш соҳасидаги қонунчилигимизни янада такомиллаштириш зарурияти юзага келмоқда.

Бугунги кунда қонунчилигимизда ҳокимият вакилига зўрлик ишлатиш, оммавий тартибсизликларни ташкил этиш усулларини ўрганиш жараёнида атрофдагилар учун катта хавф манбаи бўлган қурол-яроғ, портловчи қурилмалар, портловчи, заҳарловчи ва бошқа моддалар билан муомала қилишни ўрганиш бўйича ўқувдан ўтиш, ушбу кўникмаларни ўқитиш, шунингдек фаолиятни молиялаштириш ёки унга бошқа моддий таъминот берганлик учун жавобгарликни назарда тутувчи нормалар аниқ кўрсатилмаган ёки умуман мавжуд эмас.

Оммавий тартибсизликларнинг келиб чиқиш сабаблари, унинг олдини

олиш ва оқибатларини бартараф этишда Россия Федерацияси, Аргентина Республикаси ва бошқа бир қатор давлатлар ҳамда халқаро тажрибани ўрганиш шуни кўрсатадики, шахнинг оммавий тартибсизликларни ўтказишга тайёргарлик кўриши, бундай машғулотларда иштирок этиши учун жиний жавобгарлик кўпчилик давлатлар қонунчиликларида мавжуд.

Масалан, Россия Федерацияси Жиний кодексининг 212-моддасида (Оммавий тартибсизликлар) “Оммавий тартибсизликлар уюштириш ёки уларда иштирок этиш мақсадида тайёргарликдан ўтиш ёки унда иштирок этиш, агар ўқиган шахсга мақсади аниқ бўлса, шу жумладан, жисмоний ва психологик тайёргарлик жараёнида, оммавий тартибсизликларни ташкил этиш усуллари, қурол, портловчи қурилмалар, портловчи моддалар, заҳарли моддалар, шунингдек бошқа моддалар ва нарсалар билан муомала қилиш қоидаларини ўрганишда билим, амалий кўникма ва бошқалар учун хавфли бўлган малакаларни эгаллаш – беш юз минг рублгача ёки маҳкумнинг иш ҳақи ёки бошқа даромадларидан уч йилгача бўлган муддатда белгиланган миқдорда жарима ўндириш билан ёки беш йилдан ўн йилгача озодликдан маҳрум қилиш билан жазоланади” деб кўрсатилган. [3]

Аргентина Республикаси Жиний кодексининг 189/2-моддасида “Жамоат хавфсизлигига қарши жинийлар содир этилишига қўмаклашиш ёки техникага ёки ишлаб чиқариш жараёнига зарар етказиш мақсадида ишлаб чиқариш, етказиб бериш, сотиб олиш, ёки ядро

энергиясини, портловчи, ёнувчан, бўғувчи ёки заҳарли моддаларни чиқаришга қодир бўлган портловчи қурилмалар, моддалар ёки аппаратлар ёки уларни ишлаб чиқариш учун мўлжалланган моддалар ёки материалларга эгаллаб олса беш йилдан ўн беш йилгача мажбурий меҳнат ёки озодликдан маҳрум қилиш билан жазоланади” деб кўрсатилган.

Худди шу жазо жамоат хавфсизлигига қарши жинийлар ёки техника ёки ишлаб чиқаришга зарар етказишга қаратилган хатти-ҳаракатлар содир этишга ҳисса қўшганлигини била туриб ёки билишга мажбур бўлган ҳолда, ушбу модданинг олдинги қисмида кўрсатилган моддалар ёки материалларни тайёрлашни ўргатган ҳар қандай шахсга нисбатан қўлланилади”. [4]

Айрим давлатларда оммавий тартибсизликларнинг олдини олишга қаратилган превентив нормалар ҳам мавжуд масалан, Япония Жиний кодексининг 107-моддасида (Тарқалиш талабини бажармаслик) “Агар оломон зўравонлик ёки таҳдид қилиш мақсадида тўпланган бўлса ва тегишли давлат мансабдор шахсидан уч ёки ундан кўп марта тарқалиб кетиш тўғрисида буйруқ олинган бўлса-да, у ҳалигача тарқалмаган бўлса, жиний гуруҳ раҳбарлари мажбурий жисмоний меҳнат ёки уч йилгача озодликдан маҳрум қилиш билан жазоланади, бошқа шахслар эса юз минг ийенгача миқдорда жарима солиш билан жазоланади” деб кўрсатилган. [5]

Дания қироллиги Жиний кодексининг 134-моддасида ҳам юқоридаги каби огоҳлантирувчи

диспозицияни кўриш мумкин, яъни “тарқалиш тўғрисидаги буйруқ қонуний берилганлигини билиб, қонунга хилоф йиғилишнинг ҳар қандай иштирокчиси бундай буйруққа бўйсунмаса, уч ойдан ортиқ бўлмаган муддатга озодликдан маҳрум қилиш ёки оғирлаштирилган ҳолларда худди шу муддатга озодликдан маҳрум қилиш билан жазоланади” деб кўрсатилган. [6]

Корея Республикаси Жиноят кодексига бўлса оммавий тартибсизликлар тўғрисида алоҳида модда киритилган, яъни ушбу кодекснинг 115-моддасида (Оммавий тартибсизликлар) кўриш мумкин “Кўпчилик бўлиб йиғилиб, зўравонлик ёки кўрқитиш ишлатган ёки бузғунчи ҳаракатлар содир этган шахслар бир йилдан ортиқ бўлмаган муддатга мажбурий меҳнат ёки ўн йилдан кўп бўлмаган муддатга озодликдан маҳрум қилиш ёхуд ўн беш миллион вондан ортиқ бўлмаган жарима билан жазоланади.” [7]

Юқоридагилардан кўришиб турганидек, бундай ҳаракатлар учун қонунчиликда аниқ жавобгарликнинг белгиланиши, жуда муҳимдир. Қолаверса оммавий тартибсизликлар вақтида ҳуқуқни муҳофаза қилувчи органлари ходимларига нисбатан тажовуз, зўравонлик ва бошқача турдаги куч ишлатиш ҳолатларининг кескин ортишини, аҳоли билан ҳуқуқни муҳофаза қилувчи органлар ўртасида қуроли қарама-қаршиликлар юзага келишини, бу эса ўз навбатида ҳуқуқни муҳофаза қилувчи идораларининг ўз вазифаларини ижро этишда жуда катта қийинчиликларга дуч келишини кузатиш мумкин. Миллий

қонунчилигимизда айнан оммавий тартибсизликлар вақтида шу каби ҳаракатлар учун жавобгарлик кўрсатилмаган.

Бу каби ҳаракатлар учун жавобгарликнинг белгиланиши, яъни ҳуқуқни муҳофаза қилувчи органларининг ўз вазифаларини бажаришини мурқаблашининг олдини олишга қаратилган норманинг мавжудлиги аҳамиятлидир, масалан Бельгия қиролиги Жиноят кодексининг 269-моддасида (Кўзғолон ҳақида) “Қонунлар ёки давлат ҳокимияти органларининг фармойишлари, тергов фармойишлари ёки суд қарорлари ижросини таъминлаётган, давлат хизматчиларига, қишлоқ полицияси ходимларига ёки ўрмончиларга, Қуроли Кучлар раҳбарлари ёки агентларига, солиқ йиғувчиларга, суд ижрочиларига, божхона ходимларига, мусодара қилинган мулкни сақловчиларга, маъмурий ёки суд полицияси ходимларига нисбатан ҳар қандай ҳужум, зўравонлик билан қаршилик кўрсатиш исён деб баҳоланади” деб кўрсатилган.

Шунингдек, 271-моддасида “Битта қуроли шахс томонидан содир этилган кўзғолон уч ойдан икки йилгача озодликдан маҳрум қилиш, қуроли бўлмаган тақдирда - саккиз кундан олти ойгача озодликдан маҳрум қилиш билан жазоланади” деб, 272- моддасида “Агар кўзғолонда олдин тил бириктирган бир неча шахс иштирок этган бўлса, қурол олиб юрган кўзғолончилар беш йилдан ўн йилгача озодликдан маҳрум қилиш, қолганлари - бир йилдан беш йилгача озодликдан

махрум қилиш билан жазоланади” деб, ушбу модданинг 2 қисмида “Агар қўзғолон олдиндан келишилган натижага эришмаса, қўзғолоннинг қуролли иштирокчилари бир йилдан беш йилгача озодликдан маҳрум қилиш, қолганлари уч ойдан икки йилгача озодликдан маҳрум қилиш билан жазоланади” деб кўрсатилган. [8]

Юқоридагилардан кўришиб турганидек кўпчилик ривожланган давлатлар тажрибаси шуни кўрсатадики, жиноят кодексидаги диспозициялар асосан оммавий тартибсизликларнинг олдини олиш ва превентив чораларни кўришга қаратилган.

Шу боис, оммавий тартибсизликлар, оммавий қонунга итоат қилмаслик каби салбий ҳолатларга қарши курашишнинг ҳуқуқий асосларини яратиш мақсадида, янги қонунлар, концепцияларни ишлаб чиқиш ва қабул қилиш, айрим қонун, ҳужжатларга ўзгартириш ва қўшимчалар киритиш, уларни бугунги кун талабларидан келиб чиққан ҳолда ўз вақтида такомиллаштириб бориш мақсадга мувофиқдир.

Бу соҳада “Ўзбекистон Республикаси жамоат хавфсизлиги концепцияси”нинг қабул қилиниши жамоат тартибини сақлаш ва хавфсизлигини таъминлашни янада такомиллаштиришда муҳим қадам бўлди. Концепцияда жамоат хавфсизлигини таъминловчи ва унда иштирок этувчи субъектлар белгилаб берилди ва унга кўра Ўзбекистон Республикаси Вазирлар Маҳкамаси, Ички ишлар вазирлиги, Миллий гвардия, Фавқулодда вазиятлар

вазирлиги, Давлат хавфсизлик хизмати, Бош прокуратура, Маҳалла ва оилани қўллаб-қувватлаш вазирлиги, Ахборот технологиялари ва коммуникацияларини ривожлантириш вазирлиги, Соғлиқни сақлаш вазирлиги, маҳаллий давлат ҳокимияти органлари жамоат хавфсизлигини таъминловчи субъектлардир. Бундан ташқари “Ўзбекистон Республикаси Миллий гвардияси тўғрисида”ги [9] Қонунига мувофиқ Миллий гвардия органларига жамоат хавфсизлигини таъминлаш, ғайриҳуқуқий ҳаракатларга чек қўйиш ҳуқуқбузарликлар профилактикасини амалга ошириш ва бошқа вазифалар алоҳида юклатилган бўлиб, ушбу вазифаларнинг белгилаб берилиши Миллий гвардиянинг жамоат хавфсизлигини таъминловчи субъекта сифатида мақомига янада аниқлик киритади ва мустаҳкамлайди.

Қолаверса Ўзбекистон Республикаси Президентининг “2022-2026 йилларга мўлжалланган Янги Ўзбекистоннинг тараққиёт стратегияси тўғрисида”ги Фармони билан 100 та мақсад белгилаб олинган бўлса, шунинг 16-мақсади “Жамоат хавфсизлигини таъминлаш, ҳуқуқбузарликларнинг содир этилишига сабаб бўлган шарт-шароитларни ўз вақтида аниқлаш ва бартараф этишнинг самарали тизимини яратиш” [10] ҳисобланади.

Жамоат тартибини сақлаш ва хавфсизлигини таъминлашга қаратилган қонунлар ва қонун ости ҳужжатлари қабул қилинишига қарамасдан, жамият ривожланиб, аҳоли сони ортиб, иқтисодий томондан юксалиб боргани сари ижтимоий муносабатларни тартибга солишда янги

муаммо ва қонунчиликдаги бўшлиқлар юзага келади ва вақт ўтгани сари яққол намоён бўла бошлаши аниқ.

Бугунги кунга келиб қўшни давлатларда рўй бераётган воқеалардан хулоса чиқаришимиз, қонунларимизни такомиллаштириб боришимиз зарурлигини кўрсатмоқда. Янада чуқурроқ кириб борадиган бўлсак, Ўзбекистон Республикасида амалда бўлган маъмурий ҳуқуқбузарликлар ва жиноят қонунчилигида рухсат этилмаган митинг ва йиғилишлар ташкилотчиларининг жавобгарлиги назарда тутилган бўлиб, унинг иштирокчиларининг жавобгарлиги кўзда тутилмаган. Шу билан бирга, рухсат этилмаган митинг ва оммавий тартибсизликларда иштирок этиш учун омма олдида даъватлар қилиш, оммавий тартибсизликларни ўтказиш бўйича ўқувдан ўтиш ва бошқа масалалар бўйича жавобгарлик тартибга солинмаган.

Лекин, Россия Федерацияси, Хитой Халқ Республикаси, Болгария, Қозоғистон ва Грузия давлатларининг қонунчилигида юқоридаги каби қилмишлар учун жиноий жавобгарлик назарда тутилганини кўриш мумкин.

Хитой Халқ Республикаси жиноят кодекси 290-моддасида “меҳнат, ишлаб чиқариш, хўжалик, ўқув ва илмий-тадқиқот фаолиятини нормал амалга оширишнинг имкони бўлмаслигига ва жиддий йўқотишларга олиб келган оммавий тартибсизликларни қўзғатувчилар, оғирлаштирувчи ҳолатларда – уч йилдан етти йилгача озодликдан маҳрум қилиш билан жазоланади, ўша ҳаракатлар бошқа фаол иштирокчилар томонидан содир

этилган бўлса – уч йилгача озодликдан маҳрум қилиш, қисқа муддатга ҳибсга олиш, назорат қилиш ёки сиёсий ҳуқуқлардан маҳрум қилиш билан жазоланади” деб кўрсатилган, ёки ушбу кодекснинг 298-моддасида “Қонун ҳужжатларига мувофиқ ўтказиладиган митинглар, юришлар ва намойишларга бузғунчи ҳаракатлар, ҳужумлар ва оммавий тартибсизликларга олиб келадиган бошқа усуллар билан тўсқинлик қилиш – беш йилгача озодликдан маҳрум қилиш, қисқа муддатли ҳибсга олиш, назорат қилиш ёки сиёсий ҳуқуқлардан маҳрум қилиш билан жазоланади” деб кўрсатилган.[11]

Болгария Республикаси жиноят кодекси 320-моддасида “ким кўп одамлар орасида ваъз қилиш, босма нашрларни тарқатиш ёки шунга ўхшаш бошқа йўллар билан жиноят содир этишга очиқ-ойдин гижгизлаган бўлса, уч йилгача озодликдан маҳрум қилиш билан жазоланади” [12] деб кўрсатилган.

Миллий қонунчилигимизда ҳам оммавий тартибсизликларнинг олдини олишга қаратилган нормалар мавжуд бўлиб, масалан Маъмурий жавобгарлик тўғрисидаги кодекснинг 1951-моддасида (Ўзбекистон Республикаси Миллий гвардияси ҳарбий хизматчиларининг (ходимларининг) ўз хизмат бурчларини бажаришларига қаршилик кўрсатиш) “Ўзбекистон Республикаси Миллий гвардияси ҳарбий хизматчисининг (ходимининг) ўз хизмат вазифаларини бажариши билан боғлиқ қонуний талабларини бажармасликка омма олдида ҳар қандай шаклда даъватлар қилиш, худди шунингдек Ўзбекистон Республикаси

Миллий гвардиясиҳарбий хизматчиларига (ходимларига) оммавий равишда бўйсунмасликни келтириб чиқариш мақсадида била туриб сохта уйдирмаларни тарқатиш, базавий ҳисоблаш миқдорининг уч бараваридан йигирма бараваригача миқдорда жарима солишга ёки ўн беш суткагача муддатга маъмурий қамоққа олишга сабаб бўлади” деб кўрсатилган.

Худду шундай нормани ушбу кодекснинг 195-моддаси (Ички ишлар органлари ходимларининг ўз хизмат бурчларини бажаришларига қаршилик кўрсатиш) ва 196¹-моддаларида (Чегара қўшинлари ҳарбий хизматчиларининг қонуний талабларини бажармаслик ва уларнинг қонуний фаолиятига қаршилик кўрсатиш) кўриш мумкин. [13]

Шунингдек, Ўзбекистон Республикаси Жиноят кодексининг 244-моддасида (Оммавий тартибсизликлар) “Оммавий тартибсизликларга ва фуқароларга нисбатан зўравонлик қилишга омма олдида даъват қилиш, базавий ҳисоблаш миқдорининг юз бараваридан уч юз бараваригача жарима ёки икки йилгача ахлоқ тузатиш ишлари ёхуд уч йилдан беш йилгача озодликни чеклаш ёки уч йилдан беш йилгача озодликдан маҳрум қилиш билан жазоланади.

Ўша ҳаракатлар:

а) бир гуруҳ шахслар томонидан олдиндан тил бириктириб;

б) оммавий ахборот воситаларидан, телекоммуникациялар тармоқларидан, Интернет жаҳон ахборот тармоғидан, шунингдек матнни кўпайтиришнинг босма ёки бошқа усулларида фойдаланган ҳолда содир

этилган бўлса, базавий ҳисоблаш миқдорининг уч юз бараваридан тўрт юз бараваригача жарима ёки икки йилдан уч йилгача ахлоқ тузатиш ишлари ёхуд беш йилдан ўн йилгача озодликдан маҳрум қилиш билан жазоланади.

Қурул ёки қурул сифатида фойдаланиладиган бошқа нарсаларни ишлатиб ёхуд ишлатиш билан кўрқитиб шахсга нисбатан зўрлик ишлатиш, қирғин солиш, ўт қўйиш, мулкка шикаст етказиш ёки уни нобуд қилиш, ҳокимият вакилига қаршилик кўрсатиш орқали содир этилган оммавий тартибсизликлар ташкил қилиш, шунингдек, оммавий тартибсизликларда фаол қатнашиш, ўн йилдан ўн беш йилгача озодликдан маҳрум қилиш билан жазоланади” деб кўрсатилган. [14]

Бундан ташқари оммавий тартибсизликларнинг олдини олишга қаратилган маъмурий-ҳуқуқий асосларни такомиллаштирар эканмиз, “оммавий тартибсизликлар” тушунчасининг мазмунини очиш ва унга аниқ таъриф бериш ҳам аҳамиятли ҳисобланади. Лекин, бу борада олимлар ҳар хил фикрда бўлиб ягона ёндошув мавжуд эмас.

Масалан, В.Н.Кудрявцева, В.В.Лунева, А.В.Наумоваларнинг фикрича оммавий тартибсизликлар - бу одамларнинг катта гуруҳи (оломон) томонидан содир этиладиган жамоат хавфсизлиги асосларини бузиш бўлиб, бунинг натижасида давлат ва бошқарув органларининг, транспорт, алоқанинг нормал фаолияти фалаж ҳолатга тушади, мулкларга, фуқароларнинг

хуқуқ ва манфаатларига жиддий зарар етказилиши.[15]

А.Г.Королькованинг фикрича, “оммавий тартибсизликлар — аҳолининг катта гуруҳи (оломон) томонидан жамоат хавфсизлиги ва жамоат тартибини бузиш, бунинг натижасида транспорт, муассасалар фаолиятининг бузилиши, одамларнинг мол-мулки, соғлиғи ва ҳаётига зарар етказилиши”.[16]

В.В.Мозяковнинг фикрича “оммавий тартибсизликлар – ўз-ўзидан тўпланган муҳим гуруҳ (оломон) томонидан жамоат тартибини бузиш, оммавий қурбонлар, мулк, транспорт, алоқа воситаларининг йўқ қилинишига олиб келиниши”.[17]

И.Я.Казаченко оммавий тартибсизликларни “тартиб бузувчилар оломонининг оммавий қурбонларга, мулк, транспорт ва алоқа воситаларининг йўқ бўлиб кетишига олиб келадиган шафқатсиз бузғунчи хатти-ҳаракатлари” [18] сифатида таърифлайди.

Оммавий тартибсизлик тушунчасига қандай таъриф берилишидан қатъий назар, бир нарса аниқки, ушбу ҳодиса қонун билан ҳимоя қилинадиган ижтимоий муносабатларга

катта зарар етказилади. Шундай экан, унинг олдин олиш ва профилактикасини кучайтириш мақсадга мувофиқдир.

Юқоридаги манбаларнинг таҳлили, оммавий тартибсизликлар келтириб чиқариши мумкин бўлган зарарларнинг олдини олишга, фуқароларнинг хуқуқ ва қонуний манфаатларини ҳимоя қилишга, умуман жамоат тартибини сақлашга ва хавфсизлигини таъминлашга қаратилган чора-тадбирларни такомиллаштиришга зарурат борлигини тасдиқлайди.

Хулоса қиладиган бўлсак, чет давлатлар кодекслари ва бошқа хуқуқий манбаларининг таҳлили шуни кўрсатмоқдаки, жамоат тартибини сақлаш ва хавфсизлигини таъминлаш, инсон ва фуқароларнинг хуқуқ ва манфаатларини ҳимоя қилиш мақсадида, чет давлатларнинг ушбу соҳадаги тажрибалари самарадорлигидан келиб чиқиб Ўзбекистон Республикаси маъмурий жавобгарлик тўғрисидаги кодекс ва Жиноят кодексларига ўзгартириш ва қўшимчалар киритиш мақсадга мувофиқдир.

References:

1. 2021 йил 27 ноябрь кунги “Ўзбекистон Республикаси жамоат хавфсизлиги концепциясини тасдиқлаш ва уни амалга ошириш чора-тадбирлари тўғрисида” 27-сон Фармони;
2. Концепция внешней политики Российской Федерации // Министерство иностранных дел Российской Федерации. Официальный сайт. URL:http://www.mid.ru/brp_4.nsf/0/6D84DDEDED7DA644257B160051BF7F;
3. Россия Федерацияси Жиноят кодекси;
4. Аргентина Республикаси жиноят кодекси
5. Япония Жиноят кодекси;

6. Дания қироллиги Жиноят кодекси
7. Корея Республикаси жиноят кодекси;
8. Бельгия қироллигининг жиноят кодекси;
9. 2020 йил 18 ноябрь кунги “Ўзбекистон Республикаси Миллий гвардияси тўғрисида” Қонуни;
10. 2022 йил 28 январь кунги Ўзбекистон Республикаси Президентининг “2022 — 2026 йилларга мўлжалланган янги ўзбекистоннинг тараққиёт стратегияси тўғрисида”ги 60-сон Фармони
11. Хитой Халқ Республикаси Жиноят кодекси;
12. Болгария Республикаси Жиноят кодекси;
13. Ўзбекистон Республикаси Маъмурий жавобгарлик тўғрисидаги кодекс
14. Ўзбекистон Республикаси Жиноят кодекси
15. Уголовное право России. Особенная часть: учебник / под ред. В.Н.Кудрявцева, В.В.Лунева, А.В.Наумова. – М., 2005.
16. Комментарий к Уголовному кодексу РФ / под ред. А. Г. Королькова. – М., 2004.
17. Комментарий к Уголовному кодексу Российской Федерации. Расширенный уголовно-правовой анализ / под ред. В. В. Мозякова. – М., 2002.
18. Уголовное право. Особенная часть : учебник для вузов / под ред. И. Я. Козаченко, З. А. Незнамова, Г. П. Новоселова. – М., 2000.

O'ZBEK MILLIY MADANIYATINING TURKIY MADANIYATLAR RIVOJIGA TA'SIRI

Aziza Nazirkulova Abduvaliyevna

MAQOLA TARIXI

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2025
Ma'qullandi: 20 September
2025
Chop etildi: 14-September
2025

KALIT SO'ZLAR

Rivojlanish, o'z-o'zini
anglash, faoliyat, muloqot,
individ, individuallik, shaxs,
sotsializatsiya, jamiyat,
ong.

Shaxs sotsializatsiyasining falsafiy
jihatlari ijtimoiy hayot hodisasi
sifatida ma'lum bir jamiyatga xos
bo'lgan shaxs rivojlanishining
tarixiy shartli
jarayoni bo'lib, u
shaxs tomonidan qadriyatlar,
me'yorlar, munosabatlarning
va umri davomida xulq-
atvor namunalari
o'zlashtirilishini va uning natijasi
shaxs tomonidan o'z faoliyati va
muloqotida olingan ijtimoiy

ANNOTATSIYA

Maqolada shaxsning shakllanishi va rivojlanish
jarayonida sotsializatsiyaning roli muhokama qilinadi va
sotsializatsiya jarayonini shaxsni shakllantirishning zaruriy
sharti deb hisoblash mumkinmi degan savol tug'iladi. Shaxs
va sotsializatsiya tushunchalari mazmun-mohiyati ko'rib
chiqilgan. Shaxs shakllanishining uch bosqichi ko'rib
chiqiladi va taqqoslanadi: individ (tabiiy, genetik va biologik
jihati), individuallik (psixologik jihati), shaxs (ijtimoiy jihati),
shuningdek, sotsializatsiyaning uchta eng muhim sohasi:
faoliyat, muloqot, o'z-o'zini anglash. Maqolada dialektik va
faol yondashuv, tahlil qilish, umumlashtirish, taqqoslashning
asosiy tamoyillari qo'llanilgan. Ijtimoiylashuvning ushbu
sohalarini shakllantirish xususiyatlarini o'rganib, shaxsning
rivojlanish jarayoni ma'lum bir tarixiy davrda uning turli
bosqichlarida (individ, individuallik, shaxs) qanday kechishi
haqida xulosalar chiqarish mumkin.

tajribani faol takrorlashdir.
Ijtimoiylashuv tarbiya, ya'ni shaxsni
maqsadli shakllantirish sharoitida
ham sodir bo'lishi mumkin.
Ijtimoiylashtirish ilmiy kategoriya
sifatida 1887 yilda
amerikalik sotsiolog F.Giddings
muallifligidagi "Ijtimoiylashuv nazariyasi"
kitobining paydo bo'lishi bilan ko'rib
chiqila boshlandi. U sotsializatsiyani
insonning ijtimoiy tabiatining rivojlanish
jarayoni sifatida ko'rib chiqishni taklif qildi.

yoshigacha kengayishi bilan tavsiflanadi. Binobarin, sotsializatsiya ilmiy kategoriya sifatida jamiyatdagi ijtimoiy va shaxsiy munosabatlarni qayta ishlab chiqaradigan bir qator masalalarni ko'rib chiqadi. Bundan tashqari, yosh avlodning ijtimoiy moslashuvi va uning hayotiy kompetensiyasi muammolari atrofida to'plangan munosabatlarning keskinlashuvi ularni gumanitar fanlar, xususan: falsafa, sotsiologiya, psixologiya, etnografiya, pedagogika va boshqalar tomonidan har tomonlama o'rganilishi za'ru'rligi belgilab beradi. Odatda, biz inson tabiatini biologik, psixologik va ijtimoiy uchlik deb hisoblashga odatlanganmiz va bu jihatlar bir vaqtning o'zida shaxs rivojlanishining ma'lum darajalarini ifodalaydi. Buni falsafa klassiklarining qarashlari tasdiqlaydi. Masalan, G.Gegel individ ruh sohasida madaniyatni egallashi bilan shaxsga aylanadi, deb hisoblagan. "O'zlik haqiqati faqat tabiiy o'zlikni yo'q qilishdan iborat... Individuallik harakati... uning universal obyektiv mavjudot sifatida shakllanishidir..." [1] K. Marks va F. Engels nemis mafkurasida tarixiy farq haqida yozadilar. Odamlarning atrofdagi ijtimoiy voqelik bilan real o'zaro ta'siri natijasida kuzatilishi mumkin. Klassiklar nuqtai nazaridan, individning shaxsga aylanishi tarixiy jihatdan sodir bo'ladi. Shaxs sifatida tug'iladi, lekin uning rivojlanishida uch bosqich mavjud: individ, individuallik, shaxs [2]. Individ "ijtimoiy atom" bo'lib, u boshqa shaxslardan (birinchi navbatda jismonan,) ajralganligini ko'rsatadigan eng oddiy xususiyatdir. Ona qornidagi homila, tug'ilgan chaqaloq individdir. Individuallik har qanday shaxsning shaxsiy fazilatlarini va xususiyatlarining barcha boyligidagi va o'ziga xosligini bildiradi. Shaxs kim?

Qisqacha aytganda, bu shaxsning faol, ongli va mas'uliyatli yashash yo'lini tavsiflovchi ijtimoiy mulkdir [3]. Albatta, inson jamiyatdagina shaxsga aylana oladi, aynan jamiyat - bu muhit, insonni shaxsga aylantiruvchi eng muhim omil. Jamiyatdan tashqarida shaxsga aylanish mumkinmi? Albatta yo'q. Shunki jamiyatning mavjudligi insonning shaxs bo'lishining zaruriy sharti hisoblanishi mumkin. Jamiyatda inson ijtimoiylashadi. Unda sotsializatsiya jarayonini insonning shaxsga aylanishining zaruriy sharti deb hisoblash mumkinmi? degan savol paydo bo'ladi. Ilmiy adabiyotlarda ijtimoiylashuv jarayonining bosqichlarini aniqlash muammosi turli nuqtai nazardan ochib berilgan. Masalan, sotsializatsiya fazalari yosh mezoniga ko'ra (bolalik, o'smirlik, yoshlik, o'rta yosh, qarilik), insonning mehnat faoliyatiga jalb qilish darajasiga (mehnatdan oldingi bosqich, mehnat, mehnatdan keyingi) falsafiy nuqtai nazardan qaraganda, jamiyatda shaxsga aylanish jarayonini A. N. Leontiev kontseptsiyasidan foydalangan holda eng to'liq, mazmunli va lo'nda tasvirlash mumkindek tuyuladi. [4] Unga ko'ra, shaxs o'zining shakllanishi jarayonida va butun rivojlanishi davomida faoliyat "katalogi"ni kengaytirib, ushbu faoliyatning har xil turlarini o'zlashtirib boradi, asta-sekin ijtimoiy faoliyat sub'yektiga aylanadi. Inson mavjudligining uchta eng muhim sohasi: faoliyatning o'zi, muloqot, o'z-o'zini anglash. Shaxsning ijtimoiylashuvi - ta'lim-tarbiya ta'sirida inson psixologik funksiyalarining takomillashuvi, ijtimoiy-axloqiy qadriyatlar, xulq-atvor me'yor va qoidalarining o'zlashtirilishi, dunyoqarashining boyish jarayoni va natijasi. Demak, shaxs individ bo'lib

tug'iladi, u faqat o'ziga xos bo'lgan geno- va fenotipik xususiyatlar va xususiyatlarning o'ziga xos majmuida namoyon bo'ladi. Shu nuqtai nazardan inson faoliyati uning ijtimoiylashuviga kuchli tasir o'tkazadi.

Falsafada faoliyat deganda ijtimoiy subyekt tomonidan uning mavjudligi va rivojlanishi uchun shart-sharoitlarni yaratish, atrofdagi dunyoni va o'zini uning ehtiyojlari va maqsadlariga muvofiq o'zgartirish jarayoni tushuniladi. Faoliyat insonning o'zini, butun hayot tarzi va fikrlarini shakllantiradigan tizimni tashkil etuvchi kuch sifatida ishlaydi. Faoliyat - maqsadli va ongli faoliyat, istalgan natijaga erishish uchun ob'ektga ta'sir qilish. "Individ" bosqichda bo'lgan shaxsni faol mavjudot sifatida tavsiflash mumkin, muayyan harakatlarni amalga oshiradi, lekin faol mavjudot emas, ayrim faoliyatni amalga oshirmaydi.

Ijtimoiylashish jarayonida ongning ro'li katta ekanligini takitlab o'tish zarurli. S.Rubinshteynning falsafiy-psixologik asarlarida ong psixik jarayonlar, munosabatlar va faoliyatlarning tartibga solish funktsiyalarini bajaradigan borliqni aks ettirishning o'ziga xos shakli sifatida namoyon bo'ladi. Ong insonni dunyoga olib keladi va uni o'z-o'zidan yopmaydi, ijtimoiy va individual ravishda belgilanadigan maqsadlarni qo'yishga imkon beradi [5].

Demak, shaxsda ongning shakllanishi bilan individuallik shakllanadi. Shunday qilib, shartli ravishda sotsializatsiyaning "birinchi" sohasi - faoliyat sohasi shaxsni shakllantirish jarayonida individuallik bosqichiga mos kelishini aytishimiz mumkin. Ijtimoiylashtirishning ikkinchi sohasi aloqa sohasidir. Bu soha shaxsning rivojlanish bosqichlari bilan chambarchas bog'liq Shunki, muloqot jarayoni, muloqot

inson tug'ilgan paytdan boshlab paydo bo'ladi, ya'ni, shaxs sifatida tavsiflanishi mumkin bo'lgan bosqichdan. Bu davrda bu jarayon ibtidoiy xarakterga ega bo'lib, insoniyat taraqqiyoti jarayonida muloqotning o'zaro ta'siri tobora murakkablashib, ijtimoiy xarakterga ega bo'ladi. Agar yangi tug'ilgan chaqaloq kattalarga oddiy, instinktiv usullar va vositalar yordamida uning ehtiyojlari mavjudligi to'g'risida shunchaki ishora qilsa, u holda shaxsiyatni shakllantirish bosqichida muloqot jarayoni o'ziga xos, ko'p funktsiyali, murakkab og'zaki xususiyatga ega bo'ladi. Individuallikning shakllanish bosqichi - bu shaxsning o'ziga xosligini rivojlantirish, uni "atomlik" doirasidan tashqariga olib chiqadigan davr. Ammo bu shunchaki o'ziga xoslik emas, balki insonni boshqa barcha tirik mavjudotlardan ajratib turadigan o'ziga xoslikdir. J.Habermas ta'biri bilan aytganda, inson nafaqat shaxs sifatida, balki individual shaxs sifatida e'tirof etilgandagina ma'noga ega bo'ladi [6]. Boladagi shaxs sifatida shakllanish instinktiv emas, balki ongli ravishda uni o'rab turgan qo'zg'atuvchi omillarga munosabat bildira boshlaganida sodir bo'ladi. Tug'ilgan paytdan boshlab u o'ziga xos harakat uslubini, onasi va qarindoshlari tomonidan yaxshi taniladigan o'ziga xos xulq-atvor uslubini rivojlantiradi. Biroq, bu xulq-atvor ko'proq darajada instinktiv bo'lib, turli xil qo'zg'atuvchilarga bo'lgan reaksiyalar individual xarakterga ega bo'lsa-da, lekin ular genetik jihatdan asoslanadi va ko'proq shaxsning biologik tabiati bilan belgilanadi. Bu umumiy narsa va u faqat insonning jismoniy "men" ning mohiyatini belgilaydi [7]. Insonning individualligi yildan-yilga "o'sib boradi",

uning ruhiy "men" ni, uning ruhi doirasini belgilovchi xususiyatlarda namoyon bo'ladi. Bu insonga o'z qobiliyatlari va imkoniyatlarini ko'rsatishga yordam beradi, boshqalarga ma'lum bir tarzda munosabatda bo'ladi. Barcha xususiyatlarni sanab o'tib bo'lmaydi, chunki insonning individual xususiyatlari aqliy soha bo'lib, tizimlashtirish va tartibga solish juda qiyin. Biroq, individuallikni shakllantirish nuqtai nazaridan ba'zi muhim xususiyatlarni ajratib ko'rsatish mumkin. Ular bilish sohasiga, hissiy sohaga va shaxsning haqiqiy faoliyati sohasiga tegishli. O'z-o'zini anglashni rivojlantirish va shakllantirish shaxsni ajralmas mavjudot sifatida tushunish bilan bog'liq bo'lgan shaxsni sotsializatsiya qilishning eng muhim sohasi bo'lib, unga insoniyat doirasini kengaytirish sharoitida ijtimoiy tajribani doimiy ravishda egallash orqali erishiladi. Rubinshteynning ta'kidlashicha,

har bir inson ongli ijtimoiy mavjudot, amaliyotning, tarixning sub'ekti bo'lib, shuning uchun shaxsdir [5].

Bundan shuni bilishimiz kerakki, inson boshqa odamlarga bo'lgan munosabatini belgilab, u o'zini belgilaydi. Demak, jamiyatda shaxs bo'lish jarayoni faoliyat, muloqot va o'z-o'zini anglash orqali amalga oshiriladi. Bular shaxsning shakllanish bosqichlari: individ, individuallik, shaxsiyat bilan taqqoslandi va faoliyat individuallik bosqichiga va shaxsning o'ziga mos kelishi aniqlandi; muloqot - shaxs rivojlanishining barcha bosqichlari, o'z-o'zini anglash - shaxs bosqichi. Shartli nazariya va mantiqiy mulohazalardan so'ng, shunday xulosaga kelish mumkinki, jamiyat rivojlanishining turli bosqichlarida sotsializatsiya jarayonining o'ziga xos xususiyatlari bor, ular boshqa jarayonlar qatorida namoyon bo'ladi.

References:

1. Гегель, Г. Работы разных лет / Г. Гегель / Перев. И.Г. Арзаканьяна и А.В. Михайлова – М.: Мысль, 1971. – 316 с.
2. Кашин В.В., Мирошникова О.В. Онтологические основания социализации личности / В.В. Кашин, О.В. Мирошникова // Вестник ОГУ.-№1(150).-2013. – С. 32-36
3. Ростовцева М. В. Адаптация и социализация: анализ общего и особенного / М.В. Ростовцева // Социодинамика. 2016.-№ 7.-С. 31-37
4. Леонтьев, А.Н. Деятельность. Сознание. Личность. / А.Н.Леонтьев. – М.: Феникс, 1995. – 480
5. Рубинштейн, С.Л. Бытие и сознание: о месте психологического во всеобщей взаимосвязи явлений материального мира / С.Л.Рубинштейн. – М.: Мысль, 1957. – 328 с.
6. Хабермас Ю. Понятие индивидуальности // Вопросы философии. — 1989.-№ 2. – С. 18-23
7. Ростовцева М.В. Adaptive society: problems and prospects of its construction / Ростовцева М.В., Кудашов В.И., Машанов А.А. // Интеллект. Инновации. Инвестиции. 2015.-№ 1.-С. 170-174

БИЛЛИНГВИЗМ В УЗБЕКСКОЙ И ЧИКАНСКОЙ ЛИТЕРАТУРЕ. МАРТИН ЭСПАДА И САДРИДДИН АЙНИЙ КАК ИЗВЕСТНЫЕ ДВУЯЗЫЧНЫЕ ПРЕДСТАВИТЕЛИ

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ИСТОРИЯ СТАТЬИ

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КЛЮЧЕВЫЕ СЛОВА

Мартин Эспада,
двуязычие, Садриддин
Айний, чикано, диглоссия,
чистое двуязычие,
комбинированное
двуязычие,
национальный дух.

АННОТАЦИЯ

В данной статье рассматриваются вопросы билингвизма в узбекской и американской поэзии. Анализируются произведения двух выдающихся литераторов Мартина Эспады и Садриддина Айния. Читатель сможет понять значение слова «двуязычие» и получит возможность понять жизнь и литературную деятельность этих знаменитых поэтов.

Двуязычие можно встретить во многих произведениях мировых литераторов. Сочетание двух языков является результатом взаимодействия в многонациональных сообществах. В США распространено использование английского и испанского языков. Результат этого совпадения виден в литературе чикано. Понятие «чикано» этимологически происходит от термина «мексиканский» и в то же время выражает его значение от «испанский на английский» до «испаноязычный коммуникатор». Отсюда следует, что английский язык чикано означает общение на английском языке, основанное на влиянии испанского

Одной из самых ярких личностей в литературной деятельности чикано является Мартин Эспада. Будучи поэтом, эссеистом, переводчиком, редактором и адвокатом, Мартин Эспада посвятил большую часть своей карьеры поиску социальной справедливости, в том числе борьбе за права человека и восстановлению исторической памяти. Его сборники стихов, получившие признание критиков, прославляют — и оплакивают — опыт рабочего класса. Рассказывая о борьбе иммигрантов, приспособившихся к жизни в Соединенных Штатах, или описывая битвы, которые латиноамериканцы

озвучивала инаковость, бессилие и бедность в поэзии, которая одновременно трогательна и трогательна. яркий. Он является автором более десятка сборников стихов и нескольких сборников эссе, переводчиком пуэрториканского поэта Клементе Сото Велеса и редактором влиятельных антологий, таких как «Эль Коро» (1997) и «Поэзия как хлеб» (1994). 5]

Эспада родился в Бруклине, Нью-Йорк. Наибольшее влияние на него оказал его отец, Фрэнк Эспада, общественный деятель, борец за гражданские права и фотограф-документалист, создавший документальный проект пуэрториканской диаспоры. Эспада получил степень бакалавра истории в Университете Висконсин-Мэдисон и степень доктора права в Северо-восточном университете. Много лет он был арендатором-адвокатом; его первая книга стихов «Болеро иммигранта-ледяного мальчика» (1982) включала фотографии, сделанные его отцом. Его последующие книги, в том числе «Трубы с острова их выселения» (1987), «Восстание — это круг рук любовника» (1990) и «Город кашля и мертвых радиаторов» (1993), привлекли значительное внимание. «Представьте себе ангелов хлеба» (1996) получил Американскую книжную премию и стал финалистом Национальной премии кружка книжных критиков. Ранние работы Эспады, часто связанные с социально, экономически и расово маргинализированными людьми, полны увлекательных повествований. Хотя его работы вызывающе и настойчиво

политизированы, они также известны своим мягким юмором. Ричард Бланко прокомментировал: «Стихи Эспады продолжают определять роль поэта как эмоционального историка. Как и Уитмен, Эспада пробуждает в нас неоспоримое социальное сознание и связанность». [5]

Эспада редактировал три важных антологии: «Эль Коро: хор латиноамериканской и латинской поэзии» (1997 г.), «Поэзия как хлеб: поэты политического воображения» (2000 г.) и «Его руки были нежны: избранные тексты Виктора Хара» (2012 г.). В дополнение к своей работе в качестве переводчика и редактора, Эспада также опубликовал книги эссе и критических замечаний, в том числе «Ученик Сапаты» (1998, 2016), «Любитель подрывника тоже подрывник» (2010) и «Необходимая поэтика атеизма» (с Лорен Шмидт и Джереми Шраффенбергером, 2016 г.). [6] В «Прогрессиве» поэт Рафаэль Кампо похвалил мужество Эспады в «Ученике» Сапаты, утверждая, что он является одним из немногих поэтов, которые «берутся за вопросы жизни и смерти американского общества в целом». Книга была запрещена в Тусоне в рамках программы мексиканских американских исследований, запрещенной в штате Аризона, и выпущена в 2016 году издательством Northwestern University Press. Любовник подрывника тоже подрывник рассматривает роль поэзии в политических движениях. По словам поэтессы Барбары Джейн Рейес, «Быть поэтом, — утверждает Эспада в этой серии эссе, — значит быть защитником,

защищать тех, кого заставили замолчать, и места, о которых не говорят... Наша работа как поэтов может расширить возможности замолчал, чтобы говорить». [7]. Его «En la Calle San Sebastián» и «Поэма движения чикано» могут быть приемлемыми примерами литературы чикано:

Here in a bar on the street of the saint
en la calle San Sebastián,
a dancer in white with a red red scarf
en la calle San Sebastián,
calls to the gods who were freed by slaves
en la calle San Sebastián,
and his bronze face is a lantern of sweat
en la calle San Sebastián,
and hands smack congas like flies in the field
en la calle San Sebastián,
and remember the beat of packing crates
en la calle San Sebastián,
from the days when overseers banished the drum
en la calle San Sebastián,
and trumpets screech like parrots of gold
en la calle San Sebastián.....

«en la calle San Sebastián» означает «на улице Сан-Себастьян». В этом стихотворении Мартин Эспада дал определение системе рабства в Америке, фразой «бронзовое лицо — фонарь пота» ярко описан внешний вид мексиканского раба.

Билингвальные черты можно увидеть и в работах ряда узбекских ученых. Литературная деятельность Садриддина Айния демонстрирует идиосинкразические черты двуязычия (в тюрко-узбекской поэзии этот термин упоминается как «зуллисонайн»). Садриддин Айни, родившийся в последней четверти 19 века и доживший до середины 20 века, был плодовитым писателем, внесшим вклад в развитие узбекской и таджикской литературы. Поколение писателей, к которому он принадлежал, стремилось дать новый импульс классической восточной литературе, далекой от жизни народа и общества, обогатить ее идеями новой исторической эпохи. В этом смысле Садриддин Айни и его друзья по переписке заложили основу нового типа узбекской и таджикской литературы 1920-х годов. Садриддин Айни родился в 1878 году в селе Соктаре Гиждуванского района Бухарской области. В возрасте одиннадцати лет он осиротел своими родителями. Садриддин Айни, получивший начальное образование от своего просвещенного отца, учился в медресе в Бухаре в 1890–1899 годах и получил основательное образование в соответствии со своим временем[4]. Знакомство с газетами и журналами, издававшимися в Калькутте, Богчасарае, Уфе, Оренбурге, Казани, особенно чтение таких произведений Фитрата, как «Диспут» и «Индийский путешественник», произвело революцию в мировоззрении писателя.

Он видел упадок эмирата, необходимость модернизации управления страной, демократические

реформы и просвещение масс. [4] Таким образом, Садриддин Айни примкнул к молодобухарскому движению и стал одним из ярких представителей узбекской современной литературы. Хотя Садриддин Айни был более физически активен в подростковом возрасте, позже он начал зарабатывать на жизнь умственным трудом из-за изменений в своем общественном сознании. Например, он работает переводчиком в татарской школе. В то же время Садриддин Айни, приобретший определенные навыки, вместе со своим другом Мирзой Абдулвахидом открыл во дворе школу. В 1909 году он написал учебник «Тажиб ус-сибиён» («Воспитание детей»). [1] Эта ранняя педагогическая деятельность молодого учителя вызвала резкое противодействие, поскольку для того периода она была крупным событием. Говоря о раннем творчестве Садриддина Айни, нельзя обойти вниманием созданное в 1909–1910 годах общество «Тарбияи атфол» («Детское воспитание»). [3] Созданному при участии Садриддина Айни обществу было поручено, во-первых, распространение просвещения и различной литературы среди широких слоев населения, во-вторых, борьба с расточительством, материализмом и прочими пороками, в-третьих, широкая кампания против правительства.

Одним словом, Садриддин Айни своей творческой и организаторской деятельностью в этот период сыграл важную роль в формировании узбекского джадидского движения и джадидской литературы. Его заслуги в этом отношении являются одной из

просветительских страниц творчества Садриддина Айни. Поскольку изначально он происходил из таджикских потомков, персидский эффект виден в нескольких его стихах. [2]

Yuzi toza gul, zebo jamolu **siynasi** nasrin,

Qadi sarvu sanavbardur, **tani nuqra**, bu ta'rif chin,

Labi la'li shirin, go'yo muattar sochlari mushkin,

Bo'lur har kimsaga **oromi dil**, oromi jon, lekin

Ming afsus, men uchun bir zarra ham unda vafo yo'qdir.

Chiroyli yuzlari birlan muattar qora xoliga,

Buralgan sochlari, nozik, go'zal qaddi niholiga,

Dilu jonimni topshirdim vale kelmas xayoliga,

G'arib ushshoqlar qalbin matoin boqki holiga,

Uning bozori husni ichra arzirli baho yo'qdir.

Стихотворение о двух влюбленных. Любящий мальчик описывает красоту своего возлюбленного и выражает свою привязанность.

Demasman **dilni haq**, sen ishq i botil,

Vale **dil**, rost, holing bo'ldi mushkul,

Sen undan noliding, sendan esa dil,

Qon o'lding dilni deb, dil bo'ldi bismil,

Uyal, Lohutiy, **sharm** etsun va yo dil.

Dilu aql ila dinni yengdi savdo, ey, nasihatgo'y,

Qilursan to qachon bizni **tamosho**, ey, nasihatgo'y,

Bo'libman, Ayniy, ishqi ichra **rasvo**, ey, nasihatgo'y,

Ishida bo'ldi xo'b darmonda Yag'mo, ey, nasihatgo'y,

Chunon **rasvoi olam** ayladi, ey, aql, bo'l darmon.

В целом использование двух и более языков в литературных произведениях свидетельствует о

соединении духа двух народов. Традиции, переваренные чужой культурой, поэтому считаются великим явлением в литературной деятельности. Поскольку у медали две стороны, хотя узбекский и испанский народы подверглись жестоким процессам колониального периода, культура, традиции и язык были отшлифованы в широком диапазоне. Социолингвистические аспекты этих двух народов были расширены диглоссивными чертами в результате интерактивных коммуникаций между узбекско-таджиками и мексиканцами-американцами.

Литературы:

1. Arabova, Sharofat (2019 yil 25 mart). "Tojikiston kinoteatri". Osiyo filmlarining zarbasi.
2. Akhmatovna, J. N. Traditions and Rituals Associated with Bobodekhkan in the Lower Zarafshan Oasis. International Journal of Development and Public Policy, 1(8), 2022. 46–53.
3. Davlatova M.H. Aspectual variability of informatiobn culture in the history of the English language.-International Journal of Integrated Education, Volume3, Issue III, March 2020.-P.34-38
4. Davlatova M.H. Variability of Aspectual Meanings in English.-European Journal of Research and Reflection in Educational Science, Volume.7 No.12.2019.-P.778-780
5. Davlatova M.H. An Integrative history of Aspectual meanings.-JournalNX-A Multidisciplinary Peer Reviewed Journal, Volume 6, ISSUE 4, Apr.-2020.-P.17-22
6. Davlatova Mukhayyo Hasanovna. (2021). DIFFERENT ASPECTS OF RESULTATIVE STRUCTURES ACCORDING TO THEIR LINGUISTIC ESSENCE. Academicia Globe: Inderscience Research, 2(05), 475–479. <https://doi.org/10.17605/OSF.IO/D4T8J>.
7. Hasanov M., Ayniy chamani, T., 1978.
8. Habibova, M. N. (2021). JORJINA HOUELLNING "QUEEN OF THE DESERT" BIOGRAFIK ASARIDA GERTRUDA BELL TIMSOLI TASVIRI. ACADEMIC RESEARCH IN EDUCATIONAL SCIENCES, 2(2), 770-778.
9. Habibova, M. N. (2021). The theme feminism in the epistolary novels in modern times. ISJ Theoretical & Applied Science, 11 (103), 1101-1105. So: <http://s-o-i.org/1.1/TAS-11-103-124> Doi: <https://dx.doi.org/10.15863/TAS.2021.11.103.124>

10. Norova M.F. Connotative meanings in phonetic variants of verbal root-stems (as an example of the English and Uzbek languages) // Research & Development. EPRA International Online Journal. – India, 2020. – №10(5). – P. 358-362. (Impact Factor SJIF 7.001).
11. [O'zME](#). Birinchi jild. Toshkent, 2000-yil
12. Khayrullayeva, K. R. (2020). Description of Zahiriddin Babur's achievements in various fields in the works of Uzbek and world authors. ISJ Theoretical & Applied Science, 09 (89), 8-11. SoI: <http://s-o-i.org/1.1/TAS-09-89-2> Doi: <https://dx.doi.org/10.15863/TAS.2020.09.89.2>
13. Khayrullayeva Kamola Ravshanovna. INTERPRETATION OF ZAHIRIDDIN MUHAMMAD BABUR'S IMAGE IN UZBEK AND WORLD LITERATURE. EPRA International Journal of Research and Development (IJRD), Volume: 5 | Issue: 5 | May 2020. SJIF Impact Factor: 7.001| ISI I.F.Value:1.241| Journal DOI: 10.36713/epra2016. ISSN: 2455-7838(Online).
14. Khayrullayeva Kamola Ravshanovna. (2022). THE IMAGE OF BABUR AS KING AND LEGATE IN WESTERN ENGLISH AND UZBEK PROSE. *JournalNX - A Multidisciplinary Peer Reviewed Journal*, 8(2), 134–138. <https://doi.org/10.17605/OSF.IO/PNJZD>
15. Ravshanovna, Khayrullayeva Kamola. "The image of babur mirza in the interpretation of stephen meredith." *ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal* 11.11 (2021): 239-244.
16. Kamoliddin Abdullaev (2002). Tojikistonning tarixiy lug'ati. Rouan va Littlefield. 94-102 betlar. ISBN 978-1-5381-0251-0.
17. Ostonova Sanam Nematovna. (2021). TRADITIONAL COMPILATION MAJOR TRANSLATION IN NATIONAL CULTUR. *World Bulletin of Social Sciences*, 3(10), 49-53. Retrieved from <https://scholarexpress.net/index.php/wbss/article/view/168>
18. Ziyodillaeva Mahbuba Ermatovna. (2022). ITERLINGUISTIC FEATURES OF AMERICAN ENGLISH AND MEXICAN SPANISH. SOCIOLINGUISTIC RESEARCH ON CHICANO ENGLISH. *Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal*, 10(2), 328–332.
19. Остонова, С. Н. National traditions and rituals in modern Uzbekistan (basing on the analysis of Uzbek traditional meal «Palov») / С. Н. Остонова. — Текст : непосредственный // Молодой ученый. — 2020. — № 47 (337). — С. 199-203. — URL: <https://moluch.ru/archive/337/75335/> (дата обращения: 28.10.2021).
20. <https://www.pshares.org/issues/spring-2005/about-mart%C3%ADn-espada>
21. https://www.amazon.com/Books-Mart%C3%ADn-Espada/s?rh=n%3A283155%2Cp_27%3AMart%C3%ADn+Espada
22. <https://www.easternct.edu/big-read/bios/martin-espada.html>

АБУЛ БАРАКОТ НАСАФИЙ ИЛМИЙ МЕРОСИНИНГ ТАСНИФИ

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KALIT SO'ZLAR

аллома, фикҳ, усул, ақида,
тафсири, манба, матн,
шарҳ, мерос.

ANNOTATSIYA

Мақолада ҳанафий мактабининг забардаст фақиҳи, атоқли муфассир, машхур имом аллома Ҳофизиддин Абул Баракот Насафий ҳаёти ва илмий мероси ҳақида сўз юритилган. Олимнинг тафсири, ақида ва фикҳ йўналишларида ёзган беназир китоблари ҳақида атрофлича маълумотлар берилган. Шунингдек, унинг устоз ва шогирдлари зикр қилиниб, манбаларда унга берилган таърифлар келтирилган.

Юртимизда ўзининг бебаҳо мероси билан дунёга танилган кўплаб буюк аллома ва мутафаккирлар етишиб чиққан. Улар ақл-заковати, тафаккур дунёси ва юксак илмий салоҳиятининг маҳсули бўлган беназир асарлари ҳамда буюк кашфиётлари билан нафақат юртимиз, балки жаҳон аҳлининг маънавий мулки сифатида ҳам қадрланади.

Ўрта Осиёнинг боқий шаҳарлари ҳисобланган Бухоро, Самарқанд, Хива каби Қашқадарё воҳасининг йирик шаҳри Насафда ҳам асрлар мобайнида улкан ва бебаҳо мерос яратган буюк аждодларимиз яшаб ўтган. Ана шундай алломалардан бири атоқли муфассир, машхур имом ва фикҳ илмининг билимдони Абул Баракот Насафийдир.

Мутафаккирнинг тўлиқ исми

Ҳофизиддин Абул Баракот Абдуллоҳ
ибн Аҳмад ибн Маҳмуд Насафий бўлиб,

туғилган йили ҳақида аниқ маълумот йўқ, бироқ Муҳаммад Шафиқ Ғирболнинг “ал-Мавсуа ал-арабия ал- муяссара” (“Арабий енгил қомус”) асарида унинг таваллуди милодий 629/1232 йил деб кўрсатилган [1].

Абул Баракот Насафийнинг етук олим бўлиб етишишида устозларининг ўрни беқиёсдир. Манбаларда унинг асосан учта устозлари тилга олинади. Насафий “Шамсул аимма” (“Имомлар кўёши”) унвонига сазовор бўлган машҳур олим Муҳаммад ибн Абдуссаттор ибн Муҳаммад Кардарий (ваф. 642/1244 й.) [2], Хоҳарзода номи билан танилган Бадриддин Муҳаммад ибн Маҳмуд ибн Абдулкарим Кардарий (ваф. 652/1254 й.) ҳамда ўз асрининг таниқли имомларидан бири бўлган Али ибн Муҳаммад ибн Али Ҳамидуддин Дарир Ромиший Бухорий (ваф.

666/1267-8 й.) сингари устозлардан сабоқ олган. Ромиший вафот этганда шогирди Насафий устозига ўзи жаноза ўқиб, қабрга қўйган [3].

Абул Баракот Насафийнинг Абу Ҳанифагача бўлган устозлар шажараси қуйидагича: Шамсул аимма Кардарий, Ҳасан ибн Али Марғиноний (ваф. 599/1203 й.), Абд Азиз ибн Умар ибн Моза (ваф. 535/1141 й.), Маҳмуд ибн Абд Азиз Ўзгандий, Абу Бакр Муҳаммад Шамсул аимма Сарахсий (ваф. 482/1090 й.), Шамсул аимма Ҳалвоний (ваф. 455/1063 й.), Абу Али Насафий (ваф. 403/1013 й.), Абу Бакр Фадл (ваф. 380/991 й.), Абдуллоҳ Субазмуний (ваф. 340/951-2 й.), Абу Ҳафс Сағир, унинг отаси Абу Ҳафс Кабир, Имом Муҳаммад Шайбоний, Имом Абу Ҳанифа [4].

Кардарий каби машҳур олимнинг илм уммонидан баҳраманд бўлган Насафий “Ҳафиз уд-дин”, яъни “динни ҳимоя қилувчи” деган шарафли номга муяссар бўлган. Бу номга алломалардан икки кишигина сазовор бўлган бўлиб, булардан иккинчиси Ҳофизиддин Абул Фадл Муҳаммад ибн Муҳаммад ибн Наср Кабир Бухорийдир.

Насафий ўз замонасининг етук олимлари ҳисобланган кўплаб шогирдларни етиштириб чиқарган. Жумладан, ҳуқуқшунос, фақиҳ, адабиётшунос, “Мажмаъ ал-баҳрайн” (“Икки денгизнинг бирлашиш жойи”) асарининг муаллифи Ибн Соатий номи билан машҳур бўлган Музаффариддин Аҳмад ибн Али ибн Тағлиб (ваф. 694/1294-5 й.), “Ҳидоя”га шарҳ ёзган таниқли ҳанафий фақиҳ Ҳисомиддин Ҳусайн ибн Али ибн Ҳажжож Сиғноқий

(ваф. 714 х.), фиқҳ ва усулда илм уммони бўлган имом Алоуддин Абдулазиз ибн Аҳмад ибн Муҳаммад Бухорий (ваф. 730 х.) ҳамда ҳанафий мазҳабининг буюк олимларидан бири Муҳаммад ибн Муҳаммад ибн Аҳмад Хўжандий Кокий (ваф. 749 х.) кабилар унинг шогирдлари қаторида зикр қилинади.

Абул Барокат Насафийнинг ҳанафий мазҳабига асосланиб ёзилган “Канз ад-дақоик” номли фиқҳий асаридан унинг устози Кардарийга мувофиқ фиқҳда Абу Ҳанифа мазҳабига эргашганини билиш мумкин. Эътиқодда у Имом Мотурудия таълимотини қўллаб-қувватлаган.

Абул Баракот Насафий Насаф шаҳрида туғилиб, вояга етган бўлса-да, Бухорода таълим олиб, жуда кўплаб мамлакатларга саёҳат қилган, ҳамма жойда ўз билими билан обрў-эътибор топган. Бир муддат Кермон шаҳридаги ал-Қутбия ас-султония мадрасасида мударрислик қилган. Талабаларга Имом Мотуридий, Марғиноний ва ўз асарларидан сабоқ берган. Сўнгра Бағдодга келган. Бу даврда у дарс бериш билан бирга кўплаб машҳур олимларнинг асарларига шарҳлар ёзган [5].

Серқирра олимнинг илмий мероси улкан бўлиб, ундан кўплаб матн ва шарҳлар қолган. Аллома ҳанафий мактабининг забардаст фақиҳларидан бўлиб, илм таҳсили, асар таснифи, танқид ҳамда таҳлил бўйича ўз йўналишига эга бўлган. Тарихий манбаларда унинг етук муфассир ва моҳир усулчи экани ҳам қайд этилган. Унинг бебаҳо асарлари бугунги кунга қадар олим ва талабалар орасида

мўътабар манбалар сифатида қадрланиб ўқилмоқда, тадқиқотчилар томонидан ўрганиб келиниб, кенг ва самарали фойдаланилмоқда.

Абул Баракот Насафий тафсир, ақида, фикҳ ҳамда усул ал-фикҳ илмларида асарлар ёзган.

Аллома тафсир соҳасида “Мадорик ат-танзил ва ҳақоик ат-таъвил” (“Қуръон маънолари ва таъвил ҳақиқатлари”) асарини ёзган. Ушбу асар “Тафсир ан-Насафий” номи билан машҳур бўлиб, у ҳанафий мазҳаби қонун-қоидалари асосида ёзилган ҳамда ундаги оятлар мотуридия таълимотига биноан баён этилган.

Унда ислом дини асоси саналган Қуръон мазмуни шарҳланган ҳамда Насафийнинг бошқа асарларида бўлган муҳим ақидавий ва фикҳий масалалар ўз аксини топган. Шунингдек, “Тафсир ан-Насафий”да ислом оламида машҳур бўлган асарлардаги энг эътиборли фикрлар ва муаллифнинг кенг дунёқараши, илғор ғоялари, бутун илмий маҳорати жамлангани боис мазкур тафсирга юқори баҳо берилади [6].

Тафсирга Ҳожи Халифа қуйидагича таъриф берган: “Бу таъвилотга доир бўлган, турли ҳаракат услублари ва қироатлар жамланган, бадиъ (балоғат) ва ишоралар илмининг нозик жиҳатларини ўзида мужассам қилган, аҳли сунна вал жамоа ақидасига мувофиқ келадиган, бидъат аҳли ва адашганлар сўзларидан холи бўлган, малоллик туғдирмайдиган ҳамда тушунарсиз даражада қисқа бўлмаган китобдир” [7].

Юқорида келтирилган таърифлар “Тафсир ан-Насафий” асарининг бебаҳолигига далолат қилиб, диний бағрикенглик тамойилларига ҳамоҳанглиги, мавзу, услуб ва илмларининг кенгқамровлиги сабаб асрлар оша ўқиб, ўрганилиб келинмоқда.

Олимнинг калом илмига оид “Умдат ал-ақоид” (“Ақидалар асоси”) асари “Умдату ақидати аҳли сунна вал жамоа” (“Аҳли сунна вал жамоа ақидаси асоси”), “Умдату фи ал-иътиқад” (“Эътиқоддаги асос”) ҳамда “Умдату фи усул ад-дин” (“Усул ад-диндаги асос”) номлари билан ҳам аталади. Ҳожи Халифа унга: “Бу калом илмининг энг муҳим қоидаларини ўз ичига олган мухтасар асар бўлиб, инсонлар қалбидаги имон-эътиқодларини тиниқлаштиради”, деб таъриф берган [8].

“Ал-Иътимод” (“Таянч”) асари муаллифнинг ўзи томонидан “Умдат ал-ақоид”га ёзган шарҳи ҳисобланади. У “ал-Иътимад фи ал-иътиқод”, (“Эътиқоддаги таянч”) “Иътимод фи шарҳ ал-Умдат” (“Умда” шарҳидаги таянч”) ҳамда “Шарҳ ал-Умдат” (“Умда” шарҳи”) номлари билан ҳам аталади.

Алломанинг “Баҳр ал-калом” (“Калом илми денгизи”) номли асари ҳам калом илмига оид ҳисобланади.

Имом Насафий фикҳ соҳасида “Ҳидоя”дан кейинги ўринда турадиган “Канз ад-дақоик” (“Нозик масалалар хазинаси”) номли асар ёзган. Фикҳий масалалар кенг ёритилган ушбу асарда Абу Ханифа, Абу Юсуф, Имом Муҳаммад ва бошқа мужтаҳид олимларнинг

фикрлари, ривоятлари келтирилган, ибодат, муомалот, жазо ва шу каби масалалар баён этилган. Асар ҳанафий фикридаги энг яхши, машҳур ҳамда кўп шарҳланган мухтасарлардан бири саналади.

Абул Баракотнинг ислом ҳуқуқшунослигига оид яна бир мўтабар асари “ал-Вофий” (“Мукамал”)дир. Бу асар шу даражада қадрланадигани, ҳатто баъзи олимлар уни Бурҳониддин Марғинонийнинг “Ҳидоя”си қаторида кўрадилар. Унда “Жомеъ ас-сағир” (“Кичик мажмуа”), “Жомеъ ал-кабир” (“Катта мажмуа”), “Зиёdot” (“Зиёда масалалар”) ва “Мухтасар ал-Қудурий” (“Қудурийнинг қисқартирилгани”)даги масалалар жамланган. Шу билан бир қаторда унда фатво ҳамда “Манзумат ал-хилофият” (“Қиёсий ҳуқуқшуносликка оид назм”) китобларидаги баъзи масалалар ҳам ўрин олган [9].

“Ал-Кофий” (“Кифоя қилувчи”) муаллифнинг “ал-Вофий” асарига ёзган шарҳи ҳисобланади. Унинг муқаддимасида Насафий: “Ал-Вофий” деб номланган мухтасар асарни ниҳоясига етказиб, узайиб кетишдан ҳоли бўлган, хулосаларни ўз ичига олган, ноаниқ ибораларга ойдинлик киритган унинг шарҳи “ал-Кофий” асарини ёздим”, деган [10].

Ҳофизиддин Насафий Имом Абул Қосим Муҳаммад ибн Юсуф Ҳасаний Самарқандий (ваф. 1161 й.) қаламига мансуб “ал-Фикҳ ан-Нофеъ” (“Фойдали фикҳ”) асарига “ал-Мустасфо” (“Мукамал”) номли шарҳ ёзган. “Ал-Мустасфо” асари муҳим фикҳий манбалардан ҳисобланиб, унда фикҳий

далилларга алоҳида эътибор қаратилган, далил келтириш услублари аниқ баён этилган ҳамда масалаларнинг асл негизи очиб берилган. Муаллиф асардаги масалалар ва унга боғлиқ вазиятларни чуқур таҳлил қилиб, масалага доир муаммоларни ҳал қилган ва савол-жавоб тариқасида мантиқий-фаразий қоидалардан ҳам фойдаланган.

Шунингдек, Насафий Абу Ҳафс Умар ибн Муҳаммад Насафийнинг “ал-Манзума ал-хилафия” (“Фарқли қарашлар ҳақида манзума”) асарига “ал-Мусаффо” (“Аниқланган”) шарҳини ёзган. Асарда фикҳий масалалар бўйича мазҳаб мужтаҳид олимларининг ихтилофи қарашлари қасида ва байтлар шаклида намоён бўлган.

Олимнинг “ал-Манор” (“Маёқ”) номли асари усул ал-фикҳ ва унинг қонун-қоидалари ҳақида бўлиб, унда Қуръон ва ҳадис асосида ҳукм олиш, ижмо ва қиёс қўллаш услублари каби масалалар ёритилган. У олимлар томонидан усул ал-фикҳ соҳасидаги фойдали асарлардан бири сифатида эътироф этилади. Ҳожи Халифа унга: “Бу асарларнинг асари, кенгқамровли, мухтасар, фойдали, ўзига ўхшаш кенг ва ихчам китоблар ичида энг кўп ўқиладигани, ҳажми кичкина, матни қисқа бўлишига қарамай, ҳақиқатларга тўла денгиз ҳамда дақиқ иборалардан иборат хазина мисолидир”, деб таъриф берган [11].

“Ал-Манор” асарига Насафий “Кашф ал-асрор” (“Сирларни очиш”) номли шарҳ ёзган бўлиб, асарда Шамсул аймма Сарахсийнинг усул қоидаларидан кўп фойдаланган.

Абдулхай Лакнавий ўзининг “ал-Фавоид ал-бахия фи тарожим ал-ҳанафия” (“Ҳанафий фақиҳларнинг таржимаи ҳоллари ҳақида қимматли маълумотлар”) асарида Абу Баракот Насафийнинг Имом Ахсикатий қаламига мансуб “Мунтахаб” (“Танланган”) асарига ва ўзининг “Манор” асарига иккитадан шарҳ ёзганини қайд қилган. Шунингдек, у олимнинг бир қанча мўътабар асарларини тилга олиб, уларнинг фойдали, фақиҳлар наздида мўътабар ҳамда олимлар назарида манзур эканини айтиб ўтган [12].

Исломшунос олим Д.Махсудов олимнинг манбаларда зикр қилинмаган “Доират ал-вусул ила илм ал-усул» («Усул илмига етишиш йўли») қўлёзма асари мавжудлигини аниқлаган бўлиб, у Покистоннинг Акурахтак шаҳридаги “Дор ал-улум ал-ҳаққония” кутубхонасида 4625/247 рақами билан сақланмоқда [13].

“Ҳадият ал-аърифин” (“Орифларнинг ҳадяси”) асарининг муаллифи Исмоил Боша Бағдодий алломанинг “Фазоил ал-аъмал” (“Амалларнинг фазилатлари”) ҳамда “ал-Лаолий ал-фахироҳ фи улуми ал-ахироҳ” (“Охират илмлари ҳақида ажойиб марваридлар”) каби асарлари номини зикр қилган [14]. Бироқ, баъзи китоблардаги ишоралардан ташқари бу асарларга оид маълумотлар учрамайди.

Юқорида номлари зикр қилинган асарлар Насафийнинг диний илмлардаги кенг қиррали билими ва бой илмий меросидан далолат беради. Асарларда кўтарилган масалаларнинг

долзарблиги боис уларга асрлар оша кўплаб шарҳ ва ҳошиялар битилган.

Аллома ҳақида манбаларда турли таърифлар келтирилган. Абдулхай Лакнавий ўзининг “ал-Фавоид ал-бахия фи тарожим ал-ҳанафия” асарида: “Абдуллоҳ ибн Аҳмад ибн Маҳмуд Абул Барокат ан-Насафий замонасининг тенги йўқ комил имоми, фикҳ ва усулда етакчи, ҳадис ва унинг маъноларини билувчи жуда кучли олим эди”, деган. Шунингдек, ўз асарида Ибн Камол Бошонинг Насафий ҳақида: “Кучли билан заифни ажрата оладиган, асарларида мардуд сўзлар ва кучсиз ривоятларни келтирмайдиган муқаллид, фақиҳ олимлар жамоасидандир. У билан ижтиҳод даври тугаган, ундан кейин мазҳабда ижтиҳод қиладиган мужтаҳид қолмаган”, деб айтган гапини келтирган [15].

Ибн Тағрий Бардий унинг ҳаёт йўли, баъзи ахлоқ ва сифатларини зикр қилиб: “Имом, аллома, шайхул ислом, диннинг ҳимоячиси, зоҳид уламолардан бири, фикҳ, усул, араб тили ва бошқа илмларда фойдали асарлар муаллифи. Бир гуруҳ етук олимлардан таҳсил олган ҳамда фикҳ, усул, араб тили ва луғат илмларида етук бўлган. Бир неча йиллар фатво чиқариб, таълим берган. Ўз даврининг кўплаб олимлари ундан манфаат олганлар. Илм ва унинг амали натижаси сифатида ҳанафий мазҳабига раислик қилган. Шу билан бир қаторда у гўзал хулқли, ўта камтар, каломи фасоҳатли, тили равон, фақир ва толиби илмларга меҳрибон ҳамда яхшилик қилувчи инсон. Ўзини меҳнат, касб ва асарларга бағишлаган. Олим, имом, зоҳид, тақводор ва камтар бўлган.

Аксарият олимлар у зотнинг илми ва динини мақтаган”, деган таърифни берган [16].

Сирожиддин ибн Нужайм “Канз” шарҳининг муқаддимасида уни: “Мутааххирларнинг энг афзали, олимларнинг энг мукаммали, миллат ва дин ҳимоячиси ва тадқиқотчиларнинг таянчидир” деб васф қилган [17].

Тақиюддин ибн Абдулқодир Ғозий унга: “Мутааххир зоҳид ва ҳақиқий олимлардан бири, фикҳ ва усулдаги фойдали асарлар соҳиби” деган таърифни берган [18].

Абул Баракот Насафий 1310 йилда Бағдодга келган ва шу йили рабиул-аввал ойининг жума куни

кечаси Бағдодда вафот этган ҳамда Исфаҳон яқинидаги Изаж шаҳрида дафн қилинган.

Мутааххир уламоларнинг зоҳидларидан бўлган алломанинг айрим китоблари ва уларнинг шарҳлари ҳали етарлича ўрганилмаган. Бу эса ушбу асарлар устида илмий тадқиқот ва изланишлар олиб бориш лозимлигини тақозо этади. Зеро, Насафий асарларидаги масалаларнинг долзарблиги бугунги кун учун ҳам ғоятда аҳамиятлидир. Шундай экан, алломанинг ҳаёти, фаолияти, асарларини тадқиқ қилиш ҳамда уларнинг моҳиятини очиб бериш муҳим вазифалардан ҳисобланади.

References:

1. Муҳаммад Шафиқ Ғирбол. Ал-Мавсуа ал-арабия ал-муяссара. Дор ал-жилд вал-жамъийат ал-мисрия, 1995. Ж. II. – Б. 1833.
2. Абул Вафо Қураший. Ал-жавоҳир ал-мудия фи табақот ал-ҳанафия. Дору Ҳижр, 1993. Ж. III. – Б. 228-230.
3. Абул Фидо Зайниддин Қосим ибн Қутлубуға. Таж ат-тарожим. Байрут: Дар ал-қалам, 1992. – Б. 215.
4. Даврон Махсудов. Абул Баракот Насафий. – Тошкент: Ўзбекистон халқаро ислом академияси нашриёт-матбаа бирлашмаси, 2021. – Б. 7.

BOLALAR INTELEKTINI RIVOJLANTIRISH USULLARI

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KALIT SO'ZLAR

Maktabgacha yoshdagi
bolalar, pedagogik
jarayonlar, psixologiya,
aqliy rivojlanish, aqliy
qobiliyat, rivojlanish, ta'lim
tizimi, faoliyat jarayonlari.

ANNOTATSIYA

Katta yoshdagi maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarning intellektual rivojlanishi kognitiv jarayonlar majmuasi bilan belgilanadi: diqqat, idrok, fikrlash, xotira, tasavvur. Katta maktabgacha yoshda bola boshlang'ich maktab yoshidagi etakchi faoliyatga - ta'limga tayyorlanishi kerak. Bunda aqliy qobiliyatlarni rivojlantirish va bolalarda tegishli ko'nikmalarni shakllantirish muhim ahamiyatga ega bo'ladi. Maktabgacha yoshdagi bolaning rivojlanishi faqat uning uchun tabiiy, eng jozibali faoliyat shaklida - o'yinda amalga oshirilishi mumkin. O'yin g'oyasiga berilib ketgan bola, buni amalga oshirishda qiyinchiliklarga duch kelsa ham, "o'rganayotganini" sezmaydi. Pedagogik jarayonda o'quv o'yinlari va boshqotirmalardan foydalanish ta'lim faoliyatini qayta qurish, bolalar bilan odatiy mashg'ulotlardan kattalar bilan birgalikda yoki mustaqil ravishda tashkil etilgan kognitiv o'yin faoliyatiga o'tish imkonini beradi. O'qituvchi faqat bundan foydalanishi kerak tabiiy ehtiyoj bolalarni o'yin faoliyatining yanada murakkab va ijodiy shakllariga jalb qilish lozim. Ushbu maqolada, bolalar intellektini rivojlantirish usullari haqida fikr va mulohazalar yuritiladi.

KIRISH. O'quv o'yinlari - bu ijodiy jarayonning o'zini taqlid qiladigan va o'zlarining mikroiklimini yaratadigan o'yinlar, bu erda intellektning ijodiy tomonini rivojlantirish imkoniyatlari paydo bo'ladi. Ishda maktabgacha ta'lim muassasalari tarbiyaviy o'yinlar katta o'rin tutadi. Ular tashkil etilgan o'quv faoliyatida va bolalarning mustaqil faoliyatida

qo'llaniladi. Bunday o'yin o'quv vositasi sifatida xizmat qilishi mumkin ajralmas

qismi ta'lim faoliyati. Bu bilimlarni o'zlashtirishga, mustahkamlashga, yo'llarni o'zlashtirishga yordam beradi kognitiv faoliyat. Bolalar ob'ektlarning belgilarini o'zlashtiradilar,

tasnif

lashni,

umumlashtirishni,

taqqoslashni

o'rganadilar. Katta yoshdagi maktabgacha yoshdagi

bolalarning

e'tibori

o'zboshimchalik bilan emas, etarlicha barqaror emas, cheklangan doirada.

Ixtiyoriy diqqat boshqa funktsiyalar va

birinchi navbatda, o'rganish motivatsiyasi, o'quv faoliyatining muvaffaqiyati uchun javobgarlik hissi bilan birga rivojlanadi.

Maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarning intellektual qobiliyatlarini rivojlantirish dolzarb masala zamonaviy maktabgacha ta'lim. Bugungi kunda jamiyatda muammolarga nostandart nuqtai nazarga ega, odamlar, axborot oqimlari bilan ishlashga qodir, o'zgaruvchan sharoitlarga tez moslasha oladigan ijodkorlarni tarbiyalashga bo'lgan ehtiyoj ayniqsa keskinlashdi. Maktabgacha yoshda bilimlarni to'plash jadal davom etadi, nutq shakllanadi, kognitiv jarayonlar yaxshilanadi, bola aqliy faoliyatning eng oddiy usullarini o'zlashtiradi. Maktabgacha yoshda intellektning intensiv rivojlanishi bolalarning maktabda o'qish foizini oshirishi isbotlangan. Axir, bolaligidanoq uning ongida nima qo'yish mumkin bo'lsa, u butun umrga qoladi.

ADABIYOTLAR TAHLILI VA METODOLOGIYA.

Intellektual rivojlangan, aqlli shaxslar har doim katta narxda bo'lgan. Turli sohalarda yaxshi bilim zaxirasi bilan ajralib turadigan odam boshqa odamlardan ustunlikka ega, bu esa muvaffaqiyatga olib keladi. kasbiy faoliyat. Rivojlangan aql va eruditsiyani farqlash kerak. Axir, siz juda ko'p qiziqarli ma'lumotlarni bilishingiz mumkin, ammo tahlil qilish, taqqoslash va mantiqiy fikr yurita olmaysiz. Bugungi kunda aql-zakovatni rivojlantirishning ko'plab usullari mavjud bo'lib, ulardan juda erta yoshdan foydalanish mumkin.

Inson psixikasi ma'lum bir tarzda idrok etish qobiliyati ekanligini bilish dunyo va unga javob bersangiz, aql nima ekanligini tushunish qiyin emas. - inson faoliyatining barcha jabhalarini qamrab oluvchi

psixikaning sifati: aqliy, hissiy va jismoniy. Bu insonning rivojlanish darajasiga qarab turli vaziyatlarga moslashish qobiliyatidir. Boshqacha qilib aytganda, rivojlangan intellekt - bu ichki dunyo boyligi bilan jismoniy rivojlanishning uyg'unligi, barkamol rivojlangan shaxsning sinonimidir. Bu rivojlanishni bilasizmi intellektual qobiliyatlar bola ajralmas qismidir uyg'un rivojlanish ma'naviy va jismoniy tarbiyani o'z ichiga oladi?" Ko'pgina ota-onalar o'zlariga savol berishadi: nima uchun bolada aql-idrok rivojlanadi? Javob aniq: bola tez, oson va samarali o'rganishi, olingan bilimlardan muvaffaqiyatli foydalanishi, kelajakda kashfiyotlar qilishi yoki boshqalar qila olmaydigan narsalarni qilishni o'rganishi uchun. Shuning uchun aqlni rivojlantirishga erta bolalikdan e'tibor berish kerak.

NATIJALAR.

Avvalo, intellekt darajasi (intellekt koeffitsienti, IQ) bolaning aqliy qobiliyatida namoyon bo'ladi. Fikrlash bevosita jismoniy faoliyat bilan bog'liq. Harakat qilish, emaklash, yugurish, ko'lmaklarni oyoq osti qilish yoki qum bilan o'ynash chaqaloq atrofidagi haqiqatni o'rganadi, miyasini rivojlantiradi. Shu sababli, cheklash kerak emas vosita faoliyati crumbs, unga dunyoni mustaqil ravishda kashf qilish imkonini beradi. Kichik yoshdagi o'quvchilar stol yoki kompyuter mantiqiy o'yinlarini o'ynash orqali intellektual rivojlanadi. O'yin - har qanday narsa uchun o'rganishni tashkil qilishning ajoyib usuli. Qabul qiling, aqliy qobiliyatlarning rivojlanishi ko'zga tashlanmaydigan muhitda sodir bo'lganda ancha yaxshi bo'ladi. Bundan ham qiziqroq narsa - o'smirlarni qanday qilib intellektual

rivojlantirish. Maktab o'quv dasturi yildan-yilga murakkablashib bormoqda va shuning uchun birinchi imtihonlar intellektual qiyinchiliklarga duch kelgan talabalar uchun haqiqiy sinov bo'lishi mumkin. Yoshlik jismoniy va aqliy sohalaridagi o'zgarishlar, shuningdek, kognitiv qiziqishning biroz pasayishi bilan tavsiflanadi. Bu yerda ota-onalar o'smirlarning intellektual rivojlanishini qanday rag'batlantirish haqida ehtiyotkorlik bilan o'ylashlari kerak, ularni nafaqat ko'proq o'qishga majbur qilish kerak.

MUHOKAMA.

Bolaning aqliy rivojlanishi ma'lum omillarga bog'liq:

1. Genetik omillar. Bu bola tug'ilganda ota-onasidan olgan narsaga ishora qiladi. Bolaning intellektual rivojlanish darajasi, sifati va yo'nalishi ko'p jihatdan ana shu omillarga bog'liq.
2. Onaning homiladorligi davrida yuzaga keladigan omillar. Homilador ayolning turmush tarzi bolaning aqliy rivojlanishida namoyon bo'ladi. Masalan, tug'ilmagan bolaning aqliy zaiflashishiga quyidagilar ta'sir qilishi mumkin: noto'g'ri ovqatlanish, onada yod tanqisligi, homiladorlik paytida kasallik, dori-darmonlarni qabul qilish, spirtli ichimliklar, giyohvand moddalarni iste'mol qilish, chekish.
3. Ekologik omillar. Chaqaloqlarning aqliy faoliyatidagi buzilishlar quyidagi sabablarga ko'ra yuzaga kelishi mumkin: bolalarda noto'g'ri ovqatlanish, aloqa yetishmasligi, vosita va kognitiv faoliyatga cheklovlar to'liq bo'lmagan oila.
4. Katta oila omili. Tadqiqotlar shuni ko'rsatdiki, to'ng'ichlar oiladagi boshqa bolalarga qaraganda ko'proq aqliy rivojlangan. Biroq, ichida katta oilalar

bolalar ijtimoiy jihatdan yaxshiroq rivojlanadi: ular muloqot qilish qobiliyatini osongina egallaydilar va jamiyatga tezda moslashadilar.

5. Oilaning ijtimoiy mavqei omili. Juda kambag'al oilalar farzandlari har doim ham ota-onalarini maktabdagi natijalari bilan xursand qilishmaydi.

6. Maktab ta'sir omili. Aksariyat umumta'lim maktablarida o'qituvchilar hali ham xotirjam, savollarga undan talab qilinadigan tarzda javob beradigan, so'ramasdan hech narsa qilmaydigan yaxshi o'quvchi deb hisoblashadi. Bu xususiyatlar yuqori ijodiy salohiyatga ega bo'lgan bolalarga mos kelmaydi: muammolarni hal qilishda nostandart yondashuvni ko'rsatadiganlar. Ta'limga individual va o'quvchiga yo'naltirilgan yondashuvlar bugungi kunda maktabda bolalarning aqliy rivojlanishini rag'batlantiradi.

7. Bolaning shaxsiy fazilatlari omili. Aqliy qobiliyatlarning rivojlanishiga bolaning xarakteri va temperamenti ham ta'sir qiladi. O'ychan bolalar murakkab vazifalarga e'tiborli, ammo ular ishonchsiz va muvaffaqiyatsizlikdan qo'rqishadi. Qo'zg'aluvchan bolalar biroz yuzaki, lekin o'z-o'zidan ijodiy impulslarni namoyish etishga qodir.

8. Ota-onalarning shaxsiy fazilatlari omili. Ota-onalar intellektual rivojlangan, muvaffaqiyatli, o'ziga ishongan, o'z ishini sevsa yaxshi bo'ladi: bunday sharoitda bolalar tezroq rivojlanadi. Biroq, bu aqli bolani tarbiyalashning asosiy sharti emas. Ta'limdagi asosiy narsa - ota-onalarning g'amxo'rliqi va bolalarning kuchiga ishonish.

Bolaning aqliy rivojlanishining rivojlanish darajasini bilib, siz unga to'g'ri ta'lim

usullarini tanlashingiz mumkin. IQ darajasini aniqlash uchun maxsus foydalaning. Chaqaloqlar uchun - yorqin rasmlar, qaysini hisobga olgan holda va savollarga javob berib, bola o'z aqlining ma'lum darajasini namoyish etadi. Maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarni maxsus topshiriqlar va anketalar yordamida tashxislash mumkin. Maktab o'quvchilarining IQ darajasini tekshirish uchun psixologik testlar qo'llaniladi. Ular turli sohalarda razvedkani o'rganishga qaratilgan bloklar shaklida qurilgan. Natijalarga e'tibor qaratib, u ma'lumotni qanday yaxshi qabul qilishini bilib olishingiz mumkin.

Bolaning rivojlanishi uchun uning tadqiqot faoliyatini rag'batlantirish kerak. Ota-onalar u yoki bu narsani aniqlashga, ob'ektni uzoqdan batafsilroq ko'rib chiqishga yoki erdan qiziqarli narsalarni ushlab harakat qilayotgan qiziquvchan chaqaloqni doimiy ravishda orqaga tortib olishlari odatiy hol emas. Bunday xulq-atvor bilan tabiiy qiziqish va izlanish tezda yo'qoladi va bolaning o'rganishga qiziqishi yo'qoladi. Ammo, shu bilan birga, chaqaloq

boshqa odamlar bilan o'zaro munosabatlar me'yorlarini singdirishi va oldindan ruxsatisiz boshqa birovni tortib olish mumkin emasligini aniq ajratib ko'rsatishi kerak.

Xulosa qilib aytganda, biz, o'qituvchilar va ota-onalar, tafakkurning shakllanishi hayotning birinchi yillaridan boshlanishini unutmashimiz kerak. Fikrlash boshlang'ich maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalar pedagogika, psixologiya, fiziologiya, umumiy tilshunoslik, sotsiologiya, psixolingvistika kabi turli bilim sohalari vakillarining e'tiborini tortadi. Har bir fan o'zining maxsus muammolarini hal qilishda bir vaqtning o'zida umumiy savollarga ham to'xtaladi. Bolalar tafakkurida bir xususiyat - sinkretizm mavjud bo'lib, u bolaga bir ob'ektni boshqasidan ajratmasdan, butun bloklar bo'yicha fikr yuritish imkonini beradi. Sinkretik xarakter bolalarning fikrlashi, ya'ni butun vaziyatlarda, yaxlit bog'langan qismlarda fikrlash shunchalik kuchliki, u hali ham maktab o'quvchisida og'zaki fikrlash sohasida qoladi va bolada fikrlashning transformativ shaklidir.

References:

1. Gunnar MR, Donzella B. Social regulation of the cortisol levels in early human development. *Psycho neuro endocrinology*. 2002;27(1-2):199–220-P
2. Gunnar MR, Morison SJ, Chisholm K, Schuder M. Salivary cortisol levels in children adopted from Romanian orphanages. *Development and Psychopathology*. 2001;13(3):611–628.P
3. Gweon H, Schulz L. 16-month-olds rationally infer causes of failed actions. *Science*. 2011;332(6037):1524.P
4. Hackman DA, Farah MJ. Socioeconomic status and the developing brain. *Trends in Cognitive Sciences*. 2009;13 (2):65–73.
5. <https://www.open.edu/openlearn/body-mind/childhood-youth/childhood-and-youth-studies/childhood/methods-studying-children-the-background>
6. <https://uz.inditics.com/oquvchilarning-intellektual-va-aqliy-rivojlanishini-rivojlantirish/>
7. <https://www.lfe.uni-leipzig.de/en/project/research-methods-in-early-child-development/>

THE MAGIC OF THE WORD IN THE PROCESS OF ARTISTIC TRANSLATION

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ABSTRACT

In this article, we will talk about the skills of artistic translation and several successful methods used in the direction of translation. Undoubtedly, the need to translate Uzbek literature, including poetry into Russian, arose for certain historical and social reasons, and Alexander Faynberg was one of the leaders in this field. The wider the range of topics studied in Uzbek literature and its translation, the wider the scope of unexplored topics. During the reading of the article, from the point of view of translation, it is possible to know that the recreation of poetic art in the artistic translation is not only one of the necessary conditions for giving the national originality reflected in the work, but also the preservation of the artistic juice of the original, the difference in terms of achieving emotional poetic translation has been analyzed and interpreted for centuries by philologists, poets, poetic scientists, specially engaged in the issues of poetic translation, and examples of the work of these poets are presented.

Artistic translation involves a complex creative process. Therefore, we rightly call the representative of this sphere a poet-translator. In a prose game, there is a plot, composition, narration and solution of events. That's why teacher poet Askad Mukhtar Talib, the translator is not a painter, he works as an artist, and through various methods of translation, including metonymic, transformational, implicit (hidden) meanings expressed (mufassal), the author seeks to convey his opinion to the reader more accurately. But the four

lines translate the tone and lyrical

performance in the poem to the extent that it takes place from the reader's heart, it is necessary to have poetic inspiration and skill. The main feature of artistic translation comes from the artistic task of the language. Language becomes an aesthetic phenomenon in artistic work. The language of literary work is a separate element of "artistic reality". In translation, there is a process of transferring the artistic meaning of this figurative expressive language to the figurative expressive ground of another language, re-representing the image. Therefore, the

translator re-perceives the process of artistic reflection of events in the work. Based on the requirements of modern translation, the translator must re-create the unity of form and content as a work of art, maintain national and individual characteristics. Restoration of the national form of the work of art is one of the important problems of artistic translation. In particular, the translation of poems from Russian into Uzbek requires a strong will and perseverance from the creator. Alexander Faynberg Arkadyevich also conducted extensive research in the field of translation, and he published in Moscow the poem "Rebellion of the spirits" by Erkin Vohidov, and in Tashkent the collection "White Tower", which is considered a collection of translations from the works of Uzbek poets. [1] Every product of his creativity does not remain without the admiration of the person. The translator re-inspired the poem, which was in harmony with his soul. Information should be noted that the work and activity of Alexander Faynberg are studied by many Uzbek scientists in various spheres. I must say that although Alexander Faynberg writes in Russian, it was not so difficult for me to understand it. Because it is enough to understand the images and symbols of the poet's poems, his soul, form and content. I spoke in Uzbek only what I understood. It's like watching a unique architectural monument and describing it as if it was this kind of those who did not see it, columns, it's kind of a feat. In this regard, I will give an example of the wonders of Alexander Faynberg's poetry, his artistic works and draw your attention to its Uzbek forms. [2] The poems of Alexander Faynberg, it is drawn from simple human feelings to

universal problems in pencil. He encourages people to embrace their pure, noble feelings, save human nature and the world from crisis. The well-being of the universe, the happiness of man, knows that he is holistic with the progress of the society in which he lives. When others are happy, I can not be unhappy, when others are unhappy, he says that I can not be happy. It calls on all members of the society to be united by the development of the hometown. In particular, I tried to translate the poem "word" into English, which was turned into Uzbek by Rustam Musurman, who is interested in the work of Alexander Faynberg and is engaged in silly - creative research in this regard, and I understand that in the work of the poet there are different colourful concepts. We will focus on the following lines:

Poezd kechikishi oddiy voqea,

Samolyotni kutib ichikadi ko'z.

Haqiqiy baxtsizlik, katta fojia –

Mabodo kechiksa kutilyotgan so'z. [3, 27-page]

We will try to discuss these sentences in the case of translation into English:

Train delay is an everyday occurrence,

My eyes are yearning for waiting for the plane.

Real misfortune, a great tragedy would be-

If the expected word is too late.

The first of these lines mentioned come from vehicles like "train" and "plane" in the same place because the reader may not be able to contemplate the contents of the poem. Why are these words quoted? What

does the poet mean by this? Another feature characteristic of Faynberg's poems is a full-fledged drawing of the landscapes of the human psyche. Whatever the poet does not write on the subject, he sees the work, as proceeding from the "spirit desire", as Navoi insists. Alexander was not among the poets who were satisfied with the image of his moods. He compared these Egyptians with the events that we understandably encounter in our everyday life. Likewise, the word being said is described as being late when a person is missing something. In the following sentences, the overview is described as confused, but the meaning remained:

So'ngan gulxan uzra bo'lgandek pushmon,
Kimsasiz kulbaga boqqandek mahzun.
Kechikkan so'z g'arib, yig'laydi yomon,
Uni kecha kutgan odamlar uchun.

The art of animation is used in these lines. Words that are delayed because of how many words need to be said are left without saying, expressed in such impressive phrases as "regret", "gloomy" and "crying badly."

English translation:

Over an extinguished fire as if remorseful
To a lonely hut as if sadly look.
Delayed word is poor, crying badly,
For the people waiting for it last night.

"The nightingale's evangelical journey sounds as pleasant to everyone as the poem of the fiery poets also resonates in all corners of the world, fascinates everyone, fascinates everyone, " said one of the teachers. Therefore, although the content

of this poem sounds in different languages, its original meaning is preserved in its original form. Essence:

Kechikkan so'z bois o'rmonlar yetim,
Bepoyon yerlarning peshonasi sho'r.
Qabrlar qoshida so'z ham beso'z, jim,
Ruhlar bezovtayu qismat ko'zi ko'r.

Translation form:

Because of dallying words, forests are orphans,

Vast lands are unfortunate.

Around the graves, the word itself is speechless, silent,

Soul is concerned, the eye of fate is blind.

So the poems of Alexander Faynberg spoke Uzbek. I also looked for news from the poems of Alexander Faynberg — I translated his poems, which the poet wrote, wishing to change both himself and others. The genres of Alexander Faynberg's poetry are diverse: epic, poem, film, quartet, and sonnet. He calls his sonnets free sonnets. [4] This retains the form of a sonnet but wants to innovate in the way of expression, content and spirit of the work, and free. This means that the command to translate poetry created in the eastern language into another language is incredibly difficult and laborious. To perform such a creative task, it is not enough that you are an amateur translator, you need to live in it, you need to relate your destiny and during to oriental poetry. Only then can you understand and feel the meaning of the language, mystery of this great poem, says the poet. Alexander Faynberg also achieved a high rank in his

fate for connecting his fate with Uzbek poetry and literature and selflessly serving this land and this person during his creative and social activities.

In conclusion, it should be said that in changing the worldview of man, motivating him to understand himself, to live consciously, educating the younger generation as a perfect person, in enriching

our spirituality, the poems of the poet like Alexander Faynberg are very important. The poems of the poet Alexander Faynberg in changing the worldview of man, motivating him to understand himself, to live consciously, to educate the younger generation as a perfect person, to enrich our spirituality are important to learn and do research on them.

References:

1. <https://arboblar.uz/ru/people/fajnberg-aleksandr-arkadevich>
2. <https://vesti.uz/zapoved-fajnberga-pishi-kak-dusha-lezhit/>
3. Sirojiddin Sayyid, Rustam Musurmon [matn]. T.: "Adabiyot" publishment, 2021. 27- bet
4. <https://mknizhnik.livejournal.com/106193.html>